

22NRM06 ADMIT

Deliverable D7

Letter from the IEC/CENELEC TC38 chair confirming contribution of the project results, related to the accuracy evaluation of instrument transformers in the frequency range up to 150 kHz, to future standards (IEC 61869 standard family)

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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**METROLOGY
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Glossary

AC (Alternating Current) : Alternating current that periodically reverses direction, typically used in power systems at 50 Hz.

Accuracy Class (IT) : Classification defining the permissible ratio and phase errors of an instrument transformer under specified operating conditions.

ADMIT : European Metrology project focused on the characterization of medium-voltage instrument transformers in the frequency range up to 150 kHz.

AWG (Arbitrary Waveform Generator) : Electronic instrument capable of generating arbitrary voltage waveforms including fundamental, harmonic, and supraharmonic components.

Band-pass Filter : Electronic filter that allows signals in a specified frequency range to pass while attenuating others.

Burden : Impedance connected to the secondary of an instrument transformer that affects its accuracy and frequency response.

Calibration : Process of comparing a measurement system with a reference standard to ensure accuracy and traceability.

Comparator : High-precision system used to compare outputs of a device under test with a reference device to determine measurement errors.

CT (Current Transformer) : Instrument transformer that provides a scaled secondary current proportional to the primary current for measurement or protection.

DC (Direct Current) : Electric current flowing in only one direction.

DUT (Device Under Test) : Device or system being measured or characterized during a test.

EMC (Electromagnetic Compatibility) : Ability of equipment to operate correctly in its electromagnetic environment without causing interference.

Expanded Uncertainty : Measurement uncertainty obtained by multiplying the standard uncertainty by a coverage factor to define a confidence interval.

HF (High Frequency) : Frequency range above power frequency, in this context typically from 9 kHz to 150 kHz.

HFD (High-Frequency Distortion) : Disturbances in electrical grids with frequency components above a few kHz, mainly caused by power electronics.

High-Pass Filter (HPF) : Filter that attenuates low-frequency components while allowing high-frequency components to pass.

IEC (International Electrotechnical Commission) : International organization that develops standards in electrical and electronic engineering.

IT (Instrument Transformer) : Device used to scale high voltage or current signals to lower levels suitable for measurement and protection.

LFA (Low-Frequency Amplifier) : Amplifier designed to amplify low-frequency or power-frequency signals.

LPIT (Low Power Instrument Transformer) : Type of instrument transformer that outputs low-level signals, often using electronic or optical technology.

MV (Medium Voltage) : Voltage range typically between 1 kV and 36 kV.

NMI (National Metrology Institute) : National authority responsible for maintaining measurement standards and ensuring traceability to SI units.

Phase Error : Difference in phase angle between the input and output signals of a transformer or measurement system.

PQ (Power Quality) : Measure of how well electrical power conforms to ideal conditions for proper operation of equipment.

Ratio Error : Deviation between the actual transformation ratio and the nominal ratio of an instrument transformer.

RCVD (Resistive-Capacitive Voltage Divider) : High-voltage measurement device combining resistive and capacitive elements for broadband voltage scaling.

RMS (Root Mean Square) : Effective value of an AC signal corresponding to the equivalent DC power.

SH (Supraharmonics) : Frequency components typically in the range from 2 kHz to 150 kHz generated by modern power electronic devices.

SNR (Signal-to-Noise Ratio) : Measure of signal strength relative to background noise, important for accurate measurement of low-level harmonics.

SUT (Step-Up Transformer) : Transformer used to increase voltage from primary to secondary side.

TUR (Test Uncertainty Ratio) : Ratio between the tolerance of the device under test and the measurement uncertainty of the test system.

Traceability : Property of a measurement result that allows it to be linked to a reference through an unbroken chain of calibrations.

Uncertainty : Parameter that characterizes the dispersion of values that could be attributed to a measured quantity.

VT (Voltage Transformer) : Instrument transformer used to scale high voltages down to measurable levels.

WB (Wideband Class) : IEC-defined accuracy class extension for instrument transformers covering extended frequency ranges.

WB0–WB4 : Wideband accuracy class extensions defined in IEC 61869 covering increasing frequency ranges up to 500 kHz.

1 Summary

This deliverable presents the consolidated outcomes of the ADMIT project on the characterization of the accuracy of instrument transformers (ITs) over the extended frequency range up to 150 kHz. The document has been specifically structured to support the transfer of the project results to standardization bodies, particularly IEC/CENELEC TC38, by providing a coherent framework combining scientific analysis, experimental validation, and practical recommendations for testing and calibration.

The overall organization of the deliverable follows a logical progression from the identification of the problem and standardization gaps to the development of technical solutions and their validation, culminating in a set of recommendations addressed to standardization activities.

Chapter 2 – Context, Objectives, and Accuracy Requirements establish the technical and standardization background of the study. It analyses the limitations of the current IEC 61869 standard framework and identifies the absence of harmonized procedures for high-frequency testing as a critical gap. The chapter combines a review of standards and literature with numerical simulations of realistic power systems, aiming to define the characteristics of disturbances in the 9 kHz–150 kHz range and to derive corresponding accuracy and uncertainty requirements for instrument transformers.

The deliverable then transitions from context to methodology in Chapter 3 – Technical Solutions and Recommendations for Testing, which is one of the document's core contributions. This chapter defines the fundamental elements required for IT testing under supraharmonic conditions, including voltage and current levels, performance indices in both the frequency and time domains, and the characteristics of real-world disturbances. A key component of this chapter is the definition of the proposed test conditions and test waveforms, covering both frequency-domain and time-domain approaches, as well as composite signals that combine fundamental and high-frequency components.

Following the definition of test methodologies, the deliverable details the experimental infrastructures developed within the project. Chapter 4 – Generation Architectures for VT Testing describes different solutions for voltage generation, including parallel and series configurations, transformer-based amplification and transient generators. These architectures are analyzed in terms of design, implementation, and performance, with a particular focus on their ability to generate composite waveforms that combine power-frequency and high-frequency components.

A similar approach is adopted in Chapter 5 – Generation Architectures for CT Testing, which extends the analysis to current generation systems. This chapter addresses the additional challenges associated with high-current generation, including the need to superimpose high-frequency components onto large power-frequency currents, and presents validated solutions based on parallel or dual-source configurations and transient-generation circuits.

The next two chapters focus on measurement systems, which are essential for ensuring traceability and accuracy in the proposed test procedures. Chapter 6 – Voltage Measuring System describes the development and characterization of reference systems for voltage measurement, including dividers, digitizers and associated uncertainty analysis. Chapter 7 – Current Measuring System provides a complementary analysis for current measurement, detailing the architectures adopted by different laboratories and the corresponding traceability chains and uncertainty budgets.

Building on the technical outcome from the project, Chapter 8 – Recommendations for IEC/CENELEC TC38 synthesizes the main outcomes of the project into a structured set of recommendations for standardization. These recommendations address test waveforms, measurement methods, accuracy definitions and uncertainty evaluation, and are intended to support the revision or development of standards within the IEC 61869 series.

The two pictures in the following confirm that this document was successfully submitted to IEC Collaboration Platform on 1st June 2026.

Main findings of European Metrology research project EPM 22NRM06 ADMIT

Oggetto: Main findings of European Metrology research project EPM 22NRM06 ADMIT

Mittente: TC 38/WG 47 <noreply@iec.ch>

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Collaboration Platform

International Electrotechnical Commission

From: Mario LUISO

To: TC 38/WG 47 ;

Main findings of European Metrology research project EPM 22NRM06 ADMIT

Dear colleagues of IEC TC38 WG47,

I just submitted a document that summarizes the main findings of the European Metrology research project EPM 22NRM06 ADMIT, related to the accuracy evaluation of ITs up to 150 kHz.

Best regards

Mario Luiso.

Notified from : <https://collaborate.iec.ch/#pages/workspaces/219541/documents/>

[22NRM06_ADMIT_MainResults.pdf](#)

Main results related to IT characterization up to 150 kHz from European Metrology research project EPM 22NRM06 ADMIT

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2 Context, Objectives, and Accuracy Requirements

The European project ADMIT (Characterization of AC and DC MV instrument transformers in extended frequency range up to 150 kHz) was conceived to address a critical gap identified by IEC Technical Committee TC 38 (Instrument Transformers): the absence of standardized methods for testing and characterization of Instrument Transformers under conditions that include high-frequency disturbances up to 150 kHz.

Modern power systems, increasingly populated by power electronics and renewable energy sources, generate high-frequency emissions that propagate through medium-voltage networks. These phenomena challenge the traditional accuracy classes and test procedures, which are currently limited to power frequency and, at best, to harmonics up to 20 kHz. Without harmonized standards, manufacturers and laboratories face uncertainty in defining performance requirements, while grid operators lack reliable tools to assess compliance and ensure interoperability.

ADMIT's objectives are therefore twofold. First, it aims to develop traceable measurement methods and infrastructures capable of generating and measuring AC/DC voltages up to 36 kV and currents up to 2 kA, with superimposed components up to 150 kHz. Second, it seeks to establish accuracy parameters, uncertainty limits, and test procedures that can be directly incorporated into the IEC 61869 standard family. By providing validated data, guidelines, and good-practice documents, the project will enable IEC/CENELEC TC 38 to revise existing standards or draft new ones, ensuring that instrument transformers are fit for the evolving requirements of smart grids and power-quality monitoring.

The outcomes of this work will not only strengthen the metrological capabilities of National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and industrial laboratories but will also have a profound influence on future international standards. These standards will underpin reliable measurements in MV grids, support fair energy trade, and contribute to grid stability and efficiency amid growing renewable integration.

The purpose of this document is to provide IEC/CENELEC TC 38 with a comprehensive overview of the ADMIT project results, highlighting validated test methods, generation architectures, and accuracy benchmarks. These findings aim to inform the development of future IEC standards, ensuring that ITs are tested under conditions that reflect real-world disturbances.

2.1 International Standard Context and Current Gaps

The International Standard of Instrument Transformers is currently insufficient to address the challenges posed by high-frequency disturbances in modern power systems. Existing standards, such as the International Standard Family IEC 61869, were designed primarily for power frequency conditions and, in some cases, extended to cover harmonics up to 20 kHz. Moreover, IEC 61869 has introduced an extension of the accuracy classes (WB0 to WB4) that cover accuracy classes up to 500 kHz. However, they do not provide clear guidance on evaluating the accuracy of ITs in the frequency range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. This omission leaves manufacturers and testing laboratories without harmonized procedures, resulting in inconsistent practices and non-comparable results.

The lack of standardized methods affects several critical aspects. First, there are no defined test waveforms or amplitude levels for high-frequency components superimposed on the fundamental voltage or current. Second, there is no specification of reference-measuring systems or uncertainty-evaluation methods suitable for this extended frequency range. Finally, the standards do not address the influence of external factors—such as temperature, burden, and electromagnetic interference—that can significantly impact the performance of instrument transformers under realistic operating conditions.

This regulatory gap has practical consequences. Utilities and grid operators cannot rely on uniform criteria to validate the performance of instrument transformers installed in networks increasingly dominated by power electronics. Manufacturers, in turn, face uncertainty when designing products intended to operate accurately under high-frequency disturbance conditions.

The ADMIT project bridges this gap by proposing practical, traceable methods for generating composite waveforms and assessing IT accuracy up to 150 kHz. These methods are designed to be reproducible and scalable, enabling both national metrology institutes and industrial laboratories to adopt them.

One of the main objectives of the 22RNM06 ADMIT is to define a) characteristics of grid disturbances, b) performance requirements of ITs, c) accuracy parameters and uncertainty limits of VTs and CTs used for power system applications up to 150 kHz, in distribution grids with rated voltage up to 36 kV and currents up to 2 kA. To evaluate the metrological performance of ITs up to 150 kHz, it is necessary to define voltage and current waveforms and levels and working conditions. Indeed, the metrological characterisation of ITs is carried out by applying primary excitations and comparing the measurement result obtained with the ITs under test with those retrieved with a reference system.

To properly test VTs and CTs under realistic operating conditions (especially those installed in medium-voltage networks where harmonic disturbances in the 9 kHz–150 kHz band are increasingly present) it is crucial to identify realistic grid disturbances up to 150 kHz, along with their characteristics, to be used in the IT testing. This can be done by analysing the present knowledge (literature, standards, previous projects, etc.) and then by performing numerical simulations of power systems and measurement campaigns in MV grids.

As ITs' performance assessment is as meaningful as the applied waveforms resemble those found during typical operation, it is possible to correctly assess performance requirements for VTs and CTs up to 150 kHz by identifying the future measurement needs for power system applications up to 150 kHz and by selecting the IT types (LPIT, inductive, DLPIT), suitable for the frequency range up to 150 kHz.

2.1.1 Analysis of literature and standards about power system applications up to 150 kHz

The phenomenon of high-frequency distortion (HFD) in the electric grids, at both low voltage (LV) and medium-voltage (MV) levels, is gaining increasing interest within the scientific and technical community due to its growing occurrence and the associated impact. These disturbances are mainly injected into the grid by new installed devices, essential for achieving decentralized generation based on renewable sources. In fact, these generation systems are connected to the grid through power converters, whose switching frequencies are significantly increasing, leading to a corresponding rise in the frequency of the injected disturbances. HFD represents a quite recent issue, but numerous scientific papers have been published in recent years on this topic. Furthermore, various international standards have also covered it, to provide guidance on instrumentation and related algorithms and indices for the measurement of these phenomena. When measuring HFD in MV grids, it is necessary to use instrument transformers (ITs) to scale voltages and currents to levels fitting with the input stages of power quality (PQ) instruments. In this respect, the recently released Edition 2 of the IEC 61869-1 standard extends the concept of the IT accuracy class up to 500 kHz; however, the IEC 61869 standard family provides guidelines on how to test ITs only at power frequency.

The phenomenon of high-frequency distortion (HFD, often called supra-harmonics) consists of disturbances having significant frequency contents beyond 9 kHz. HFD gained significant interest in recent decades due to its increasing presence in both low-voltage (LV) and medium-voltage (MV) grids [1], [2], [3], [4]. In fact, many renewable energy sources, as well as new electronic loads, are connected to the main power grid through power converters, whose switching frequencies are significantly increasing, leading to a corresponding rise in the frequency of injected disturbances. In particular, the main sources of HFD include energy-saving equipment, power electronics technologies associated with renewable energy sources, electric vehicle chargers, power line communication associated with smart grids, LED lamps, and photovoltaic inverters. Due to the negative impact of HFD on power quality (PQ) and on the normal operation of the grid, including power loss, heating of grid elements, aging of dielectric materials, and interference with equipment and power line communication technology [5], several challenges arise across the various fields of electrical/electronic engineering on how to deal with them. These challenges include the accurate identification and measurement of HFD, assessing their impact on equipment, understanding the transfer impedance between LV and MV grids, considering partial discharge effects, modeling grid impedance, implementing new standards or updating existing ones, and developing effective methods to mitigate their impact on power networks [6], [7], [8], [9]. In the literature, several papers are focused on the topic of HFD. These research studies are focused on measuring the level of emissions generated by different sources [9], [10] and their effects on LV and MV power system components, evaluation methods of HFD levels, propagation through power network impedance, and mitigation strategies. As regards the specific area of HFD, accurate measurement methods and indices for their quantification have been included into in-force international standards such as IEC 61000-4-7 [11] and IEC 61000-4-30 [12]. In addition, suitable measurement techniques have been proposed in the scientific literature to measure HFD. For instance, Digital CISPR [13], Light-QP [14], and matrix pencil methods [15],

[16] are some of the proposed methods that provide different approaches to measure HFD, which differ from each other in computational resources, accuracy, and immunity to noise [17]. As regards the measurement chain for the monitoring of HFD in MV grids, it must always include transducers to properly scale down the voltage and current to levels fitting with the input stage of PQ analyzers or, more generally, acquisition systems. For MV grids, the widely used transducers are instrument transformers (ITs), such as voltage and current transformers (VTs and CTs). Consequently, it is evident that the ITs metrological performances at frequencies higher than 9 kHz strongly impact the overall accuracy associated with HFD measurements [18]. From the standardization point of view, the ITs are covered by the IEC 61869 standard family. The recently released IEC 61869-1 Edition 2 [19] extends the concept of accuracy classes, previously limited to the power frequency, over five different frequency ranges up to 500 kHz. However, the entire standard family lacks indications on test procedures, methods, and specifications of the reference systems used for characterizing the ITs at frequencies different from the fundamental frequency. In this respect, the European research project EMPIR 19NRM05 IT4PQ [18], [20], concluded in June 2023, focused on building up the entire metrological framework for the accuracy verification of ITs from power frequency up to 9 kHz. As regards the frequency range 9–150 kHz, a new project has recently started: the European Partnership in Metrology (EPM) 22NRM06 ADMIT [21]. The most significant activities that will be carried out within this project are definition of accuracy parameters and related procedures for the performance evaluation of ITs, definition of realistic waveforms, development of new reference systems for the generation of alternating current (AC, 50/60 Hz) or direct current (DC) voltages (up to 36 kV) and currents (up to 2 kA) with spectral components at reduced amplitudes up to 150 kHz, and development of reference MV voltage and current sensors up to 150 kHz. The first key activity to achieve these objectives is the collection of all available information regarding HFD occurring in electrical grids in the 9–150 kHz range and the behaviour of ITs in this range. Ω

The most significant HFD sources were revealed to be photovoltaic (PV) power parks and electric vehicles (EVs) and their charging stations (EVCSs), which are more intimately interconnected in the MV and LV grids, rather than larger wind parks and other large power installations, usually connected farther away in the grid an closer to the high-voltage level, with some exceptions [22], [23], [24]. In [25], a voltage HFD at 16.1 kHz was observed, in addition to the main HFD peak in the spectrum at the frequency of 2.5 kHz. The occurrences of this HFD indicate that they were caused by PV power installations in the considered grid. In [26], a dominant emission at 10 kHz was found due to the switching frequency of the power converter. The paper highlighted time-varying emissions due to variations in the switching frequency of wind turbine converters across different operating modes during low power extraction, with switching frequencies ranging from 7 to 10 kHz. Therefore, 10 kHz can be considered an HFD frequency component due to wind turbine converters, which can impact the network and connected equipment. In [27], HFD components were observed in the range 2–50 kHz for both voltage and current. Here, the predominant frequencies were 12.5 kHz, 16.1 kHz, and 34.1 kHz, with amplitudes below 0.1% and 0.25% for voltage and current, respectively. In [28], [29], a measurement campaign in a distribution network was performed. The paper showed that the components of HFDs were primarily concentrated below 50 kHz, with amplitudes generally below 0.3 V, particularly around 10 kHz and 12 kHz. Moreover, in the presence of high PV penetration, 10 kHz, 26 kHz, and 36 kHz frequency components were found predominant, compared with tones at other frequencies. Finally, a component with 0.15 V at 126 kHz was found. Probably, this is due to the presence of resonances in the system, as caused by grid-connected inverters and their filters. In [30], a long-term measurement was performed at several locations with small-scale PV installations. The results of the measurements showed that there were two dominating HFD frequencies at 16 kHz and 16.7 kHz. However, no additional information was provided regarding the amplitude of these HFD components. The study in [31] examined the intermodulation resulting from the interaction between PV systems and electric vehicle (EV) charger stations, demonstrating that it produced HFD at several frequencies with significant amplitudes. In particular, a dominant frequency was identified at 16 kHz, probably due to the switching frequency of the PV inverter circuit. Additionally, lower-amplitude emissions were observed at integer multiples of the switching frequency, especially at 32 kHz and 48 kHz. Furthermore, the primary emission of the EV charger station was detected below 25 kHz, but during the charging process, a component around 100 kHz emerged, likely attributed to the switching frequency of the EV. The intermodulation between the main emissions of PV and EV generated HFDs at various frequencies, including 16 kHz, 32 kHz, 52 kHz, 48 kHz, 64 kHz, 68 kHz, 80 kHz, 84 kHz, and 96 kHz. In [32], HFDs generated by Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs) in a LV network were examined. The paper highlighted that BEVs can produce a high level of HFDs, which can significantly impact PQ. In particular, the findings revealed that the HFD components with higher amplitudes for BEVs charging at 16 A were concentrated around 10 kHz, reaching magnitudes of up to 1080 mA. Harmonics of this component were observed at approximately 20 kHz and 40

kHz. Furthermore, for BEVs charging at 23 A, the dominant HFD components with higher amplitudes were found around 45 kHz, with magnitudes up to 200 mA, and their harmonics were noted at around 90 kHz. In [33], a measurement campaign conducted in LV grids detected the presence of HFDs within the context of residential PV inverter installations. Specifically, peaks were observed at approximately 16 kHz and 19.5 kHz. In some papers, the transmission of HFD distortions through a transformer from the LV grid to the MV grid was studied. HFD currents were injected using an HFD-emitting device, which can create components in the frequency ranges 3.3–3.9 kHz, 6.8–7.8 kHz, and 10–11 kHz. The paper showed that HFD can propagate with various transfer ratios (i.e., a transfer ratio of 0.5 V/V means that 1 V becomes 0.5 V) for voltage or current and from LV to MV, or vice versa. In particular, from LV to MV, the current ratio was approximately 1 A/A, whereas the voltage ratio was between 0.01 V/V and 1.0 V/V and depended on the transformer ratio. The transfer ratio from MV to LV was, instead, between 0.5 V/V and 3.0 V/V, while no information was reported for the current transfer ratio. In [25], an advanced converter harmonic model was introduced to study harmonic resonance when an ultra-fast charging station was connected to the MV grid. This model was used for the impedance calculation up to 2.5 kHz. In [34], the propagation of HFD in a MV network was studied, focusing on the frequency range of 2–50 kHz. The analysis was based on the on-site measurements carried out in a 20 kV public network, which included a small MV wind plant and solar parks distributed over the whole network and connected to the MV grid via dedicated transformers. The results showed HFDs characterized by amplitudes of tens of millivolt and high variability during the day. In [35], [36], the impact of voltage HFDs on MV cables was evaluated. In [37], the accelerated aging of MV cable terminations due to HFDs was addressed in order to provide recommendations to evaluate the risk of cable terminations' failure under the presence of HFD in MV networks in the frequency range of 2–150 kHz. This paper suggested not to overcome the 24% of the rated voltage under 20 kHz and 9% of the rated voltage above 20 kHz. In [38], the effects of HFD on cable insulation were analysed. It was shown that cable insulation degradation progresses faster under power frequency voltage with superimposed HFDs. The test conducted in this paper consisted of superposing damped sine wave pulses with a natural frequency of 7.2 kHz and a repetition frequency of 800 Hz to the power frequency voltage. Moreover, the peak-to-peak voltage was set to 15% of the power frequency peak-to-peak voltage. These parameters were chosen according to a numerical simulation, which emulated a 1 MW PV power plant connected to the MV distribution grid. The HFD distribution in terms of amplitude and frequency was also evaluated, focusing on a wide range of victims, providing a justification for limits in the supraharmic range based on documented negative effects. Such negative effects range from the already mentioned impact on MV cables, and cable joints in particular, to aging of capacitors and dielectrics in general, as well as flicker as acoustic noise generated by interference to electrical appliances and EVs themselves, to interference to electrical equipment; in particular, in the presence of electronic circuits and communications, as in the case of power line communication (PLC) technology. Being the base for grid monitoring and automation, protection of PLC devices and communications from interference is a priority. An important part of this wide group of electrical devices is represented by devices for protection (residual current devices) and metering (energy meters). As for protection, the real risk is desensitization of the protection relay, for which in the presence of HFD, the tripping threshold is increased, with relevant implications for electrical safety. Metering is heavily influenced by HFD, where devices working on different principles but equally available on the market and complying with the same standard reacted quite differently. The problem is not only susceptibility of the electronic devices inside, but the different algorithms used to calculate the active and reactive power, as well as the interpretation of the active and reactive power.

Various measurement methods have been proposed for identifying and quantifying the occurrence of HFDs in power grids. More specifically, the international standards IEC 61000-4-7 [11], IEC 61000-4-30 [12], and CISPR 16-1 [13] provide methods for measuring HFDs. The proposed method for measuring frequency components above 9 kHz involves aggregating the energy of the signal under analysis into predetermined frequency ranges. Whereas for frequencies up to 9 kHz the commonly employed frequency bandwidth is 200 Hz, a bandwidth of 2 kHz is suggested for higher-frequency components. However, it is important to note that these methods offer reduced computational complexity but may sacrifice accuracy, particularly for high-amplitude components. However, additional methods based on different techniques have been developed and presented in the scientific literature. These methods provide different accuracy and resolution associated with both amplitude and frequency of HFD. The different accuracy and resolution of HFD measurement methods can be attributed to the following causes:

- The susceptibility to noise: some methods are less immune to noise and may lose accuracy in estimating high-amplitude HFDs.

- Computational complexity: some methods require more mathematical operations during processing, affecting their efficiency.
- Measurement equipment: the sampling rate, resolution, and accuracy class of measurement equipment can affect the accuracy of methods.
- Calibration process and data processing techniques can also contribute to the variation in accuracy and resolution.
- Transducers and sensors: all of the measurement methods are influenced by the accuracy and precision of the transducers and sensors.

More generally, the developed measurement methods can be categorized into two main groups: time-domain and frequency-domain measurement techniques. The time-domain methods involve analyzing the waveform using cross-correlation and matrix pencil to process the measured signal and estimate the HFD components. These measurement methods include Digital CISPR [13], Light-QP, Numerical-Heterodyne [39], the matrix pencil method [15], [16], and the sliding-window TLS-ESPRIT. The advantages of time-domain measurement methods include high time resolution and the ability to effectively reduce the influence of colored noise on the measurement [16]. However, time-domain methods have limitations in terms of computational complexity and accuracy in estimating high-amplitude HFD components. The frequency-domain methods involve analyzing the spectral content of the waveform. These methods use the Fourier transformer (FT) in order to analyze the frequency component up to 150 kHz. The advantage of these methods includes the ability to provide wide frequency-domain measurement and higher-frequency resolution. However, these methods are susceptible to noise and require a higher sampling rate to accurately detect the HFD components. The main issue across all methods concerns the amplitude resolution of measurement devices in the high-frequency range. Typically, the input stage of these devices is designed based on the amplitude of the fundamental component. Consequently, when an HFD with an amplitude below 5% of the fundamental component is present, the resolution of the measured components diminishes compared to the fundamental component. To address this issue, many measurement approaches include a high-pass filter to strongly attenuate the amplitude of the fundamental component. In this way, the input stage is designed to fit the high-frequency component, optimizing the amplitude resolution for HFDs. However, it is worth noting that scientific literature lacks papers addressing the metrological characterization of sensors, transducers, and high-pass filters specifically developed for MV applications from 20 kHz to 150 kHz.

The monitoring of HFD propagation in power grids through the grid impedance is a crucial issue since it can cause resonance phenomena. Resonance is common to DC and AC grids, as a consequence of the interaction between the grid impedance itself and the admittance contribution of connected loads, in particular renewables interfaced by means of actively controlled inverters. This is not only a characteristic of AC grids but also quite in DC grids and can affect not only "grids" intended as distribution networks, but also specialized systems, such as electrified railways. HFD from sources connected to the MV network, such as PV installation, wind farms, EV charger stations, and all renewable sources that use switching power converters, will spread through the MV network and, from there, through the transfer impedance to equipment connected to the LV grid. Furthermore, LV devices, such as LED lamps, can produce HFD and, from there, can be transferred to MV grids. Therefore, the equipment connected to both the LV and MV grids can be interfered with or damaged by the propagation of HFDs. Methods for grid impedance measurement are classified into active, passive, and quasi-passive methods, each with its own advantages and disadvantages. Active methods are the most accurate, as they rely on a test signal injected into the grid. The shape of the test signal may vary, from ideally a pulse to a swept sine, or a combination of sinusoidal components at selected prime frequencies, or a pseudo-random binary sequence. The test signal must be efficiently coupled into the grid with problems of galvanic insulation and bandwidth of the amplifying and coupling device. Passive methods, instead, are based on passive listening of the electrical quantities and rely on transients and excitation signals that are intrinsic to the grid itself. Such excitation signals may be the spectral components of emissions of distorting loads, as well as transients due to maneuvers (load or compensator switching, breakers tripping, etc.). This approach was successfully used to identify the railway line impedance following electric arcs, exploiting the high-frequency content of the arc transient and compensating the reduced number of samples with advanced spectral estimation techniques. An impact evaluation based on the kind of interference between HFDs and power networks was introduced in some papers. These papers considered adverse effects, such as audible noise, light flicker, tripping of residual current devices, and cable termination failure. HFD propagation generally

depends on the impedance of the LV and MV grids and the connected devices. The sensitivity of HFD propagation to changes of the grid impedance at the delivery point has been modelled for the case of EV chargers connected to a LV DC distribution grid and assessed in two experimental case studies. It has been found that HFDs can propagate through transformers, with different transfer ratios depending on the direction of propagation. Moreover, HFDs can interact with close devices in end-user installations, and the propagation toward the grid can either increase or decrease depending on the ratio between the device and grid impedance. For these reasons, it is evident that a key issue in the HFD framework is the frequency dependent grid impedance measurement, which provides more accurate information about the connection capacity of points of common coupling, enabling more efficient grid utilization and optimization of large-scale generation plants. To measure grid impedance in the frequency range of 9–150 kHz, several methods have been proposed in the literature:

- A windowed Fourier transform is a commonly used method to improve the calculation precision and anti-interference ability of grid impedance detection.
- A three-stage interpolation-based measurement method, using cubic spline interpolation and Hanning-window-based interpolated discrete Fourier transform (IpDFT), can remove undesired components and deal with spectral leakage caused by FFT.
- Spectral excitation currents can be used to identify grid impedance, and different measurement systems have been successfully developed for different voltage levels.
- A time–frequency distribution method using a single rectangular pulse injection is employed for grid impedance estimation in the frequency range of HFD.
- Advanced methods for characterizing LV grid access impedance in the frequency range assigned to Narrow-band power-line communications (NB-PLC) have been developed and validated.

The main issue of grid impedance measurements is related to the emissions from several sources, such as non-linear loads or power electronics, and varies with frequency. These emissions can corrupt impedance measurements, leading to false resonances, phase distortion, and additional coupling of impedance elements. For these reasons, the identification of accurate techniques for the broad-band measurement of grid impedance, particularly at MV, is still an open issue.

Mitigation of HFD is a crucial task to avoid equipment malfunctions and decrease of the equipment lifespans and to maintain power grid stability. It is worth pointing out that both LV and MV grids are exposed to the same risks since HFD can be transmitted from MV to LV grids and vice versa through power transformers. To mitigate HFDs, several potential solutions have been proposed in the scientific literature. Some of these solutions are summarized below:

- Filters, such as EMC (electromagnetic compatibility) filters, can mitigate the HFDs by creating a low-impedance path for high-frequency signals, thus preventing their propagation into LV and MV grids.
- Resonance control strategies can mitigate the HFD propagation.
- Impedance control strategies can mitigate HFDs by managing the impedance of the grid and connected devices to counteract the propagation.

Commonly used techniques in the literature deploy filtering schemes, which can have different characteristics:

- Passive filters are widely used for harmonic filtering and offer several advantages, including energy saving and reductions in power demand.
- Active filters are effective in compensating for current and voltage harmonics, reactive power, and voltage imbalance in three-phase systems.
- Distributed multiple low-voltage filters can be deployed in random locations of a distribution system to mitigate harmonic distortions.
- Passive zero-sequence harmonic filters can trap two harmonics with one filter and are effective in mitigating zero-sequence harmonics.

However, all these solutions have several unsolved issues related to the behavior of HFD, especially in MV grids. The lack of recommended practices to assess the effects of HFD on the power grids makes the diagnosis and the mitigation of the related problems challenging tasks. Moreover, HFDs can propagate through transformers and the transfer ratio and amplification of different components can vary, the propagation of HFDs less predictable. Finally, HFDs can cause interference with elements for power delivery and end-user equipment, which complicates discovering the point of injection of these disturbances.

A considerable number of international standards on the topic of power grid disturbances has been published. However, there is not a specific international standard covering the disturbances in the frequency range of 9 – 150 kHz in an MV grid. So far, standards have only partially addressed voltage and current components resulting from disturbances and signalling within the frequency range of 9 – 150 kHz.

The IEC 61000-4-7 [11] and IEC 61000-4-30 [12] standards provide methodologies for measuring voltage and current components up to 150 kHz. In addition to measurement methods, the IEC 61000-4-7 [11] and IEEE Std 1159 [40] also give a classification of power grid disturbances as conducted low-frequency and high-frequency phenomena. It is worth noting that the terms high frequency and low frequency in these standards are not defined in terms of a specific frequency threshold but instead indicate the relative difference in the frequency content of the phenomena listed in these categories. The main disturbances in the frequency range 9 – 150 kHz considered by the standards are the induced continuous wave (CW) voltage or currents, unidirectional transients, and oscillatory transients. However, the standards do not set specific limits to these disturbances for voltage and current in MV grids.

Table 2-1: Relevant international standard families dealing with HFDs

Reviewed International Standards	
Voltage characteristics of electricity supplied by public distribution network	EN 50160 IEC 62749
Recommended practice for monitoring electric power quality	IEEE 1159
Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC)	IEC 61000
Instrument transformers	IEC 61869 IEC 60044

As previously outlined, the measurement of HFD in MV grids requires the use of ITs. Consequently, the frequency behaviour of ITs significantly influences the accuracy associated with the measurement of these phenomena. In this respect, the IEC 61869-1 Ed.2 standard [19], which has been recently released, introduces new frequency accuracy class extensions for ITs up to 500 kHz. More specifically, it introduces five different extensions (WB0 to WB4) that differ in the covered frequency range. The WB0 class, which prescribes limits up to the 13th harmonic, is indicated as mandatory for Low Power Instrument Transformers (LPIT) and SAMUs (Stand Alone Merging Units), whereas the other extensions (WB1 to WB4) are optional. Regarding inductive IT, no wideband class extension is mandatory, not even the WB0.

However, the standard [19], but also the entire IEC 61869 standard family, does not provide guidelines on how to test ITs to verify their accuracy class at frequencies different from the power frequency (i.e. 50/60 Hz). Specifically, it does not specify the type of test signal to be used, i.e., whether the tests should be performed at reduced or nominal voltage. In this context, everything remains at the discretion of metrological institutes and testing laboratories intending to verify the accuracy of ITs according to the classes limited provided by the standard.

The traceable characterization of ITs, with reference to AC and DC grids applications, at frequencies different from the fundamental, currently represents an open issue for National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and other metrological communities. Consequently, several European research projects have been funded in recent years to address this issue. This section aims to provide a concise review of previous research projects

conducted over the years. For brevity, only key findings from these projects are presented here and detailed information can be accessed through referenced papers and webpages.

The EMRP ENG52 Smart Grid II [41], [42] was funded with the main aim of implementing a comprehensive metrology framework for Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs). Specifically, the project has focused on meeting the accurate calibration requirements for PMUs and their associated transducers, crucial for monitoring the stability of distribution networks. Additionally, the project has emphasized the need for innovative synchronized grid measurement techniques to analyse the propagation of PQ disturbances in networks, identify significant sources of disturbance and measure network impedance.

In the framework of the European project Smart Grid II, an optimised non-invasive CT was developed. A non-invasive split-core CT with nanocrystalline core material was developed. Three different split-core CTs with primary currents of 100 A, 500 A and 1000 A were designed and built. An extensive characterisation was performed to quantify the CTs performance both in amplitude and frequency up to 5 kHz. The investigation of error frequency dependence revealed that employing nanocrystalline materials for CT core construction allows their utilization within a frequency range of up to 5 kHz, with ratio error variations on the order of a few hundred $\mu\text{A}/\text{A}$.

Within the Smart Grid II project, calibration facilities have been developed for the calibration of inductive MV VTs under distorted realistic voltages up to 30 kV and frequency content lower than 7 kHz. Specifications and constraints of the facility for the frequency-dependent calibration of MV inductive VTs were identified, considering a range of voltages from 1 kV up to 30 kV with superimposed harmonics up to the 50th. Two possible generation and measurement setups were identified and developed. The key elements of both setups are a power amplifier (30 kV, 20 mA, DC to 30 kHz, with full generation capabilities up to 7 kHz), supplied by an arbitrary waveform generator, and a suitably built digital comparator with associated control and measurement software.

The first proposed setup extends the one used for the two-step procedure based on a high-voltage (HV) capacitance bridge, which is currently employed in NMI laboratories for the calibration of inductive VTs at power frequency. A second setup, more oriented to the calibration of non-conventional VTs with LV output, was instead developed to calibrate VTs by comparison with a reference sensor. The reference sensor, designed and built for this particular purpose, is a resistive capacitive divider with suitable shields introduced to improve its frequency response and reduce proximity effects.

The first setup allows for calibrating VT up to 10 kHz with standard uncertainty within 200 $\mu\text{V}/\text{V}$ and 300 μrad for ratio and phase errors, respectively. The second setup produces similar uncertainties in a narrower frequency range (DC to 8 kHz).

Ratio and phase errors up to the first resonance were measured on commercial VTs with primary voltages from 1 kV up to 50 kV. Measurements were performed carrying out a frequency sweep with the fundamental at the rated MV voltage (up to 30 kV) with a superimposed harmonic of amplitude from 20 % to 0.2 % of the fundamental component.

A technique was developed for compensating ratio and phase errors of MV VTs up to several tens of kHz. This involved metrological characterization of the VT over a wide frequency range, followed by cascading a device with a frequency response equal to the transducer inverse transfer function to compensate for systematic deviations. An impulse infinite response digital filter was adopted for this purpose, with its complex transfer function factorized in second-order sections. An objective function was defined to identify the best set of coefficients to fit the given transducer, using a hybrid scheme combining stochastic and deterministic approaches to minimize fitting errors. The technique was applied to compensate for the behaviour of a 50 kV VT, resulting in significant improvement in its frequency response up to 5 kHz. The MATLAB implementation of the filter showed substantial enhancement in frequency response, which was further implemented by using a PXI platform. Testing on a $55/\sqrt{3}$ kV VT demonstrated compliance with standard limits up to 4 kHz, with a significant reduction in resonance peak after compensation. Lastly, the compensating filter for a 1 kV VT was successfully implemented.

The project 18NRM05 SupraEMI [43] dealt with the development of a metrological framework for the measurement of disturbances in the LV grids from 2 kHz to 150 kHz. Within this project, a new measurement method for HFDs was proposed and tested in laboratory and onsite in different LV grids.

The new method was developed with the objective of updating the existing international standard IEC 61000-4-30 [12], which defines PQ measurement methods for power grids.

A major constraint on the development of the method was the need to demonstrate compatibility with a historic radio standard defined in CISPR 16-1-1 which is used with an analogue radio receiver to sweep across the frequency band to look for emissions. This standard includes the 2-150 kHz band and as such has established itself in several EMC and PQ standards as the only available measurement method. For example, the basis of EMC is the definition of compatibility levels which is the maximum level of interference on the electricity grid for which any connected appliance should ever expect to be exposed to. The compatibility levels must be measured and monitored in grids, but in the absence of a suitable measurement method, the committee in charge used to refer to CISPR 16-1-1, thus creating the constraint that a new practical method for grid measurements must respect.

The method had to resolve the amplitude of emissions in the 2-150 kHz range which implies a decision on the frequency resolution for each component in the spectrum. The higher the resolution, the more data the instrument will be produced, leading to issues of storage, data presentation and interpretation. However, if the resolution is too low, it will not be possible to determine the emission problem frequencies preventing the tracing of the source of the emission and its mitigation. As a compromise, a frequency resolution of 200 Hz was chosen. Computationally, calculating the 2-150 kHz magnitude spectrum is extremely demanding and the algorithm used needs to be as efficient as possible. Therefore, the processing requirements of the instrument are realistic within the low-cost constraints, which over the 2-150 kHz spectrum leads to 740 frequency results every measurement period.

Defining the measurement period (and time resolution) has similar constraints on storage and interpretation and is also fundamentally constrained by the selection of the frequency resolution. A basic measurement update time of 200 ms (every ~10 cycles of a 50 Hz grid) was selected and aggregation over periods of 3 s and 10 minutes was suggested for compatibility level surveys to reduce storage and interpretation issues. The aggregation is obtained, for each frequency interval, by the square root of the square sum of the corresponding phasors evaluated from every 200 ms intervals involved in the aggregation period.

The required accuracy of the measurement (including method and instrumentation) is 10 % at each measured frequency for all magnitude values greater than 5 % of the instrument range.

Emissions usually cause problems for equipment connected to the grid, which are generally considered in terms of the peak value and the Root Mean Square (RMS) value of the emission. So, the new method was conceived to be able to measure both peak and RMS of the individual frequency values across the spectrum. CISPR 16-1-1 already addresses these measurements but introduces a third type, called the quasi-peak value, which is based on an analogue circuit implementing a peak hold and decay function. IEC SC77A WG8 has chosen this quasi-peak value to be the basis of compatibility levels. Therefore, the new method had to produce this quasi-peak output too, using digital filters [14].

The main purpose of the EMPIR 16ENG04 MyRailS was the development of both laboratory and on-board train calibration and measurement setups and robust data processing algorithms to enable high accuracy energy and PQ measurements under highly dynamic electrical conditions. The envisaged frequencies ranged from a few hertz up to 5 kHz for AC systems and up to 3 kHz for DC systems. The uncertainty targets for laboratory calibrations were 0.5 % and 0.1 % for AC and DC systems, respectively, and 0.4 % for on-board calibration of DC systems.

In this context, within the MyRailS project a new system for the generation of high voltage waveforms up to 25 kV- 50 Hz and 15 kV-16.7 Hz with harmonics up to 5 kHz and phase-fired current waveforms going up to 500 A and harmonics up to 5 kHz was developed. In particular, the developed AC calibration facility can generate:

- A sinusoidal high voltage up to 25 kV, 50 Hz or 15 kV 16.7 Hz with up to 5 kHz harmonic content.
- A sinusoidal current (50 Hz or 16.7 Hz) up to 500 A RMS value and up to 5 kHz harmonic content.

Moreover, in the framework of this project, a DC power measuring system was developed. It was able to generate DC power (phantom power) up to 8 MW with the supply voltage ranging from 1 kV to 4 kV and current from 10 A to 2000 A and with a superimposed ripple with arbitrary frequency content up to 15 kHz for the voltage and 600 Hz for the current.

The EMPIR project Future Grid II [44] provided missing solutions for the calibration and the timing of the digital substation instrumentation according to IEC 61850 [45]. The main objectives of the Future Grid II project were:

1. Establish calibration methods to support testing of digital instrument transformers.
2. Provide references for instruments with digital input or output.
3. Develop tools for devices that exploit sampled values in digital substations.
4. Create traceable references for the verification of time and synchronization methods.

In the framework of this project, a “universal” comparator was developed and characterized, able to compare the output of any type of transducer (voltage or current, conventional or non-conventional, analogue or digital) in the presence of PQ or PMU (intending here the typical voltage or current phenomena used to evaluate the accuracy of a PMU) events with a frequency spectrum up to 9 kHz. The developed “universal” comparator also included synchronization with GPS or a different sync pulse. Regarding the uncertainties, 100 $\mu\text{V/V}$ ($\mu\text{A/A}$) for the voltage (current) magnitude and 150 μrad for the phase were the target uncertainties up to 9 kHz. The universal comparator was included into the generation and measurement setup developed for the characterization of VT and Low Power VT (LPVT) with digital output in the presence of PQ phenomena up to 9 kHz.

Triggered by the needs expressed by the IEC TC 38, the primary goal of the EMPIR project 19NRM05 IT4PQ [20] was to establish a metrological framework that ensures the traceability of PQ measurements conducted by various types of IT, ranging from calibrations at NMIs to characterizations performed in industrial laboratories. To reach this objective, four key technical goals were pursued:

- Developing reference measuring systems and methodologies to establish reference systems for ITs and assess their contribution to PQ indices' uncertainty.
- Establishing methods and procedures for calibrating ITs, including adherence to grid PQ disturbance limits outlined in current standards.
- Defining an "IT PQ Accuracy Class" for different types of ITs and PQ phenomena, based on identifying an overarching PQ performance index (PI) for ITs and its corresponding accuracy thresholds.
- Assessing IT behaviour under realistic conditions, such as the simultaneous presence of various influencing factors.

In the framework of this project, a number of PQ phenomena with spectral content up to 9 kHz were analysed, and the typical range of variation of each phenomenon was identified. Suitable generation and measurement setups were implemented in order to test different types of ITs in the presence of PQ events. In particular, reference systems were developed to assess the errors introduced by CTs, VTs and combined ITs in PQ disturbance measurements. The general scheme of the developed setups includes a generation section, a reference sensor and a suitable acquisition system. Utilizing programmable waveform generators and step-up transformers or power amplifiers, the generation systems are capable of generating stationary waveforms as well as transient PQ disturbances such as dips, swells and oscillatory transients with a frequency content limited to 9 kHz. The applied waveforms are measured by characterized reference sensors, which may include MV resistive-capacitive dividers, VTs, CTs with associated conversion stages, and Low Power CTs (LPCTs). Investigative efforts explored the potential use of a current comparator as an alternative reference sensor, demonstrating its feasibility. Digital bridges are employed to record outputs from both the reference and characterized ITs, with quantities of interest being evaluated either in the time or frequency domain. Standard measurement uncertainties are maintained within a few tens of $\mu\text{V/V}$ and $\mu\text{A/A}$ (μrad), respectively, for voltage and current ratio (phase) errors at power frequency, with a slight increase to a few hundreds of $\mu\text{V/V}$ and $\mu\text{A/A}$ (μrad), respectively up to 9 kHz. As a main result, it was highlighted that the simultaneous presence of PQ phenomena impacts the performance of ITs, suggesting that to understand their actual metrological characteristics, it is necessary to test ITs in the presence of waveforms containing multiple disturbances. For instance, it was observed that for inductive VTs, the ratio error at the harmonic frequencies increases by an order of magnitude if the test signal includes subharmonics in addition to harmonics.

The experimental setups were also used to investigate the impact of single and multiple influence quantities on ITs' performance in the measurement of PQ disturbances. Several tests were performed under various conditions, such as temperature variations, burdens, vibrations, proximity effects and adjacent phases. The

primary finding revealed that burdens and temperature have the most significant impact on VTs, especially near the resonance frequencies. For LPITs, proximity effects and adjacent phases were found to be crucial. However, the way individual influencing factors interact, and influence IT performance largely depends on the specific type of IT and its construction.

2.1.2 Numerical simulations of realistic power systems

The purpose of this analysis is the evaluation of the characteristics of realistic power systems for what regards the propagation of supraharmonic (SH) emissions and their expected intensity, that corresponds to the “characteristics of grid disturbances”. With the term “realistic power system” it is meant an AC distribution network including both MV and LV levels with an extension and physical characteristics (e.g. electrical parameters) typical of a range of real systems. The “power system” will include cables for MV and LV levels, a MV/LV transformer and sources of SH emissions connected on each side; such “sources” correspond to a traditional 3-phase inverter architecture with configurable switching frequency and output filter, realistically selected of the LCL type (as commonly used to connect to distribution networks).

The modeling results will be compared to those available in the literature, as identified in the activity A1.1.1. Available published results cover mechanisms of emission, typical distortion levels in LV and MV distribution networks, and electrical behavior of the MV/LV transformer with respect to SH propagation.

The model is implemented in Simulink with a MATLAB script governing the simulations and parameter settings. Simulations will check both the behavior of the transformer taken alone and that of the whole network, evaluating the following phenomena: transfer between MV and LV levels, attenuation of SH signals while propagating along the network, and expected level of SH distortion.

The network is composed of one MV and one LV line interconnected by an MV/LV transformer and with a range of loads connected:

- power inverter as source of SH emissions,
- resistive load to change network damping,
- capacitive load to influence the resonant behavior of the MV and LV circuits.

In the following the most relevant blocks of the model are discussed. In general block parameters can be controlled from the Matlab script.

The transformer model is a standard circuit with mutual coupling and stray inductive terms at primary and secondary, as built in block of Simulink Simscape. Resistive terms can be included, but their behavior vs. frequency is hard to determine (to this aim the findings of A1.1.1 may be exploited) and to introduce in the model, as simulations are carried out in time domain; so an average value representative of the SH frequency interval will be introduced.

To prepare the input parameters for the auxiliary transformer in below table have been considered. The parameters selected are as follows:

Parameter or characteristic	Value
Nominal apparent power for primary (HV), S (kVA)	100
Percentage impedance between HV and LV %	4
No load losses (W)	1000
Full load losses (W)	5520
No load current (% of nominal current)	2
Primary voltage, V1 (kV)	11
Secondary voltage, V2 (kV)	0.4
Vector group	Dyn11
Nominal frequency (Hz)	50

The parameters of the equivalent circuit can be determined by open-circuit (no-load) and short-circuit (load) tests. The open-circuit test determines the shunt parameters of the simplified equivalent circuit of Figure 1.

Figure 1: Simplified transformer equivalent circuit

The leakage impedance value is much smaller than those of the shunt branch parameters. Therefore, the voltage drop in the resistance and leakage reactance is negligible as compared to the rated voltage. The input power measured by the wattmeter consists of the core loss and the primary winding ohmic-loss. If the no-load current is 2% of the full load current, the ohmic-loss in the primary winding resistance is just 0.04% of the load loss at the rated current; the value of the winding loss is negligible as compared to the core loss. Hence, the entire wattmeter reading can be taken as the core loss.

Figure 2: Open circuit test

Using the below formulas, we derive the value from m-file.

$$P_c = V_{HV} * I_o * \cos \theta$$

$$\cos \theta = \frac{P_c}{V_{HV} * I_o}$$

$$I_c = \frac{P_c}{V_{HV}^2}$$

$$I_{rhv} = \frac{s}{\sqrt{3} * V_{HV}}$$

$$I_o = 0.01 * I_{rhv}$$

$$I_m = \sqrt{I_o^2 - I_c^2}$$

$$R_c = \frac{V_{HV}}{I_c}, X_m = \frac{V_{HV}}{I_m}, L_m = \frac{X_m}{2 * \pi * f}$$

where:

- P_c is no load losses per phase (also referred as P_{nl}), X_m is magnetising reactance,
- R_c is core loss resistance,

- V_{HV} is HV side voltage per phase, I_c is current flowing in R_c branch, I_m is current flowing in X_m branch, I_o is no load current,
- I_{rhv} is rated current in HV winding.

A short-circuit test is done to measure the load loss and leakage impedance of the transformer. For a transformer having 4% leakage impedance, the voltage required to circulate the rated currents is 4% of the rated voltage, with one of the windings short-circuited. Since the core loss varies approximately in the square proportion of the applied voltage, with 5% voltage across R_c , it is just 0.25% of the core loss at the rated voltage. Hence, the entire loss measured by the wattmeter is almost equal to the load loss of the transformer.

Figure 4 Short circuit test

The parameters of the equivalent circuit, R_{eq} ($= R_1 + R_2$) and X_{eq} ($= X_{L1} + X_{L2}$), can now be determined from the measured quantities.

It is considered that $R_1 = R_2 = R_{eq}/2$ and $X_{L1} = X_{L2} = X_{eq}/2$.

$$\%R_{eq} = \frac{P_{fl} * 100}{S}$$

$$\%X_{eq} = \sqrt{\%Z_{eq}^2 - \%R_{eq}^2}$$

$$X_{eqHV} = \frac{\%X_{eq}}{10} * Z_{bHV}$$

$$X_{eqLV1} = \frac{\%X_{eq} * 9}{10 * a * a} * Z_{bHV}$$

$$X_{eqLV2} = \frac{\%X_{eq} * 9}{10 * b * b} * Z_{bHV}$$

where: R_{eq} is equivalent resistance of primary and secondary, X_{eq} is equivalent reactance of primary and secondary, Z_{eq} is equivalent impedance, R_{eqHV} is the resistance of primary winding (delta), R_{eqLV} is the resistance of secondary winding (star), X_{eqHV} is the reactance of primary winding (delta), X_{eqLV} is the reactance of secondary winding (star), c is the turn ratio.

To convert DC to AC, inverter has been added with PWM control. The switching frequency used in 10 kHz. Individual IGBTs are controlled, and the control strategy is based on dq control. Further details are provided in the following sections. The input for this converter is booster converter output. Thus, the dc link voltage 800 V is connected to it. The output of the inverter is fed to grid with LCL filter added in between to remove the harmonics and smoothen the output waveform. In order to measure the current, VI measurement is added in which only current is enabled.

The output current of the grid-connected inverter is obtained by the Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) method, so it contains higher-order harmonics. Therefore, the L filter most commonly is used between inverter and the grid. However, the L filter suppresses existing harmonics and has slow system dynamic response large power applications. Besides, a high voltage drop occurs in L filter. Instead of the advanced L-filter, a high-order LCL filter has been used to correct the output currents of the Voltage Source converter (VSC). Compared to the L filter, the LCL filter is known to be more effective in reducing the switching harmonics, but has a resonance problem. Furthermore, the design process that determines the parameter values of the LCL filter is quite complex compared to the L filter. Due to various limitations such as filter size, current harmonics, the power absorbed in the filter capacitor, it is important to select the appropriate parameters.

Following steps are adopted in the design of LCL filter:

1. Selection of switching frequency ($F_{sw} = 10 \text{ kHz}$)
2. Selection of resonant frequency ($f_{res} = \frac{F_{sw}}{10} = 1 \text{ kHz}$)
3. Finding value of capacitance (C') $C' = \frac{0.05 \cdot S}{V^2 \cdot 2 \cdot \pi \cdot f} = 100 \text{ } \mu\text{F}$, where grid frequency ($f = 50 \text{ Hz}$), grid voltage ($V = 230 \text{ V}$), power ($S = 100 \text{ kVA}$).
4. Finding value of inductance (L'); the LCL filter inductance chosen on each side of capacitance is $500 \text{ } \mu\text{H}$.

Figure 5: Inverter

The grid with one MV/LV transformer, a branched line on the LV side and two variable loads at LV and MV sides respectively has been simulated using Simulink – Simscape. The topology is shown Figure 6 with the detail of the equivalent circuit for the transformer.

The green elements are cable lines, modeled using a T equivalent with the cable capacitance in the middle. The dark red elements are resistive loads, with which the resultant damping effect was verified.

The grid is excited with a chirp signal at the far end (red generator) and the voltages at the point of injection (VLV or simply VLV), and at the LV sides (VLV2) and MV sides (VMV) of the transformer, are simulated. The chirp signal is made varying between 1 kHz and 150 kHz. From these quantities the frequency response is

calculated by determining the instantaneous frequency, interval by interval, and plotting the ratio of the amplitude of the respective voltage components, obtaining two frequency responses.

Figure 6: Scheme of the simplified system for frequency response determination (comprising a low voltage side and a medium voltage level).

The model of the transformer has been augmented by introducing stray capacitance terms, taken from [46] and transforming the capacitive terms for the equivalent circuit referred to the LV side (where relationships are well summarized in [47]).

The behaviors that were investigated are the influence of the long cable and its stray capacitance, the effect of the loading level (surely providing some damping), and the behavior of the MV/LV transformer with and without stray capacitance terms.

Simulations have been parameterized, as described in the following table, changing the length of the cable from 400 m to 4 km, its stray capacitance from 20 nF/km to 200 nF/km and loading from 10% to 30% of the transformer nominal power (having a fixed 10% load at the MV side).

	Green curves	Brown curves	Blue curves
	short cable (400 m) low cable cap (20 nF/km)	long cable (4000 m) low cable cap (20 nF/km)	long cable (4000 m) high cable cap (200 nF/km)
loading: MV 10% / LV 10%+cable no trafo parasitic cap FR1 freq resp.	Figure 7: dark curve	Figure 7: dark curve	Figure 7: dark curve
loading: MV 10% / LV 30%+cable no trafo parasitic cap FR1 freq resp.	Figure 7: bright curve	Figure 7: bright curve	Figure 7: bright curve
loading: MV 10% / LV 30%+cable no trafo parasitic cap FR2 freq resp.	Figure 8: bright curve	Figure 8: bright curve	Figure 8: bright curve
loading: MV 10% / LV 30%+cable trafo parasitic cap 1-3 nF FR2 freq resp.	Figure 8: bright curve Figure 9: thin dashed curve	Figure 8: bright curve Figure 9: thin dashed curve	Figure 8: bright curve Figure 9: thin dashed curve
loading: MV 10% / LV 30%+cable trafo parasitic cap 10-15 nF FR2 freq resp.	Figure 8: bright curve Figure 9: thick dashed curve	Figure 8: bright curve Figure 9: thick dashed curve	Figure 8: bright curve Figure 9: thick dashed curve
loading: MV 10%+cable / LV 30%+cable trafo parasitic cap 10-15 nF FR2 freq resp.	Figure 9: black		

The curves for the three cases show a resonance that goes from the high frequency at the margin of the 150 kHz interval (green curve) down to about 25 kHz (blue curve). The peak amplitude is slightly higher at 25 kHz thanks to the lower losses. The orange-brown curves provide an intermediate resonance at 80 kHz, since the cable length is long, but a low parasitic capacitance is assumed.

Each case has a dark curve obtained for low loading (10%-10%) and a bright curve for higher loading (10%-30%), showing the expected damping of about a factor of 2 (proportional to the amount of loading).

It is observed that the increased loading has almost no effect at low frequency, becoming more relevant above 10 kHz.

This frequency response FR1 shows the effectiveness of a SH source far from the transformer to transfer to the high voltage side.

Figure 7: FR1 transfer function (between the far source voltage and the MV-side voltage)

Independent on the distance of the SH source, the frequency response FR2 provides, instead, indication of how effectively SH signals transfer from the LV to the HV side through the transformer.

In Figure 8 the three bright curves in reality are overlapped to the dark ones, as measuring directly at the transformer LV side the effect of the loading at some distance away is not relevant.

The low-frequency behavior of the previous figure is confirmed with a significant amplification instead above about 100 kHz, as there is no attenuation along the cable lines, but the resonant effects remain, with the contribution of the transformer.

Figure 8: FR2 transfer function (between the LV-side voltage and the MV-side voltage)

The results of Figure 9 have been obtained introducing the transformer stray capacitance terms: the 1-2 capacitance term across the LV and HV side is responsible mainly for the almost flat transfer curve, especially for the case with the largest capacitance value (thick dashed). The resonant dip is quite narrow as iron and copper losses at high frequency within the transformer are not modeled (they should include skin and proximity effect and core losses), but this is not so relevant as such short frequency interval may be neglected. What is relevant is that the thick dashed curves agree on a flat frequency response at a value slightly larger than 0.01.

Quite interesting is the effect of including cables on the MV side in some way putting the MV transformer terminals in a higher impedance condition: the black thick curve provides an estimate of the amount of disturbance transmitted across the transformer, with an efficiency of about 0.02 (so doubled with respect to the thick dashed curves).

Figure 9: FR2 transfer function introducing parasitic capacitance: small capacitance (thin dashed) and large capacitance (thick dashed); the bright curves are those of the case without parasitic capacitance terms

The results discussed so far indicate attenuation between 0.1 and 0.01 for the modeled transformer, with peaks towards unity at resonances. The real disturbance at the HV voltage level (in this case a Medium Voltage value of 11 kV with a turns ratio of 27.5) is obtained by multiplying the obtained values for the turns ratio, indicating:

- transmission values between 0.3 and 0.01 for SH sources far away and decoupled by the connecting cable, with an overall linear behavior with frequency provided by the inductive parts in the absence of parasitic capacitance terms for the transformer;
- transmission values approaching 0.01-0.02 to multiply by the turns ratio, resulting in an effectiveness of 0.3-0.5 for a wide range of frequency, thanks to the parasitic capacitance terms;
- the same parasitic terms introduce a significant amplification about approximately 50 kHz, for which an effectiveness of transfer of SH distortion of several units may be reached, up to an ideal maximum of about 30; in reality the turns ratio is bound to decrease with frequency for the reduced permeability of the core, so that amplification of some units may be expected as a maximum at such high-frequency resonances;
- it is observed that the switching transients of power converters have large dv/dt values able to significantly excite such resonances and propagate to the HV side.

A simple case has been simulated where the source of SH emissions is a PWM inverter, simulating the situation of a PV inverter connected on the LV side of a MV-LV grid.

The inverter is assumed 100 kW providing power sourced from a PV installation at 800 Vdc.

It is connected to the rest of the LV network with a cable of nominal length 1 km (tested to 3 km in one simulation).

The LV grid has also a passive load of 100 kW, configured with a 10% of inductive reactive power. The MV grid is supplied from a source with a nominal power of 10 MVA and the nominal voltage is 22 kV (the reason for selecting this voltage level is the availability of accurate data for the MV/LV transformer).

The MV/LV transformer is a 350 kVA transformer, with 4% short-circuit reactance. Additional transformer capacitance has been simulated in line, ranging between 3 and 20 nF during simulations.

The MV grid is distributed over a length of 10 km (4 cable sections by 2.5 km each, for which cable capacitance was included with a conservative value of 100 nF/km). It will be observed that long cables provide decoupling of disturbance but can trigger network resonances at lower frequency and thus more critical.

The analysis was carried out to get the feeling of the relevance of the various parameters and an estimate of the intensity of the distortion caused on the LV and MV sides. As we will see, the combinations of parameters are many and various phenomena intermingle: resonances at LV and MV side, voltage drop caused by cable length, resonance and bypass of the transformer due to capacitance, damping provided by passive loads.

The inverter filter has been designed as LCL, as customary nowadays to interface such PV inverters, and similar power converters. The inductance has been calculated trying to keep the voltage drop acceptable, also in a control perspective, as longitudinal filter inductance causes always delay in the control response. A value of 340 uH has been estimated, that selecting a resonance frequency slightly below 2 kHz, leads to a filter capacitance of 40 nF.

The overall scheme of the simulated MV and LV network is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Block diagram of the Simulink model

The results of the various simulations are reported in the following and discussed at the end.

Some simulations have checked the effect of the MV/LV transformer capacitance, decreasing and increasing the assumed 10 nF to 3 nF and 20 nF, that are two values in line with the extreme values.

The effect also of the length of the LV cable is considered, as it adds in series to the output inductance L2 of the inverter filter; it is clear that one of the purposes of L2 is right hiding variability of the connection, allowing stability and robustness of sizing and control. It is thus not expected a significant influence from non-dramatic increase of LV cable length.

The effect of the cables has been checked by reducing the length of the MV cables from a total 10 km to 4 km.

The effect then of the damping caused by the connected loads is checked by increasing the MV side loading from 100 kW to 500 kW and then 1500 kW.

(a)

(b)

Figure 11: (a) Voltage and (b) Current spectra at LV side (blue) and MV side (red). Nominal case.

(a)

(b)

Figure 12: (a) Voltage and (b) Current spectra at LV side (blue) and MV side (red). Transformer capacitance 3 nF

(a)

(b)

Figure 13: (a) Voltage and (b) Current spectra at LV side (blue) and MV side (red). Transformer capacitance 20 nF.

(a)

(b)

Figure 14: (a) Voltage and (b) Current spectra at LV side (blue) and MV side (red). MV cable length 4 km.

(a)

(b)

Figure 15: (a) Voltage and (b) Current spectra at LV side (blue) and MV side (red). LV cable length 3 km.

(a)

(b)

Figure 16: (a) Voltage and (b) Current spectra at LV side (blue) and MV side (red). MV side loading 500 kW

(a)

(b)

Figure 17: (a) Voltage and (b) Current spectra at LV side (blue) and MV side (red). MV side loading 1500 kW

Some conclusions may be based on the previous results, regarding both the effects of single parameters and scenarios (e.g. cable length, loading level, stray capacitance, etc.) and the general values that we may assign to this type of distortion, in order to establish reference levels for the instrumentation necessary to their measurement. The nominal case shows the following distortion level:

Starting for the nominal case with 10 nF of transformer stray capacitance between the primary and secondary windings, the effect is prevalently the increase of the resonance phenomenon, lowered to 50 kHz (from the previous nearly 60 kHz), with an increase of the MV voltage to 0.5 V with 20 nF.

	V_LV (mV)	V_MV (mV)	I_LV (mA)	I_MV (mA)
few kHz	10-100	10-100	10-30	<1
switching freq. (10 kHz)	400	400	3	10
first harm. of the switching freq. (20-50 kHz)	10-100	20-40	1-200	0.05-0.5
possible resonance	--	60 @ 60 kHz	--	0.1 @ 60 kHz

The effect then of the MV cable shortening is important for the current on the MV side, as shorter cables have lower impedance while pushing resonances to higher frequency. The effect is a MV voltage of 150-160 mV at 90 kHz, and a corresponding current of 40 mA. There is also a slight increase of the LV side voltage to about 20-50 mV at 90 kHz (at resonance). Increasing the length of the LV cable does not cause a significant change except a marginal increase of V_MV at the resonance of 90 kHz, from about 150-160 mV to 200 mV. The damping effect of the loading level is perceivable in the lower part of the frequency interval, where at already the switching frequency of 10 kHz it is marginal. The reason is that the loads are modeled as RL passive circuits, neglecting their capacitance.

To conclude, the estimate distortion levels should not be taken as maximum values, because there may be critical situations where local resonances may enhance voltage or current components, and because the nominal power of the involved elements is not dramatically large, although being on the high side. The estimated spectra indicate plausible values showing the range of variation of the main components, supporting consequently the definition of suitable likely minimum values that in turn define sensitivity levels for the involved instrumentation.

On the other hand, we need to underline that such low values would be of no interest in terms of disturbance or stress to components and, consequently, do not represent a requirement for the instrumentation.

2.2 Accuracy and Uncertainty Requirements for ITs

As mentioned in 2.1, IEC 61869-1 introduces an extension of accuracy class (Table 3: Accuracy requirement for harmonics up to 150 kHz), particularly under non-sinusoidal conditions caused by harmonics.

Table 2-2 Accuracy requirement for harmonics up to 150 kHz

Accuracy class	Ratio error at frequencies shown below			Phase error at frequencies shown below		
	%			Degrees		
WB1	$f_r < f \leq 1 \text{ kHz}$	$1 < f \leq 1,5 \text{ kHz}$	$1,5 < f \leq 3 \text{ kHz}$	$f_r < f \leq 1 \text{ kHz}$	$1 < f \leq 1,5 \text{ kHz}$	$1,5 < f \leq 3 \text{ kHz}$
WB2	$f_r < f \leq 5 \text{ kHz}$	$5 < f \leq 10 \text{ kHz}$	$10 < f \leq 20 \text{ kHz}$	$f_r < f \leq 5 \text{ kHz}$	$5 < f \leq 10 \text{ kHz}$	$10 < f \leq 20 \text{ kHz}$
WB3	$f_r < f \leq 20 \text{ kHz}$	$20 < f \leq 50 \text{ kHz}$	$50 < f \leq 150 \text{ kHz}$	$f_r < f \leq 20 \text{ kHz}$	$20 < f \leq 50 \text{ kHz}$	$50 < f \leq 150 \text{ kHz}$
WB4	$f_r < f \leq 50 \text{ kHz}$	$50 < f \leq 150 \text{ kHz}$	$150 < f \leq 500 \text{ kHz}$	$f_r < f \leq 50 \text{ kHz}$	$50 < f \leq 150 \text{ kHz}$	$150 < f \leq 500 \text{ kHz}$
0,1	±1	±2	±5	±1	±2	±5
0,2 – 0,2 S	±2	±4	±5	±2	±4	±5
0,5 – 0,5 S	±5	±10	±10	±5	±10	±20
1	±10	±20	±20	±10	±20	±20
Protection	±10	±20	±30	-	-	-

These harmonics vary with network configuration and voltage level and are particularly relevant for measurement systems, power quality analysis, and protection functions. To address this, the standard allows the use of accuracy class extensions that describe an instrument transformer's performance at higher frequencies:

- WB0: up to the 13th harmonic
- WB1: up to 3 kHz
- WB2: up to 20 kHz
- WB3: up to 150 kHz

These extensions are added to the base accuracy class (e.g., Class 0.5-WB1) and provide a clear, practical way to indicate performance across a wide range of harmonic frequencies. For Low-Power Instrument Transformers (LPITs) and Stand-Alone Merging Units (SAMUs), the WB0 extension is mandatory. For conventional ITs, these extensions remain optional, although multiple extensions can be declared when relevant (e.g., Class 0.2-WB1 and Class 0.5-WB2). This system applies equally to both VTs and CTs. The introduction of this extension scheme in IEC 61869-1 represents a significant innovation, addressing the evolving needs of modern power systems where harmonics and wideband signal content are increasingly prevalent.

In the context of IT assessments, metrological traceability and the associated measurement uncertainty are essential to ensure the reliability of conformity evaluations. Metrological traceability refers to the property of a measurement result that allows it to be linked to a reference—typically an SI unit—through an unbroken, documented chain of calibrations, each contributing to the overall uncertainty. National Metrology Institutes play a key role by providing calibration and traceability to the SI system through transfer standards such as high-accuracy comparators, reference transformers, or other precision devices. These transfer standards are then used by laboratories or manufacturers to verify the accuracy of ITs.

NMIs can calibrate these transfer standards with the best achievable uncertainty, known as UNMI, which indicates the lowest possible uncertainty under controlled laboratory conditions. This value considers all relevant factors, including the performance of the standard, reference values, environmental influences, and traceability to national or international standards. However, when the transfer standard is later used by a manufacturer to evaluate an instrument transformer, the total measurement uncertainty naturally increases. This is due to additional factors such as the measurement setup characteristics (e.g., cabling and connections), operator variability, environmental conditions (temperature, electromagnetic interference), the influence of the transformer under test (loading effects, saturation, drift, linearity), and the resolution and linearity of the measuring instruments.

In practical applications, these additional influences are often estimated to increase the uncertainty by a factor, usually between 3 and 5, relative to U_{NMI} . This leads to a total expanded uncertainty for the calibration of the instrument transformer:

$$U_{IT} = (3 \text{ to } 5) \times U_{NMI} \quad (1)$$

According to metrology best practices, the calibration process uncertainty should be significantly lower than the device under test's tolerance or accuracy, typically by a factor of 3. This is commonly referred to as the Test Uncertainty Ratio (TUR), which is calculated as:

$$TUR = \frac{\text{Accuracy IT}}{U_{IT}} \geq 3 \quad (2)$$

For example, at 50 Hz or 60 Hz, NMIs can calibrate transfer standards with an uncertainty typically around 0.002%. According to equation (1), this results in a total uncertainty of 0.006% to 0.01%. If an IT with a declared accuracy of 0.1% is being assessed, the resulting TUR ranges from 10 to 16, comfortably exceeding the minimum recommended value of 3 for reliable conformity assessment. Therefore, the achieved uncertainty level fully complies with metrological requirements for assessing an instrument transformer with a 0.1% accuracy class at 50 Hz. This confirms that the traceability chain, from the NMI to the transfer standard and from the transfer standard to the instrument transformer, is reliable and appropriate. The expanded uncertainty remains within acceptable limits, ensuring that conformity or non-conformity decisions are statistically reliable and metrologically justified.

To determine the minimum accuracy requirement for ITs operating up to 150 kHz, equations (1) and (2) should be combined, resulting in (3):

$$\text{Accuracy IT} \geq (9 \text{ to } 15) \times U_{NMI} \tag{3}$$

Since degrades with increasing frequency due to the frequency response of the reference equipment and system limitations due the small level of harmonics which poses a challenge for accurate measurement. ITs used up to 150 kHz are typically designed with technologies where the fundamental output is scaled down to standard values such as 1 Vp to be compatible with conventional acquisition systems. However, harmonic components are usually less than 1 % of the fundamental, and therefore their output voltages are significantly lower, often in the millivolt range. This makes the reliable measurement of these components difficult, especially when considering the resolution, linearity, and noise floor of the measuring instruments. As a result, the ability to characterize harmonic performance is directly influenced by the limitations of the measurement system itself.

Two main methods can be used to assess the performance of ITs at higher frequencies:

- Frequency sweep method (simplified method): injecting a known sinusoidal signal at various frequencies into the IT and measuring the output voltage or current.
- Multitoned method (reference method): injecting a fundamental signal superimposed with one or several harmonic components and measuring the resulting output quantity.

Both methods lead to an increase in measurement uncertainty as the frequency rises. The uncertainty budget becomes the limiting factor when determining whether an IT meets a given accuracy class at a specific frequency. We can derive the minimum required accuracy of the instrument transformer as a function of the NMI’s typical calibration uncertainty at each frequency range. This process is performed inversely: instead of computing the uncertainty from a given IT accuracy, we determine the minimum accuracy requirement that still satisfies the $TUR \geq 3$ criterion. The two tables below have been developed based on this approach and are differentiated by the relative amplitude of harmonic components:

- Table 2-3 assumes the harmonic component at the output of the IT under consideration has an amplitude of 10 mV and 1 mV, using the first method.
- Table 2-4 considers the harmonic component under consideration using the second method.

Table 2-3 Recommended Minimum Accuracy For Harmonics Using The First Method

Amplitude of harmonics at the output of IT	Frequency Range	Typical U_{NMI}	Minimum required IT Accuracy
>10 mV	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.01%	0.15%
	10 kHz – 150 kHz	0.02%	0.30%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.03%	0.45%
>1 mV	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.06%	0.9%
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	0.2%	3,0%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.3%	4.5%
>10 mA	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.02%	0.15%
	10 kHz – 150 kHz	0.03%	0.30%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.05%	0.45%
>1 mA	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.1%	0.9%
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	0.2%	3,0%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.3%	4.5%

Table 2-4 Recommended Minimum Accuracy For Harmonics Using The Second Method

Amplitude of harmonics at the output of IT	Frequency Range	Typical U_{NMI}	Minimum required IT Accuracy
>10 mV	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.05%	0.75%
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	0.10%	1.50%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.10%	1.50%
>1 mV	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.50%	7.50%
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	1.00%	15.00%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	1.50%	22.00%
>10 mA	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.10%	0.75%
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	0.20%	1.50%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.20%	1.50%
>1 mA	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.50%	7.50%
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	1.00%	15.00%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	1.50%	22.00%

The tables show that the alignment between theoretical metrological constraints and IEC61869-2024 requirement are consistent when the output voltage of the IT is higher than 10 mV using both methods. When the voltage is lower, the minimum required specification surpasses sometimes what is mentioned in the IEC61869-2024. So, it is then important to determine conditions of the minimum output voltage of harmonics, which is proportional to the percentage of harmonics relative to the fundamental.

Indeed, when measuring high voltage signals that include superimposed harmonic components, the measurement uncertainty can vary significantly depending on several key factors:

- Scale Factor of the IT, typically used to scale down high voltage signals to standard levels, such as 1 V or 10 V, suitable for acquisition systems (usually with 16-bit or 18-bit resolution). The chosen scale factor directly affects the magnitude of the output signal. If the scale factor results in a low output voltage, especially for harmonic components, the relative uncertainty increases due to limitations in resolution and noise floor of the measuring system.
- Percentage of Harmonics: Harmonic components are often much smaller in amplitude than the fundamental frequency. When these small signals are measured at low voltage levels (e.g., due to high scaling or weak harmonic presence), they approach the resolution limit of the data acquisition system. As a result, the signal-to-noise ratio deteriorates, leading to degraded measurement accuracy and increased uncertainty for harmonic content.
- Resolution and Noise of the Measuring System: The effective resolution of the acquisition system limits the ability to detect small voltage changes. For low-amplitude harmonics superimposed on a high voltage signal, the quantization error, inherent noise, and possible aliasing effects become more significant, further contributing to the overall uncertainty.

The first method (simplified one) gives better accuracy assessment compared with the first second one (reference one) but do not give any possible interactions between the fundamental component and the harmonics component.

However, some rated conditions need to be specified to better meet these accuracy requirements.

3 Technical Solutions and Recommendations for Testing

The third chapter moves from principles to practice. It describes the generation systems developed for voltage and current testing, explains the measurement strategies adopted to ensure accuracy, and summarizes the experimental results that validate these approaches. Finally, it translates these findings into concrete recommendations for IEC/CENELEC TC38, outlining how they can be incorporated into future standards.

3.1 Definition of voltage and current levels

This section establishes appropriate voltage and current levels – informed by standards, literature, and recent research – for testing medium-voltage (MV) instrument transformers (measurement transformers) under high-frequency distortion conditions (supraharmonics up to 150 kHz). This includes summarizing key findings from previous activities, identifying recommended practices/guidelines, comparing results across sources, and noting any gaps or needed additional information.

Instrument transformers (voltage transformers VTs and current transformers CTs) are useful to scale down power system voltages and currents for metering and protection. Traditional accuracy specifications and test methods cover only power frequency (50 / 60 Hz) and low harmonics. However, supraharmonic distortion – defined as high-frequency components in the range 2 kHz to 150 kHz – is increasingly present in modern grids due to the proliferation of power electronic devices (inverters for solar/wind plants, EV chargers, LED drives, etc.). Supraharmonics can impact power quality (PQ), causing additional losses, insulation stress, and potential malfunctions in equipment and measurement devices.

The recently released IEC 61869-1 Edition 2 Standard, issued in 2023, extends instrument transformer accuracy classes over five wideband ranges up to 500 kHz. In effect, manufacturers can specify accuracy of voltage and current transformers, voltage dividers and current sensors for HF components (denoted classes WB0–WB4) – but the Standard doesn't provide very clear procedures or required waveforms to check the accuracy of conventional and low-power instrument transformers at those frequencies. As a result, there is a gap in how to characterize and verify instrument transformer performance at high frequency. To ensure reliable PQ measurements in the 9–150 kHz band range, realistic test waveforms and harmonics levels must be defined.

There is currently no direct standard which provides specific voltage/current test levels for instrument transformers at supraharmonic frequencies. Relevant standards provide context but not limits:

- IEC 61000-4-7 / -4-30 (EMC and PQ measurement standards) classify disturbances up to 150 kHz and recommend measurement methods (e.g. 2 kHz bands). They recognize “induced continuous waves” and “oscillatory transients” in this range, but do not specify compatibility levels for MV networks or test amplitudes for transformers. In practice, compatibility levels (commonly a few % of nominal) are often cited for lower frequencies (<2 kHz); above 9 kHz, no uniform emission limits exist yet in MV grid standards.
- IEEE 1159 (Power Quality monitoring) similarly classifies high-frequency phenomena but gives no numeric limits for 2–150 kHz in MV systems.
- IEC 61869-1 Ed.2 (2023) does define a method for determining the accuracy of ITs and LPITs for harmonics, based on the assigned wideband (WB) class. Still, the methodology as established in the standard is not fully detailed and presents significant limitations depending on the particular characteristics of the sensor to be characterized or the harmonic level to be verified. Notably, the IEC standard does not define the value of the harmonic percentage with respect to the fundamental signal that should be applied. This new version of the standard extends instrument transformer accuracy classes to cover high frequencies. Five wideband classes WB0–WB4 are defined, e.g. WB4 spans up to 500 kHz. However, the standard does not indicate how to test for these classes – it neither prescribes test waveforms nor states what magnitude of HF voltage/current to apply. It simply defines accuracy as a percentage error allowable in those frequency bands, leaving implementation to laboratories. For traditional inductive transformers (VTs/CTs), all wideband classes are optional; only low-power instrument transformers (LPITs), voltage divider and current sensors, the WB0 class requirements shall be at least satisfied.

- IEC Technical Committees: Several IEC TCs are examining supraharmatics (TC77A for EMC, TC38 for instrument transformers, TC8 for grid integration, etc.). Some have issued Technical Reports – e.g. IEC TR 63222-3 lists common sources of supraharmatics (EV chargers, PV inverters, etc.) and affected equipment – but binding test requirements are still under development. In this context, the IEC TC 38 "Instrument transformers" has assigned the task to TC38/WG47 "Evolution of Instrument transformer requirements for the modern market" to establish Task Forces to study the topic of extended frequency response qualification of Instrument Transformers for PQ measurement and travelling waves relaying applications and to study the topic relevant to the effects of combined influencing factors on the accuracy of Instrument Transformers. In addition, TC38 has identified a series of needs and open issues concerning the definition of measurement methods and test procedures for assessing the accuracy performance of ITs intended to be used for Power Quality Measurements, which have been submitted to the STAIR/EMPIR Committee.
- Given the standards' gap, literature reviews and measurement campaigns to analyze the levels and effects of supraharmatics in the grid have been performed in previous activities and described in previous sections.

3.1.1 Literature review

Both literature and standards are summarized to define "significant waveforms to test ITs". It concludes with some key consolidated points:

- Amplitude-Frequency Ranges: It confirms that supraharmatic sources (PV, wind, EV) typically inject frequencies below 50 kHz with amplitudes generally below 0.3 V; in some high-PV scenarios, up to 0.15 V at 126 kHz was found, likely due to resonances. Dominant emissions: 10 kHz (wind), 12–16 kHz (PV and EV chargers), sometimes with smaller multiples (32, 48, 68 kHz, etc.). In EV charging tests, 10 kHz components up to 1080 mA (at 16 A charge) and 45 kHz components ~200 mA (at 23 A charge) were recorded, meaning 4–5% of the 23 A current in a troublesome case. Those are among the higher reported percentages on the current side. Still, they were local to the device; once propagating through a transformer, the grid-side effect is smaller.
- Propagation Attenuation: The review details how supraharmatics propagate across transformers with various transfer ratios. A crucial observation: MV to LV transfer can sometimes amplify certain frequencies. For example, one measurement showed a 0.5 V LV distortion became ~1.5 V on the MV side at a resonance (transfer ratio 3 V/V). Generally, though, MV/LV transformers attenuate HF: often a 1 V LV distortion yields only 0.01–0.5 V on MV (i.e. <50% of turns ratio). This implies an instrument transformer on the MV side could see at most a few tenths of a percent of nominal from any single supraharmatic that originated in LV.
- Conclusions for Testing: To quote the paper, "The analysis of on-site results has shown it is difficult to define typical values... however, in general the frequencies are tied to converter switching and amplitudes do not exceed 5% in 9–150 kHz". Moreover, "test procedures must replicate actual operational conditions, i.e., fundamental plus disturbances". The document recommends testing wideband accuracy by applying a fundamental and superimposing multiple high frequency components up to 5%, then evaluating the transformer's output using the same PQ indices that a meter would use (e.g., measure how much the HF is attenuated or phase-shifted by the transformer).

As a summary, the document recommends testing the accuracy of the ITs at the following current and voltage levels:

- Voltage test levels: ~0.5% to 5% of nominal RMS per HF component, depending on frequency. In MV terms, this is on the order of 0.1% (for higher kHz) up to 1% (for low kHz where emissions cluster). For example, appropriate bands would be in the order of 5% of nominal for 2–10 kHz band, 2% for 10–50 kHz and 1% for 50–150 kHz. This aligns with literature: lower-frequency "supraharmatics"

overlap with high-order harmonics, which occasionally reach a few percent (e.g., some PV inverters had ~2% at 2.5 kHz, whereas above 50 kHz it's typically < 1%.

- Current test levels: A similar percentage rated current. If a CT is rated 200/1 A, injecting up to ~1 A of HF (0.5%) would be appropriate. In many cases, supraharmmonic currents are limited by device filters and don't approach 1% at MV level. But testing up to 1% ensures covering a broad range of scenarios, including an aggregation of many devices.

3.1.2 Measurement campaign

A field measurement campaign was conducted in 2024 on a medium-voltage network in Milan (Unareti 23 kV feeder supplying EV charging stations). This study directly measured the natural supraharmmonic content on an MV system over several months. Key findings include:

- Supraharmmonic Voltage Levels: The measured MV phase-to-ground voltage distortion in 9-150 kHz was in the order of a few tens of volts (RMS) per 10 kHz band. Table 3-1 compiles the maximum RMS voltage in each 10 kHz band group (Y1: 50 Hz–10 kHz through Y18: 170–180 kHz). The highest HF voltage observed was about 29.07 V in the 140–150 kHz band, and values in most bands were 15–25 V or lower. Even the 9–10 kHz band (Y2) peaked at ~32.4 V. Considering the MV rated voltage of 20 kV, these correspond to extremely small fractions (~0.1–0.2%). For perspective, 29 V of HF on 20 kV is 0.15 % of nominal. The 50 Hz–10 kHz band (excluding the fundamental) had a higher residual (~49 V), but that primarily reflects low-order harmonics up to 9 kHz.
- Supraharmmonic Current Levels: The currents were measured via Rogowski coils on the LV side of the substation transformers (since the MV feeder load flows into two 0.4 kV, 400–630 kVA transformers). Maximum HF current components varied widely between the two measured paths (likely due to different loading). Current I1 had a highest HF component ~1.83 A in the 0–10 kHz band, dropping to < 0.1 A beyond 20 kHz. Current I2 showed an anomalous 159 A reading in the 0–10 kHz band (this may include a fundamental leakage or an outlier), but beyond that it too dropped to ~1.2 A at 10–20 kHz and ≤ 0.1 A above 20 kHz [2]. Thus, typical HF currents in the LV circuit were well below 1 A RMS for $f > 20$ kHz. On the MV 15 A line side, that would translate to only a few milliamps of HF current after accounting for the transformer ratio.

This measurement campaign supports setting supraharmmonic test voltages in the tens-of-volts range for MV transformers. For a 20 kV class VT, it would be appropriate to apply e.g. 50 V at 10 kHz, 30 V at ~150 kHz, etc., simultaneously with the rated $20\text{ kV}/\sqrt{3}$ fundamental. Likewise, for a CT rated e.g. 100 A, it would be appropriate to superimpose supraharmmonics in the order of 0.5 - 1 A in the lower kHz (1% HF distortion) and a few hundred mA at higher kHz to emulate worst-case conditions.

Table 3-1: Maximum values of Y_g over band groups of measured quantities

	Y_g								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
V	48.99	32.41	19.62	22.72	19.77	18.14	17.46	18.55	16.02
I_1	1.83	1.70	0.07	0.10	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.01
I_2	159.64	1.21	0.13	0.06	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.03	0.02
	Y_g								
	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
V	17.53	18.13	16.39	14.47	20.51	29.07	24.57	17.27	4.49
I_1	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.08	0.01
I_2	0.10	0.01	0.01	0.08	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.61	0.04

In summary, previous activities conclude that testing with supraharmonic voltage/current components on the order of 1-5 % of the transformer’s rating. This aligns with both typical supraharmonic magnitudes recorded on-site and protective considerations. The exact values within that range can be adjusted by frequency band. For example, 5 % of the nominal rating in the lower supraharmonic range, while 1–3 % in the upper supraharmonic range. In any case, to harmonize the voltage and current injection through all frequencies, it might be appropriate to aim to the same percentage of supraharmonics through the whole frequency range from 9 – 150 kHz. An example of the voltage and current levels based on this percentage is given below:

- Regarding the voltage levels, for example, testing a 20 kV VT with a 5 % of high-frequency content distributed across relevant frequencies would mean injecting up to 1000 V of supraharmonics from 9-150 kHz.
- Regarding the current levels, for example, testing a 200 A CT with a 5 % of high-frequency content distributed across relevant frequencies would mean injecting 10 A of supraharmonics from 9-150 kHz.

Additionally, two further considerations can be added to the conclusions, as it would be appropriate to assess them during the next activities that will be carried out in WP2 and WP3:

- The influence of the injected voltage/current value on the LPIT: If the applied levels at the input are too low, the resulting signals at the output may be of very low magnitude. This can lead to technical limitations when trying to obtain results with low measurement uncertainty.
- The influence of the employed methodology: It is possible that determining a sensor’s accuracy for a specific harmonic level alone is not equivalent to evaluating the sensor’s response when this harmonic is superimposed on the fundamental frequency. Although this methodology is accepted by IEC 61869-1, there is no evidence that the results obtained are equivalent in all cases.

3.2 Performance indexes (PIs)

Performance indexes (PIs) synthesize and implement assessments of IT accuracy and may be scalar or vector, frequency- or time-domain-based, etc. They are reviewed and discussed below.

3.2.1 PIs in the frequency domain

PIs range from the classical amplitude error and phase error to more elaborate combinations of error components extending them to the harmonic and supraharmonic interval.

Single frequency ratio error $\varepsilon(f)$ and phase error $\Delta\varphi(f)$:

$$\varepsilon(f) = \frac{k_r X_s(f) - X_p(f)}{X_p(f)} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta\varphi(f) = \varphi_s(f) - \varphi_p(f) \quad (2)$$

where k_r is the expected IT ratio, X indicates either voltage or current for generality, and subscripts “p” and “s” indicate primary or secondary, respectively.

The ratio $\varepsilon(f)$, if calculated not using magnitudes, but complex quantities, may become the so-called “harmonic transfer function” $H_{IT}(f)$ (the frequency-dependent complex ratio of the IT), also named “Frequency-Response Deviation Index”.

A straightforward extension is the combined evaluation over an assigned frequency interval or band, calculating indexes like:

- the maximum of $H_{IT}(f)$ expressed also as the ratio -1: $\max |H_{IT}(f)| = \max \left| \frac{kx_s}{X_p} - 1 \right|$ (3)
- some total rms or weighted rms combination of the frequency values as shown below.

In fact, extending the single-frequency indexes to weighted quantities covering an assigned frequency interval, we get a PI called Total Frequency Response Deviation ε_{TFRD} [24]:

$$\varepsilon_{TFRD} = \frac{k_r TFRD_s - TFRD_p}{TFRD_p} \quad (4)$$

where

$$TFRD_p = \frac{\sum_{f=f_1}^{f_N} X_p^2(f)}{X_p(f^*)} \quad TFRD_s = \frac{\sum_{f=f_1}^{f_N} X_s^2(f)}{X_s(f^*)} \quad (5)$$

and f^* indicates the reference frequency, that may be the center band of the interval, the largest component, etc.

A similar approach is taking the quantity $H_{IT}(f)$ as expressed above (with notation separating the ratio and the “-1”) and consider it a complex quantity named ξ to split then in a deterministic and statistic part:

$$\xi = \xi_d - \xi_s \quad (6)$$

where the statistic part represents the unknown distortion of the IT itself [48]. As a remark, this part is unknown, but in principle deterministic, as the mechanism at its origin is the IT non-linearity.

Another PI borrowed from synchrophasor metrology (IEEE C37.118) is the Total Vector Error (TVE), which was classified as a dynamic index in [24], but limited to the fundamental. Extension to the entire frequency range with a quantity that depends on frequency is straightforward and was proposed in various contexts, i.e. such as vs harmonic order, vs frequency, etc. [48], [49]. It is another manipulation of the quantity, this time not expressing the complex quantities separately but providing their amplitudes; thus, it is a scalar that weights both the ratio and phase errors.

$$TVE = \sqrt{\frac{[\text{Re}\{k_r X_s(f)\} - \text{Re}\{X_p(f)\}]^2 + [\text{Im}\{k_r X_s(f)\} - \text{Im}\{X_p(f)\}]^2}{[\text{Re}\{X_p(f)\}]^2 + [\text{Im}\{X_p(f)\}]^2}} \quad (7)$$

In this representation the vectors of secondary and primary measured quantities are assumed to be very generally frequency vectors, without any further restriction on harmonic components or similar. As harmonic components they appeared in [24].

Another approach that has the merit of being well known and tested is using existing PQ indexes to benchmark ITs accuracy: a weighted sum of harmonic components is, for example, an all-comprehensive index for that frequency range, that summarizes the amplitude of harmonic components and may be used as well to summarize the IT behavior vs frequency at the harmonic frequencies, when fed with composite test signals [50].

The proposed indexes are all variants of THD tailored to a specific frequency interval (named “harmonic” [100 Hz – 2500 Hz], “extended” [2550 – 9000 Hz] and “supraharmonic” [9050 – 150000 Hz]), assuming, first, an analysis carried out at multiples of 50 Hz, but, then, testing also other smaller frequency resolutions (e.g. 5 Hz).

$$THD = \frac{\sum_{h=2}^{h_{\max}} X_h^2}{X_1} \quad (8)$$

where the summation of harmonic components is extended up to h_{\max} , usually taken as 40 or 50.

$$TWD = \frac{\sqrt{X^2 - X_1^2}}{X_1} \quad (9)$$

where X^2 denotes the total rms squared of quantity X .

The THD index is then applied to the three frequency intervals identified above, deriving

$$THD_{PQ} = \frac{\sum_{h=2}^{50} X_h^2}{X_1} \quad (10)$$

$$THD_{EX} = \frac{\sum_{h=51}^{180} X_h^2}{X_1} \quad (11)$$

$$THD_{SH} = \frac{\sum_{h=181}^{450} X_h^2}{X_1} \quad (12)$$

and, correspondingly, three versions of such metrics normalized by TWD may also be derived:

$$\rho_{PQ} = \frac{THD_{PQ}}{TWD} \quad (13)$$

$$\rho_{EX} = \frac{THD_{EX}}{TWD} \quad (14)$$

$$\rho_{SH} = \frac{THD_{SH}}{TWD} \quad (15)$$

These indexes may be used to test IT performance, starting from a reference test signal, for which all these indexes can be calculated providing a reference result. The signal is then fed to the IT under test and the output is treated as a new signal, to which the indexes are again applied. The two sets of indexes provide a quick way to evaluate the IT response. Due to the nature of the proposed indexes, only the amplitude response may be evaluated, as all such indexes are invariant to phase.

3.2.2 Pls in the time domain

The ratio error may be transferred into time domain with direct application to recorded waveforms $X_s(t)$ and $X_p(t)$, where they represent e.g. a pulse, surge or similar transient. Being not an exact one-to-one translation from frequency to time domain, its name has been changed to E_{L2} , being an L2 norm of the time-domain error:

$$E_{L2} = \frac{\sqrt{\int_{T_1}^{T_2} [k_r x_s(t) - x_p(t)]^2 dt}}{\sqrt{\int_{T_1}^{T_2} [x_p(t)]^2 dt}} \quad (16)$$

and the discrete time implementation is straightforward.

A remark is due for the verification of performance at high frequency: the two signals $x_s(t)$ and $x_p(t)$ are assumed in phase with the same origin, but $x_s(t)$ is unavoidably delayed by the IT delay. This may seem natural as also in frequency domain the phase rotation caused by the IT is well captured in the phase error quantity. However, here in time domain a delay would translate in an amplitude error: let's think for example in a perfect reproduction at the secondary of the primary signal, except for the introduce delay; in signal theory this is a linear phase system that introduces only a constant delay for all signal components, but the difference at the numerator of (16) would result in a significant amplitude error. For this reason, $x_s(t)$ and $x_p(t)$ should be aligned by the amount of delay estimated for the IT before proceeding with the calculation of various forms of error (e.g. by difference).

Taking the maximum instead of the L2 norm (which, for clarity, is equivalent to rms), then

$$E_{\max} = \max \left| \frac{k_r x_s(t) - x_p(t)}{x_p(t)} \right| \quad (17)$$

that may be useful for absolute accuracy, spotting out worst-case instantaneous deviations, and possibly finds application when ITs are used connected to protection relays. A smoothed version may be adopted, where occasionally excessive noise and spikes are leveled (pruned) before feeding the signals to E_{\max} .

Another similar metric is obtained taking not the maximum, but the cumulated absolute error, so what is called "integral absolute error":

$$E_{IAE} = \int_{T_1}^{T_2} \left| \frac{k_r x_s(t) - x_p(t)}{x_p(t)} \right| dt \quad (18)$$

All these metrics may be recalculated in their corresponding weighted versions, so multiplying the error by a weighting function $w(t)$ that filters to emphasize certain time intervals, such as the importance of the peak amplitude of an impulse, rather than matching its tail.

It is quite interesting to shift the paradigm from quantification of error to quantification of similarity, thus adopting a series of approaches that may be based on:

- correlation coefficient (or cosine similarity)

$$r = \frac{\int_{T_1}^{T_2} (k_r x_s(t)) x_p(t) dt}{\sqrt{\int_{T_1}^{T_2} (k_r x_s(t))^2 dt} \sqrt{\int_{T_1}^{T_2} (x_p(t))^2 dt}} \quad (19)$$

- correlation function (that is a more general expression, where the correlation coefficient r corresponds to its value at 0 lag)

$$R(\tau) = \frac{\int_{T_1}^{T_2} (k_r x_s(t)) x_p(t+\tau) dt}{\sqrt{\int_{T_1}^{T_2} (k_r x_s(t))^2 dt \int_{T_1}^{T_2} (x_p(t))^2 dt}} \quad (20)$$

where the integrals under square root at the denominator represent the normalization by the rms values of the primary and secondary (scaled) signals, as it was done above for the correlation coefficient.

Also for the calculation of the correlation coefficient r and correlation function $R(\tau)$ the delay introduced by the IT is relevant:

- in the case of r $x_s(t)$ must be adjusted for the delay to make the scalar product with $x_p(t)$ meaningful;
- for $R(\tau)$ in reality the delay comes out from the calculation as the τ value corresponding to the maximum of $R(\tau)$; this is in fact one of the most straightforward ways to determine the delay of a system; the interpretation of $R(\tau)$, then, must be done taking τ on the abscissa as the reference.

3.3 Characteristics of Real-World Disturbances (9–150 kHz)

Supraharmonic disturbances originate primarily from switching actions in converters and other electronic devices. They manifest as clusters of frequencies—typically around 10–16 kHz, 30–50 kHz, and extending up to 150 kHz—with amplitudes that, although small compared to the fundamental, can reach 0.1–0.5% of nominal voltage or current in medium-voltage networks. These components interact with network impedances, sometimes creating resonances that amplify their effect.

For instrument transformers, this means that their frequency response becomes critical. Attenuation and phase displacement increase with frequency, and external factors such as temperature and burden can exacerbate these deviations. Understanding these behaviors is essential for defining meaningful accuracy requirements.

3.4 Proposed Test Conditions and Reference Levels

To ensure consistency, the project recommends standardized test conditions. These include applying high-frequency components at levels between 1% and 5% of the fundamental, selecting representative frequency points across the 9–150 kHz range, and considering both single-tone and multitone excitations. Transient tests, based on damped sinusoidal waveforms, should also be included to replicate realistic overvoltage scenarios. Environmental factors such as temperature and burden must be controlled or compensated, as they can significantly influence results.

3.5 Proposed Test Waveforms

Addressing the discussed performance indexes, test waveforms in both standards and scientific literature have been conceived as superposition of:

- DC or AC fundamental “bias”;
- harmonics of different amplitude;
- supraharmonics of different amplitude.

3.5.1 Frequency-domain test signals

The most commonly used and preferred frequency-domain test signal is substantially a superposition of the three components: bias, harmonics and supraharmonics. An additional term may be an inter-harmonic component that, however, causes variability between the fundamental cycles, not being an integer multiple of the fundamental. The same may be said in general for supraharmonics, but their frequency is much higher and the cycle-to-cycle variability is lesser, notwithstanding that they may be easily generated synchronized with the fundamental (without loss of generality).

Going into the details of the most suitable amplitudes and frequency ranges and considering the typical sources of disturbance and disturbing/distorting components at LV and MV, it is possible to say Supraharmonic sources (photovoltaic parks, wind farms, electric vehicle charging stations) are a source of emissions mostly located in the first 50 kHz with amplitudes in voltage generally below a few V, as dictated by the EMC compatibility levels for residential, industrial and public networks (IEC 61000-2-2 and IEC 61000-2-4).

Typical switching frequencies are in the range of 4 to 20 kHz (typically 8 kHz, 10 kHz and 16 kHz are the mostly used) and harmonics of such switching components can be significant up to order 3 to 5, namely the previously announced 50 kHz, although resonances and specific scenarios do not exclude relevant components also in the rest of the supraharmonic range.

In terms of current values up to 1 A have been observed and in general some hundreds of mA for nominal currents in the order of tenths of A up to a hundred, so in the order of some %, 5% at most.

It may be concluded that tests of ITs should be carried out at distortion levels of some % of the fundamental to cover typical representative operating conditions. Supraharmonic amplitudes of 5% are already rare, although in extreme cases where the IT function would be early warning to protect network assets, even loosely quantified accuracy is acceptable (due to the relevance of the early warning function) [51].

We may thus synthesize the appropriate test levels as follows, remembering that IT accuracy verification does not imply the test of the entire operating range, rather the selection of relevant operating points in the expected span of supraharmonic distortion values.

- Voltage test levels: from 0.5% to 2% of nominal rms amplitude for LV applications for each high-frequency component, with possible derating (if necessary) above 50 kHz depending on frequency. For MV levels, a practical adaptation (also supported by grid measurement results) amplitude may be reduced privileging the low-frequency portion where larger components are expected: up to 1% of nominal rms amplitude up to 10 kHz, 0.2–0.5% between 10 and 50 kHz and 0.1% for the 50–150 kHz interval. This aligns with literature and experimental findings on the one hand and is achievable with available instrumentation.
- Current test levels: similar to the voltage test levels in p.u. of the nominal rms current.

Superposition of more than one supraharmonic component may be used to test phenomena of non-linearity and resulting inter-modulation products.

In both cases when testing with superposition of more than one supraharmonic component, the overall peak value of the supraharmonic test signal is the sum of the peak amplitudes, as it cannot be excluded that instantaneously over the entire test time interval all supraharmonic components are in phase. In this case, to cope with the capabilities of the instrumentation (in particular amplifiers), individual test levels of each supraharmonic component should be correspondingly reduced.

3.5.2 Time-domain test signals

The use of impulsive test waveforms has not been discussed extensively in the literature, except for the proposal of using a tapered sinc pulse with the objective of testing a multitude of frequency points with one test waveform (thanks to the flat spectrum) [52].

The sinc has an ideally rectangular spectrum where all components are zero after the cutoff frequency f_c . To this aim the sinc must have the form

$$s(t) = \frac{\sin(\pi t/T_c)}{\pi t/T_c} \quad (21)$$

where $T_c = 1/f_c$. Due to truncation of the sinc() signal in any practical implementation, the spectrum is corrupted and deviates from the desired rectangular form due to spectral leakage. As commonplace, in such case the time-domain signal may be shaped by a tapering window that controls spectral leakage; a tapering window with fast frequency decay should be selected in order to have as most rectangular as possible spectral shape.

In addition, aiming at generating large test amplitudes with already available instruments, surge and fast transient waveforms may be considered, as commonly used for electromagnetic immunity tests (IEC 61000-4-5 and IEC 61000-4-4 standards for definition and application of surges and fast transients, respectively).

In this case the IT transfer function is estimated by using a standard non-parametric estimate based on auto- and cross-spectra (indicated by $S_{pp}()$ and $S_{sp}()$, respectively):

$$\hat{H}_{IT}(f) = \frac{S_{sp}(f)}{S_{pp}(f)} \quad (22)$$

The calculation of $S_{sp}()$ is done with the cross-spectrum between $X_s(t)$ and $X_p(t)$. Improvements may be introduced by simply averaging between different tests: it is noted in fact that, despite some variability between tests due to some parametric changes (e.g. self heating of a component), $x_s(t)$ will follow anyway the new $x_p(t)$, providing consistent values of $H_{IT}()$, although the same cannot be said for the single terms S_{sp} and S_{pp} . The so determined $H_{IT}()$ then provides information on amplitude and phase and will be compared to the nominal k_r .

It is observed that the so-determined $H_{IT}()$ is a transfer function determined under an impulsive excitation, so that, depending on the amplitude excursion, linearity assumptions are stressed and may become invalid.

3.5.3 Set of test waveforms in WP2 and WP3

The set of waveforms discussed for the round robin test on the three CTs and three VTs is well representative of the approach above in sec. 3.5.1.

In a frequency domain perspective, the test waveforms set is composed of:

- F0: sine wave at 50 Hz with amplitude at 10 %, 20 %, 50 %, 80 %, 100 %, 120 % of the rated input;
- FH1: sine wave at 50 Hz 100 % amplitude + SH sine tone at frequencies 9, 10, 15, 20, 35, 50, 75, 100, 125, 150 kHz, zero phase, with amplitude equal to 2 % of the rated input at the fundamental;
- FH1N: variation of FH1 with different choices of frequencies and amplitude, and varying the phase relationship;
- FH1A: simple variation of FH1 where the SH amplitude is varied from the fixed 2 % from 1 % up to 10 % (if attainable, depending on the capability of the signal source);
- A simplified version of FH1, where all SH components are applied simultaneously; to avoid issues due to the limited capability of the signal source (the instantaneous SH amplitude value would be 10 %), the amplitude is reduced to 1 % for each component.

A sinc to be provided by UNIBO was included as an optional test (time domain transient signal as in sec. 3.5.2).

3.5.4 Test and Measurement Methods

Accurate measurement is as critical as accurate generation. The setups developed in the project employ high-resolution digitizers, broadband power analyzers, and reference devices such as zero-flux CTs and resistive-capacitive dividers. Coherent sampling techniques were implemented to avoid spectral leakage during Fourier analysis, and calibration procedures were applied to correct for gain and phase errors in both sensors and acquisition systems. These measures ensure that the uncertainty associated with the measurement chain remains well below the target accuracy limits.

4 Generation Architectures for VT Testing

One of the major achievements of the ADMIT project was the design and validation of advanced generation systems capable of producing composite waveforms with controlled spectral content. For voltage transformers, several architectures were explored, including parallel-connected generators, series-connected systems, and single-transformer setups with digital compensation. Each approach offers specific advantages in terms of complexity, scalability, and performance. For example, parallel generators allow independent control of low- and high-frequency components, while single-transformer systems simplify hardware requirements by relying on software-based compensation.

For current transformers, the challenge was to combine high power-frequency currents—up to 2 kA—with high-frequency components reaching 150 kHz. Solutions included dual-path configurations, where separate generators feed the fundamental and supraharmonic through the same CT window, and transient generators based on RLC discharge circuits for simulating oscillatory surges.

4.1 Parallel-Connected Generators for AC Voltage at LNE

4.1.1 Introduction

This section describes a parallel-connected generator architecture developed to supply composite AC test voltages for the characterization of voltage transformers. The system combines two independent sources: one dedicated to generating the fundamental power frequency (50/60 Hz), and another providing high-frequency components up to 150 kHz. Their outputs are connected in parallel and applied simultaneously to both a reference transformer and the device under test. By using this approach, it becomes possible to evaluate the accuracy, phase displacement, and frequency response of voltage transformers under realistic operating conditions, where both fundamental and harmonic components are present.

4.1.2 Set-up architecture

The generation architecture proposed consists of the parallel connection of a power frequency generator, operating at 50/60 Hz, and a high frequency components generator. Their outputs are summed to provide a composite signal that is applied simultaneously to a reference voltage transformer and the VT under test. The basic block diagram of this setup is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Block diagram of the proposed generation architecture and comparator-based VT characterization method.

This configuration implements a classical characterization method based [6-8] on the comparison of the outputs of a reference VT and a VT under test, using a comparator. The comparator, as well as the reference VT, must have sufficient accuracy over the entire frequency range of interest, from the nominal power frequency up to 150 kHz. By comparing the outputs, it is possible to determine the ratio error and phase displacement of the VT under test both at the fundamental frequency and in the presence of high-frequency components, thereby enabling the assessment of its frequency response and transient performance.

In practice, the Power Frequency Generator (PFG) is implemented by means of an Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG), followed by a low-voltage amplifier and a step-up transformer to achieve the required test voltage levels. The High-Frequency Generator is also realized using an Arbitrary Waveform Generator,

cascaded with a low-voltage amplifier, and provides output signals from DC up to 150 kHz. The complete measurement setup is illustrated in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Setup implementation of the proposed generation setup.

4.1.3 Setup implementation

The applied voltage signals are provided by a two-channels arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) Keysight 33612A (± 10 V output range, 660 MHz maximum sampling rate, and 64 million of samples per channel of onboard memory). The comparator is realized by a Data Acquisition System (DAQ) PicoScope 5244D MSO (16-bit resolution, 200 MHz bandwidth, ± 20 V maximum input voltage), which acquires the primary and secondary waveforms of the VT under test.

The output of the first channel of the AWG (AWG ch. 1) is connected to a voltage amplifier (± 120 V, ± 50 A, 6 kVA) feeding the VT under test at 50 Hz through a 100 V / 35 kV step up transformer with a power capacity of 5 kVA. Indeed, the transformer T1 and the associated low-frequency amplifier must be able to supply very high power levels because of the blocking elements. Since the blocking capacitors are in the nanofarad range, their impedance at 50 Hz is very low, and consequently a large amount of power is required to maintain the desired test voltage.

The ration of the transformer T1 has been measured. The results show that it exhibits only a very small sensitivity of about 0.3% in its transformation ratio when subjected to different capacitive loads (100 pF, 1 nF, and 2.5 nF) over the voltage range from 5 kV to 35 kV at 50 Hz. The ratio remains essentially stable and only weakly dependent on load conditions, with no need for correction when the load changes. However, the ratio increases from 332 at 5 kV to 340 at 35 kV, which indicates that a correction may be required to account for the voltage dependence if the 50 Hz voltage is to be assigned with high accuracy.

The output of the second AWG (AWG ch. 2) is connected to a power amplifier N4L LPA400 (± 400 V, 50 mA, DC – 1 MHz, selectable gain). The output impedance of the LPA400 amplifier was measured from 50 Hz to 150 kHz and remains essentially constant around 50 Ω . At 50 Hz, the voltage drop across this output impedance is minimal, ensuring that virtually the entire 50 Hz voltage appears across the blocking capacitor C2. Of course the rms current flowing through the LPA400, both the fundamental and harmonics, need to be less than its current capability, a current sensor has been installed in the output of the LPA400 to monitor it. The gain has been also measured from DC to 150 kHz allowing us to generate precisely the desired voltage of harmonics.

The device under test was represented by a RC divider (100 M Ω /100 pF) designed and implemented within a collaboration between LNE and University of Campania “L. Vanvitelli”; it has a scale factor of 50000:1, frequency response remains better than 0.1 % from DC up to 150 kHz, and voltage linearity better than 0.02 % from 5 kV to 35 kV. Such a divider has been placed in the DUT slot of the setup, and it was used to measure the output voltage generated by the whole setup (i.e., the combination of the outputs of the two generators). From this point on, this divider will be addressed as Universal Divider (UD).

Two other dividers have been used to measure 50 Hz and high-frequency voltages respectively, just at the output of the corresponding generators. Divider D1 is a commercial RC divider (300 M Ω /10 pF, ratio 1000:1,

accuracy 0.1% at 50 Hz and 1% at 150 kHz). Divider D2 is a commercial RC divider (100 M Ω /3 pF, ratio 1000:1, accuracy 0.1% at 50 Hz and 1% at 150 kHz).

Moreover, a full remote control of the setup has been implemented in LabVIEW environment. The realized software allows to choose generation parameters, to enable and disable the generation, and to monitor overvoltage and overcurrent situations.

4.1.4 Blocking elements

In this generation architecture, it is necessary to protect each generator from the voltage coming from the other generator. Therefore, two blocking filters have been designed and included. First, a resistor R1 and a capacitor C1 (rated at 50 kV too) are used to protect the step-up transformer from high-frequency current. C1 is a polypropylene film capacitor with voltage coefficient at 50 Hz < 0.2% and linearity error up to 150 kHz < 0.1%. These elements make up the blocking element n. 1 and create a low-pass effect with a cut-off frequency equal to $f_{\text{(cutoff,1)}} \cong 636$ Hz, ensuring that HF components are sufficiently attenuated on the transformer side. Moreover, it should be avoided that an amount of 50 Hz voltage drops across the resistor R1. Therefore, DUT impedance at 50 Hz should be much larger than R1 resistor by a factor of 10 allowing a voltage drop in R1 of only 10 %.

Additionally, a HV capacitor, C2 (rated at 50 kV), is placed on the high-frequency amplifier side. C2 is a ceramic capacitor (N4700 dielectric). Together with the output impedance R2 (50 Ω) of the amplifier itself, it makes up the blocking element n. 2 and creates a high-pass effect with a cut-off frequency equal to 1.5 MHz, ensuring that the 50 Hz component is almost totally removed. Moreover, as it was previously stated for blocking element n. 1, it should be avoided that an amount of high-frequency voltage drops across capacitor C2. As DUT is made up of resistors and capacitors parallel-connected, for high frequency DUT capacitors dominate. Therefore, for the case at hand, the influence of DUT resistive part is negligible in high frequency, and it can be stated that DUT capacitance should be much smaller than capacitor C2 by a factor of 10 allowing a voltage drop in C2 of only 10 %.

Obviously, if DUT is changed, it is necessary to rescale blocking elements as well taking into account the current and voltage capability of each generator. These current limitations are managed directly on the software. Blocking elements are not influenced by dividers D1 and D2. Divider D1 and D2 have a negligible effect on blocking element since their capacitance only a few pF.

4.1.5 Generator performance assessment based on waveform analysis

In this system, the generator is fully controlled via dedicated software, which plays a central role in configuring and shaping the signal before it is delivered to the DUT. The software allows the user to precisely define the voltage level, the number and type of harmonic tones, and the phase of each individual frequency component. The generator supports both single-tone and multi-tone operation. All signal parameters are initially defined in the frequency domain. This includes:

- The base frequency (typically 50 Hz),
- The list of harmonics to be included (9 kHz to 150 kHz)
- The amplitude of each harmonic component taking into account the gain of each amplifier
- And the relative phase of each harmonic with respect to the fundamental.

Once the spectral content is defined, the software performs an inverse Fourier synthesis to construct the corresponding time-domain waveform. This waveform is then sent to the amplifiers, which boosts the signal to the required voltage level. This approach ensures that the final signal reaching the DUT is a precisely constructed with an accuracy of about 1 % matching the specifications of the voltage with high fidelity.

The correct operation of the generator in this setup can be verified, in Figure 20, by observing the yellow waveform shown in the upper left section of the diagram. This waveform represents the output voltage at the generator's secondary, and it clearly demonstrates the superposition of a 50 Hz fundamental component with its harmonic content at 150 kHz. The presence of the smooth sinusoidal envelope confirms the dominance of the 50 Hz base frequency, while the higher-frequency oscillations riding on the sinusoid indicate that harmonic

components are being accurately generated and added. Importantly, the harmonic structure appears coherent and stable, without signs of distortion. This confirms that the generator is operating correctly, producing a signal that matches the intended spectral content and waveform shape. It also indicates that the amplifier and coupling system are not introducing significant non-linearity or filtering effects that would distort the signal before it reaches the DUT. In summary, the observed waveform validates that the 50 Hz excitation is being produced correctly and, the harmonics are superimposed in a stable and controlled manner, and the generator is delivering a clean, consistent signal suitable for testing the DUT under defined harmonic conditions.

Figure 20. Example of generation of one tone superimposed with the fundamental

The red waveform displayed in the upper right of the Figure 20 corresponds to the output voltage of the high-frequency amplifier, just before the signal is applied to the DUT. This signal is designed to contain primarily harmonic components while the fundamental 50 Hz component is expected to be suppressed by a filtering stage. However, visual inspection reveals a low-frequency modulation pattern superimposed on the high-frequency content. The observed red waveform confirms that the generator delivers the intended high-frequency excitation, with only a minor residual 50 Hz contribution. Since this residual does not lead to amplifier saturation or waveform distortion, it is considered acceptable and non-influential for the measurement scenario.

Figure 21, presents both time-domain and frequency-domain views of a high-voltage signal composed of a 50 Hz fundamental frequency and multiple harmonic tones. In the frequency domain, the central spectrum shows a strong fundamental component at 50 Hz with an amplitude of 96 dBm, confirming that the main excitation signal is correctly generated with very low noise. Superimposed on this are multiple harmonic tones, ranging from 10 kHz to 150 kHz, spaced every 10 kHz. These harmonics display a very consistent amplitude, generally between 43 dBm and 46 dBm, indicating good balance across the harmonic range. This small non-linearity observed in the harmonic amplitudes between 10 kHz and 150 kHz are primarily due to the intrinsic non-linearity of the arbitrary waveform generator used to synthesize the multitone signal. This non-linearity affects the precise voltage levels delivered at each harmonic frequency and result in slight deviations (in dB) across the spectrum. However, this behaviour is well characterized and could be fully correctable. Through software-based correction, the generator can apply pre-distortion algorithms or frequency-dependent compensation, allowing the user to achieve perfectly flat harmonic amplitudes — either equal across the frequency band (same dB level from 10 kHz to 150 kHz), or following any desired voltage profile.

Figure 21. Generation of multi-tones superimposed with the fundamental

The stability of the harmonic and fundamental components is further supported by the statistic calculations presented in Figure 21:

- The measure P1 is the measurement across the DUT (Figure 19)
- The measure P2 is the measurement across the divider D1 (Figure 19)
- The measure P3 is the measurement across the divider D2 (Figure 19)

The standard deviation values associated with each voltage measurement are extremely low, about 0.035 % at 50 Hz (Measure P1) and about 0.02 % for harmonics (Measure P3). This confirms that both the 50 Hz component and the harmonic tones remain stable over time as required for reproducible and reliable testing. Overall, the generator delivers a clean, well-defined multitoned signal, with both frequency and amplitude content tightly controlled. The combination of low standard deviation, coherent harmonic spacing, and clean time-domain waveform demonstrates that the signal is stable, precise, and suitable for high-voltage harmonic analysis and characterization. We can also see that the measured voltages at points P2 and P1 are 14.229 kV and 14.296 kV respectively, resulting in a very small difference of 67 V rms. This corresponds to a relative deviation of only 0.5%.

4.1.6 Interaction between both parallel generators

The aim of the conducted tests is to quantify how voltage generation is affected when both generators are active. To this end, test procedure involves three steps:

- Both generators are connected, but only the 50 Hz generator is active;
- Both generators are connected, but only the high-frequency generator is active;
- Both generators are connected and active.

In the following, the first two tests are indicated using the subscript “S”, whereas the third one is addressed by the subscript “FHF”. The amplitude of the fundamental component is chosen equal to 12 kV. The frequency of the high-frequency tone varies from 10 kHz to 150 kHz, while its amplitude is chosen as equal to 1 % of fundamental tone.

The ratio error $\epsilon(f)$ has been calculated comparing the amplitudes generated during the single-tone generation to the ones generated in the FHF test. Mathematically, the ratio error $\epsilon(f)$ is defined as in (1):

$$\epsilon(f) = \frac{V_{FHF}(f) - V_S(f)}{V_S(f)} \tag{1}$$

where:

- $V_{FHF}(f)$ is the measured voltage at frequency f under the FHF test;
- $V_S(f)$ is the measured voltage at frequency f under the S test.

As the only difference between the single-tone generation S test and the FHF test is the presence of both generators, the index $\varepsilon(f)$ estimates their mutual influence. In the following, experimental results are provided and discussed. Figure 22 provides the values of the errors $\varepsilon(f)$ associated to the generated high-frequency tones.

Figure 22. Impact of the simultaneous presence of both generators on the generated high-frequency tone vs. frequency

With regards to Figure 5, it can be observed that the mutual influence of the two generators is relatively low up to 50 kHz, because the error $\varepsilon(f)$ is less than 2 %. Up to 100 kHz, the error is below 3 %, whereas at 150 kHz it increases to 6 %. As the error curve has a negative polarity for all the frequencies, it means that, during FHF tests, HF tone amplitudes decrease due to the simultaneous presence of the other generator, with respect to S test. This behavior can be explained by the voltage dependence of capacitor C2, which uses an N4700 dielectric known for its poor stability under high voltage at 50 Hz. When the 50 Hz component is applied, the dielectric’s properties vary with voltage, leading to a non-linear response. This voltage dependence affects the behavior of the blocking element and can introduce unwanted variations in the signal. For applications involving high 50 Hz voltage, a capacitor made with a polypropylene dielectric would be more suitable, as it offers better linearity and lower voltage dependence.

With respect to the error at 50 Hz (Figure 23), it can be observed that it is much lower, and it is lower than ± 0.1 %. Moreover, the frequency of the high-frequency tone does not significantly influence the error at 50 Hz.

Figure 23. Impact of the simultaneous presence of both generators on the generated 50 Hz tone vs. frequency

Therefore, it can be concluded that the biggest influence is from the 50 Hz generator to the high-frequency one, whereas the 50 Hz generation is little affected by the mutual presence of both generators.

4.1.7 Influence of the blocking elements

This section provides some results to evaluate the effect of the blocking elements.

The residual high-frequency voltage measured by D1 has been compared to the full voltage measured by UD. Mathematically, it was calculated as in (2):

$$res_{HF}(f) = \frac{V_{D1}(f)}{V_{UD}(f)} \quad (2)$$

Figure 24 provides the values of $res_{HF}(f)$ vs. the frequency of the generated high-frequency tone. It can be observed that the residual $res_{HF}(f)$ decreases with frequency, because the higher the frequency, the farther you are from cutoff frequency.

On the other side, the residual 50 Hz voltage $res_{(50\text{ Hz})}$ measured by D2 has been compared to the full voltage measured by UD. Mathematically, it was calculated as in (3):

$$res_{50\text{ Hz}} = \frac{V_{D2}(50\text{ Hz})}{V_{UD}(50\text{ Hz})} \quad (3)$$

Figure 25 provides the values of $res_{(50\text{ Hz})}(f)$ vs. the frequency of the generated high-frequency tone. The cut-off frequency of the blocking element n. 2 is high enough to avoid significant 50 Hz voltage to be present at the input of the high-frequency amplifier. It can be observed that the residual 50 Hz voltage which falls across the high-frequency generator output is less than 0.002 % of the generated 50 Hz voltage. That ensures safety for the high-frequency amplifier and avoids that the 50 Hz current coming from the 50 Hz side and flowing into high-frequency amplifier is too high.

Figure 24. Percentage of high-frequency voltage measured by D1 compared to full high-frequency voltage measured by UD vs. frequency

Figure 25. Percentage of 50 Hz voltage measured by D2 compared to full 50 Hz voltage measured by UD vs. frequency

4.1.8 Conclusion

This chapter presents a generation system for the characterization of voltage transformers, for Medium Voltage grids, in the frequency range from power frequency (50/60 Hz) and for harmonics in the range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. The proposed generation system is based on the separate generation of the 50 Hz fundamental tone and the high-frequency components. The two generators are grounded and parallel-connected to obtain the composed voltage waveform. Two blocking elements have been added to the setup to prevent 50 Hz current from flowing into the high-frequency generator, and vice versa. The generator configuration presented in this system offers a flexible and practical solution for injecting combined 50 Hz and high-frequency signals into various types of DUT such as voltage transformers. Its modular design makes it easy to install in different environments, including industrial test benches or laboratory setups.

The use of adjustable blocking elements allows the system to be adapted to a wide range of DUTs with varying electrical characteristics. By tuning the values of the blocking element the system can optimize the coupling between low-frequency and high-frequency sources while maintaining electrical isolation and protecting the amplifiers. The required signal levels can be achieved using different types of amplifiers, depending on the application. Furthermore, the entire system can be integrated with a remote control interface, which facilitates automated test procedures. This feature is especially valuable for routine testing in industrial environments, enabling operators to perform tests more safely, efficiently, and with repeatable results.

This generator architecture is also highly scalable and adaptable. It can be extended to operate at frequencies up to 500 kHz, simply by selecting appropriate high-frequency amplifiers and adapting the blocking elements accordingly. In addition to sinusoidal excitations, the system can also be used to superimpose other types of signals, such as impulses, transients, or damped oscillatory waveforms, making it suitable for a wide range of test applications.

4.2 Series connected generators for AC Voltage at UniCampania

4.2.1 Introduction

This section introduces a novel generation and measurement setup developed at the University of Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli” for the frequency characterization of voltage transformers. The system is based on the independent generation of the fundamental power-frequency component, obtained through an Arbitrary Waveform Generator, a low-frequency amplifier, and a step-up transformer, and of the high-frequency components, produced by a second generator and a high-frequency amplifier. By connecting these sources in series, the setup enables the creation of distorted test waveforms composed of a rated 50 Hz voltage with superimposed harmonic tones in the range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. Dedicated reference devices and a high-resolution acquisition system ensure accurate measurement of both the power-frequency and harmonic components. This flexible configuration provides a practical solution for reproducing realistic distorted signals at medium-voltage levels, supporting advanced studies on the accuracy and frequency response of voltage transformers.

4.2.2 Design and development

In Figure 26a, the general block scheme of the proposed novel setup is presented, whereas a picture is shown in Figure 26b. The setup has been realized at University of Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli” and used in a temperature-controlled room. The most commonly used test waveforms for the VT frequency characterization are composed of fundamental tone at the rated frequency and amplitude and one or more superimposed tones at different frequencies and with reduced amplitudes. The proposed solution involves the independent generation of the fundamental tone and of the high frequency components to produce the desired distorted test waveform.

According to a commonly used practice in calibration laboratories (but also at NMI level), the generation of fundamental frequency components up to hundreds of kilovolt can be obtained by means of Step-Up voltage Transformers (SUT). Similarly, the proposed architecture generates the fundamental component using an Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG1), a low-voltage and Low-Frequency Amplifier (LFA), and a SUT. Due to its intrinsic galvanic insulation, this method allows for the generation of a voltage waveform with respect to a desired reference potential. It is important to underline that the desired reference potential should not necessarily be the earth potential or the reference potential of the rest of the circuit, thanks to the galvanic insulation of the SUT. Therefore, the secondary winding of the SUT can be easily series connected with another generation system as well depicted in Figure 26c.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 26. Basic block scheme (a), picture (b) and circuit diagram (c) of the proposed generation and measurement setup arranged at University of Campania

Considering that the frequency components have an amplitude lower than fundamental components, up to 3%, they can be generated using AWG2 coupled with a high-frequency amplifier (HFA). Thus, the distorted test waveforms can be obtained by simply using the SUT and HFA connected in series to superimpose the frequency components in the range [9, 150] kHz to the MV component at 50 Hz.

As regards the measurement section, two different reference transducers are used, one (LFRD, Low Frequency Reference Device, calibrated at INRIM) for the measurement of the power frequency component at MV level and the other (HFRD, High Frequency Reference Device) for the measurement of the high frequency components, characterised by amplitudes in the range up to hundreds of volt. It is worth noting that one of the main goals of the ADMIT project is the design, the realization and the characterization of reference sensors operating in the frequency range [9, 150] kHz and capable to work at MV amplitude levels.

As regard the acquisition section, the comparator is realized by using a Data Acquisition (DAQ) module that acquires the outputs of the device under test, of LFRD and of HFRD. Gain and offset of the adopted DAQ have been determined at INRIM. The DAQ module is installed in a PXI chassis along with the AWGs; the 10 MHz PXI clock is used as a reference clock for the AWGs Phase Locked Loop (PLL) circuitry. The time base of AWG1 provides also the sampling clock for the digitizer; this allows obtaining coherent sampling, thus avoiding spectral leakage.

Moreover, in Figure 26c, the impedances Z_1 , Z_2 and Z_3 (green colour) are the input impedance of DAQ channels. Moreover, if the DUT output voltage is too high to directly be acquired by the DAQ (as in the case of inductive VTs), a Low Voltage Divider (LVD) is used (see Figure 26a). This divider can be characterized by NMIs at voltage levels in the range of hundreds of volt up to 150 kHz.

The main specifications of the various devices used to implement the described setup are summarized in Table 4-1.

Table 4-1. Main specifications of the setup components

NAME	MAIN FEATURES
AWGs	National Instruments (NI) PCI eXtension for Instrumentation (PXI) 5422, 16-bit, variable output gain, ± 12 V output range, 200 MHz maximum sampling rate, and 256 MB of onboard memory.
LFA	Voltage amplifier, ± 75 V, ± 20 A, 1 kW, DC – 100 kHz
SUT	Step-Up Voltage Transformers, 100 V / 24 kV
HFA	Voltage amplifier, ± 150 V, 200 VA, DC – 500 kHz.
DAQ	Data acquisition module NI PXIe-6124, ± 10 V, 16 bit, maximum sampling rate of 4 MHz, input resistance > 100 G Ω with parallel 10 pF.
LFRD	Commercial resistive-capacitive divider, 10 / 10 kV/V, uncertainty of 0.01% and 100 μ rad @ 50 Hz (level of confidence 95 %)
LVD	Commercial resistive divider, 18.5 V/V, uncertainty of 0.01% and 100 μ rad @ 50 Hz (level of confidence 95 %)

The series connection of the two generators presents some issues that must be addressed in order to make this architecture suitable for the scope at hand.

First of all, according to the equivalent circuit of a voltage, the equivalent impedance $\dot{Z}_s(f)$ of the secondary winding, in the frequency range [9, 150] kHz, is mainly inductive and increases with frequency. Therefore, in the frequency range [9, 150] kHz the equivalent circuit (shown in Figure 27) of the measurement setup is constituted by the HFA and its load, that is the series connection of $\dot{Z}_s(f)$ and $\dot{Z}_m(f)$, that, in turns, is the equivalent impedance resulting from the parallel of the input impedances of DUT, LFRD and HFRD.

Figure 27. Equivalent circuit of the setup in the range from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz.

Figure 28. Equivalent circuit of the setup at the primary side of SUT

Looking at the Figure 27, it can be seen that the output voltage of HFA is divided among $\dot{Z}_s(f)$ and $\dot{Z}_m(f)$. The voltage drop across $\dot{Z}_s(f)$, that is undesired, increases with frequency, making thus the portion of voltage across $\dot{Z}_m(f)$ smaller and smaller. To avoid this issue, it is possible to add a capacitor C_s in parallel to the secondary winding of SUT in order to drastically reduce the voltage drop across $\dot{Z}_s(f)$.

However, the insertion of C_s at the SUT output increases the load of LFA. In fact, the equivalent impedance $\dot{Z}_s(f)$ (including now C_s), transferred at the primary side of SUT, must be sufficiently high, at 50 Hz, to stay within the current limit of LFA (LFA generates voltage and current at 50 Hz). Since the rated transformation ratio of SUT is $k = \frac{N_p}{N_s}$, where N_p (N_s) is the number of turns at primary (secondary) winding, the load impedance of LFA is $\dot{Z}_p(50) = k^2 \dot{Z}_s(50)$. In the case of SUT, N_s is higher than N_p and then k is lower than 1. Therefore, the magnitude Z_p of \dot{Z}_p is lower than Z_s . To calculate the maximum value of C_s , the current of primary winding

of SUT must be considered. For sake of clarity, Figure 28 shows the circuit for the calculation of $C_{s,max}$. The current I_1 is the maximum LFA output current, which divides in I_2 and I_z , which are, respectively, the current that flows in the primary winding of SUT and the current that flows in Z_p . I_2 depends on the load of the SUT. However, generally, the load impedance of SUT is high; therefore, the I_2 can be assumed to be the magnetizing current of SUT. Therefore, the maximum value of C_s is calculated by the following equation:

$$C_{s,max} = \frac{I_z}{2\pi f_1 V_1} \quad (4)$$

where V_1 and f_1 are, respectively, the maximum magnitude of the fundamental voltage phasor and its frequency and I_z is the difference between I_1 and I_2 . For the case at hand, $C_{s,max}$ is equal to 50 nF.

As regards the current limit of HFA, the magnitude of the equivalent series impedance of $Z_s(f)$ and $Z_m(f)$ must be sufficiently high to stay within the current limitation of HFA in the frequency range [9, 150] kHz. This condition generally holds, since the input impedance of the VTs designed for MV applications is generally high. However, it is worth noting that a check against the limitations of the HFA generator must be done before the execution of the tests.

4.2.3 Conclusion

In summary, the proposed setup provides a flexible and accurate way to generate distorted test waveforms by combining a fundamental 50 Hz component with controlled high-frequency tones. Its modular design, based on independent low- and high-frequency sources, ensures reliable medium-voltage testing and supports detailed characterization of voltage transformers across a wide frequency range.

4.3 Using a step up transformer for AC Voltage at INRIM

4.3.1 Introduction

The proposed generation architecture is simpler and more cost-effective compared to those presented in previous sections as it is tailored for industrial laboratories with standard equipment like Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG), wideband LV power amplifier, and commercial step-up transformer (SUT). Its key advantages are the use of a single voltage source for the generation of distorted waveforms with both power frequency and HF content and no need for a high-voltage capacitor. However, frequency-dependent performance, especially of the SUT, necessitates a compensation technique to ensure the correct high-frequency generation.

4.3.2 General voltage generator architecture and test procedure

Figure 29 shows the proposed voltage generation architecture, it includes an AWG, a wideband LV power amplifier and a SUT.

The objective is to supply the VT/LPVT under test and the reference device with MV test waveforms representative of the realistic ones. The considered actual waveforms consist of a multitone voltage signal composed by a fundamental component at the rated voltage V_0 and frequency f_0 and a number of superimposed tones, ranging from 1 up to a generic number N . Each of these tones has reduced amplitude $V_{HF,k}$ and higher frequency $f_{HF,k}$, as described in Equation 5:

$$v_G(t) = \sqrt{2}V_0 \sin(2\pi f_0 t) + \sqrt{2} \sum_{k=1}^N V_{HF,k} \sin(2\pi f_{HF,k} t) \quad (5)$$

Contrarily from the architectures presented in previous sections, where two different voltage generation sources have been used to generate the component at f_0 and those at f_{HF} , here the distorted waveform $v_G(t)$ is produced using a single-generation setup. The proposed architecture offers a significant cost advantage, as it requires only a single wideband amplifier and does not include a high-voltage capacitor.

However, a critical drawback of the generation architecture in Figure 29 is that the resulting distorted MV signal does not represent an amplified version of the target waveform.

Figure 29. General scheme of the proposed setup for VT characterization up to 150 kHz

This discrepancy mainly arises because SUTs are known to exhibit a non-flat frequency response over a wide frequency range since they experience filtering effects, frequency resonance and non-linearity phenomena. However, experiments under laboratory controlled temperature has evidenced that the non-linearity issue is significant only up to 1 kHz so considering the ADMIT [9-150] kHz target range, the generation system in Figure 29 can be considered composed of linear elements. Starting from this assumption, the non-ideal frequency behavior problem can be solved by first measuring the frequency response functions of the three elements of the generation section. Then, these measurement data can be used to produce a dataset of test waveforms according to equation (6), designed to compensate for distortions introduced by the elements of the generation system.

$$\bar{V}_{SYNT}(f) = \frac{\bar{V}_G(f)}{\bar{G}_{AWG}(f) \cdot \bar{G}_{AMP}(f) \cdot \bar{G}_{SUT}(f)} \quad (6)$$

where: $\bar{V}_{SYNT}(f)$ and $\bar{V}_G(f)$ are the spectra of the synthesized and generated test waveforms, respectively. $\bar{G}_{AWG}(f)$, $\bar{G}_{AMP}(f)$ and $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$, are the gain functions of the AWG, the power amplifier and the SUT. To summarize, the test procedure for using the generation setup in Fig. X involves three main steps:

1. measurement of the three compensation gain functions $\bar{G}_{AWG}(f)$, $\bar{G}_{AMP}(f)$ and $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$;
2. synthesis of the distorted test waveforms dataset to be generated according to equation (6);
3. generation of the MV test waveforms for the characterization of the VT/LPVT under test.

However, some papers have evidenced that the frequency performance of inductive VTs can be significantly affected by influence quantities such as operating temperature and burden conditions. Therefore, it can be necessary to include the monitoring of these parameters in the definition of $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$ and, subsequently, of $\bar{V}_{SYNT}(f)$.

4.3.3 Experimental setup arranged

The setup arranged at INRIM and used for the experimental activity to demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed approach is shown in Figure 30. It consists of three sections: generation, measurement, and a software section for digital waveform synthesis, remote control of the instrumentation, and data analysis. The generated voltage is measured by means of a Resistive-Capacitive Voltage Divider (RCVD). In particular, two different RCVDs were tested. The first, indicated as RCVD_A is air insulated, designed for DC and AC (50/60 Hz) applications, it has a rated primary voltage of 3 kV, a rated scale factor (SF) equal to 1000 V/V and

accuracy class of 0.2 %. The second RCVD (RCVD_B) is gas insulated and it designed for PQ applications, it has ± 45 kV rated primary voltage, a SF of 10000 V/V, a declared bandwidth from DC to 1 MHz and 0.2 accuracy class at 50/60 Hz. The two RCVDs have been characterized with a sinusoidal frequency sweep (SFS) in the range [10, 150] kHz at reduced amplitudes using a Fluke 5730 A calibrator. As can be observed in Figure 31, RCVD_A SF variation is within 0.2 % whereas for RCVD_B it is within 0.5 %.

Figure 30. Block scheme of the generation and measurement setup arranged at INRiM. The figure also provides an example of a synthesized waveform (a) alongside the corresponding generated MV waveform (b).

Table 4-2. Step up VT specifications

Rated input voltage (kV)	Turns ratio	Accuracy Class	Rated Burden (VA)
100/√3	200	0.5	30

As the acquisition system, a NI 9223 board has been used (± 10 V, 16 bit, 1 MHz sampling rate). When used in comparator mode, that is using two acquisition channels, the frequency response in the range [10, 150] kHz is flat within ±70 μV/V

The signal acquisition and the voltage generation were managed by LabVIEW program, whereas the post processing was performed in MATLAB environment.

Figure 31. General scheme of the proposed setup for VT characterization up to 150 kHz

4.3.4 Performance of the proposed setup in HF tone generation

The first experimental activity aims to assess the performance of the developed generation system and demonstrate its ability to produce distorted waveforms with spectral content up to 150 kHz. The tests are carried out under controlled laboratory temperature conditions ($23\text{ C} \pm 1\text{ C}$). The evaluation procedure consists of two main steps:

1. identifying the compensation functions for the three elements of the generation chain, and
2. verifying the system's performance after applying the compensation.

4.3.5 Identification of the compensation functions

Starting with the identification step, the frequency functions $\bar{G}_{AWG}(f)$, $\bar{G}_{AMP}(f)$ and $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$ are measured by performing a sinusoidal frequency sweep (SFS) in the range [10, 150] kHz.

More in detail, for the AWG, its frequency response is measured by programming it to generate a virtually pure sinewave at 1 V and varying the frequency within the range of 10 kHz to 150 kHz. The produced voltages are measured and the module of $\bar{G}_{AWG}(f)$ is computed as the ratio between the output voltage of the AWG and the expected reference voltage of 1 V.

For the measurement of the power amplifier compensation function $\bar{G}_{AMP}(f)$, it is set to have a rated amplification gain of 100 V/V; it is supplied with a SFS at 70 mV using the Fluke 5730 A calibrator. The $\bar{G}_{AMP}(f)$ function is then computed using the input and output voltages acquired by the NI 9223 board. The approach used for the power amplifier characterization is also applied to the identification of the SUT compensation function. It involves supplying the SUT with a SFS at rated voltage ($100/\sqrt{3}\text{ V}$) and measuring both the input and output voltages. In this case, RCVD_B is connected to the SUT to account for the burden effect while simultaneously scaling down the SUT output voltage to ensure compatibility with the input range of the acquisition system. The characterization results for SUT are presented in Figure 32 in terms of $\bar{G}_{AMP}(f)$ module. As can be observed, several resonances occur over the investigated frequency range. The SUT gain module is always lower than the rated value (200 V/V) and it varies from a maximum of 42.6 V/V at 14.85 kHz to a minimum of 0.24 V/V at 104 kHz.

Figure 32. General scheme of the proposed setup for VT characterization up to 150 kHz

4.3.6 Verification of the generation system performance

For the evaluation of the generation system performance, an appropriately distorted test waveform is digitally synthesized. The chosen test signal consists of a fundamental tone with one superimposed HF component, referred to as the FHF1 test. The fundamental tone is set to 3 kV at 50 Hz, while the amplitude of the HF component is adjusted to be 1 % of the fundamental tone within the range of 10 kHz - 150 kHz. The adjustment is made according to Equation (6) by considering the frequency gains measured during the identification step described in Section 4.3.1. The distorted MV waveforms are then generated, and a 5-second acquisition is performed. Post-processing analysis involves applying a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) over 10 cycles of the fundamental tone.

To quantify the performance of the generation setup, the index in Equation 7 is used:

$$\varepsilon(f) = 1 - \frac{|\overline{SF_{RCVD_B}}(f) \cdot \bar{V}_{HF,meas}(f)|}{|\bar{V}_{HF,desired}(f)|} \quad (7)$$

where $\overline{SF_{RCVD_B}}(f)$ is the SF frequency function of the reference RCVD_B; $\bar{V}_{HF,meas}(f)$ and $\bar{V}_{HF,desired}(f)$ are the root mean square (rms) values of the measured and desired HF components, respectively.

The index defined in (7) quantifies the deviation between the generated HF voltage and the target value, providing an appropriate metric to assess the error introduced by the proposed generation system.

For the setup described in previous section, results in terms of $\varepsilon(f)$ are provided in Figure 33.

Figure 33. Errors $\varepsilon(f)$ associated with HF tones measured when the generation system is used to generate a FHF1 voltages.

As can be observed, over the entire investigated frequency range the error goes from 0.06 % to 0.56 %. In general, it never exceeds 1 % which can be considered a satisfactory threshold.

4.3.7 Impact of influence quantities on the SUT

This section presents the analysis and experimental activity conducted to assess the impact of external factors on the performance of the proposed generation approach.

In particular, it is investigate on the effect of temperature variation and burden condition on the $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$ used to design the compensation function.

4.3.8 Temperature

To assess the impact of temperature variation on the SUT frequency gain, the SUT is placed inside a climatic chamber (100x100x120 cm³, from -80 °C to +180 °C) whereas the rest of the generation and measurement system is kept at constant ambient temperature.

Tests are performed at three different temperatures: 20 °C, 25 °C and 30 °C. The tested SUT has a thermal class of -5/40; however, its performances are investigated in a narrower temperature range, reflecting the possible realistic fluctuations occurring throughout the year in a test laboratory without temperature control.

The SUT is supplied with a sinusoidal waveform at rated voltage and with frequency from 10 kHz and 150 kHz. The output voltage is acquired with the RCVD_B connected to the SUT.

To quantify how the variability of $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$ due to the temperature impacts on the performance of the proposed system a specific analysis is performed. First, $\bar{V}_{SYNT}(f)$ is synthesized using the $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$ compensation function measured at the reference temperature of 25 °C. The system is then cooled/warm up, reaching the steady-state temperatures of 20 °C/30 °C. At this stage, the verification step, is carried out and the measured indices $\varepsilon(f)$ are summarized in Table 4-3.

As first comment, it can be observed that the results for the two cases differ in sign indicating that at 20 °C, the module of $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$ is higher than the one measured at 25 °C, whereas at 30 °C, it is lower than at 25 °C. The errors due to thermal variations are significant, with the most critical case observed at 30 °C, where the error $\varepsilon(f)$ is one order of magnitude higher than the error observed in the analysis conducted at a constant temperature (Figure 33). These results suggest that, to keep low the uncertainty associated with HF tones generated by the proposed system, it is necessary to monitor the temperature during the test session. If

significant temperature variations occur between the identification step and the testing phase on the VT under test, the appropriate gain curves of the SUT should be measured and used to synthesize $\bar{V}_{\text{SYNT}}(f)$.

Table 4-3. Impact of SUT operating temperature on $\varepsilon(f)$

Temperature (°C)	Frequency (kHz)			
	10	50	80	100
20	-3.0 %	-2.3 %	-2.4 %	-2.2 %
30	6.8 %	7.8 %	7.2 %	7.3 %

4.3.9 Burden

To evaluate how burden affects the frequency gain of the SUT, SFS tests with both RCVD_A and RCVD_B used as load are performed. From the burden point of view and considering the investigated range, the most significant difference between the two devices is the input capacitance C_{in} . For RCVD_A the input capacitance is equal to 780 pF whereas for RCVD_B is two orders of magnitude lower, that is 8 pF.

Table 4-4 provides the SUT module gains measured when it is used to supply the two different RCVDs.

The module of $\bar{G}_{\text{SUT}}(f)$ measured under the two different burdens conditions show a remarkable difference: with RCVD_A, the module of the $\bar{G}_{\text{SUT}}(f)$ is approximately five times lower than with RCVD_B over the entire investigated frequency range. Therefore, as expected, the identification step should be performed with the device under test (DUT) and the reference VT already connected to the circuit in order to account for burden effect.

Table 4-4: Impact of burden on the module of $\bar{G}_{\text{SUT}}(f)$

Frequency (kHz)	10	50	80
$ \bar{G}_{\text{SUT}}(f) $ with RCVD _A (V/V)	0.72	0.21	0.08
$ \bar{G}_{\text{SUT}}(f) $ with RCVD _B (V/V)	3.52	1.27	0.44
Frequency (kHz)	100	130	150
$ \bar{G}_{\text{SUT}}(f) $ with RCVD _A (V/V)	0.05	0.05	0.09
$ \bar{G}_{\text{SUT}}(f) $ with RCVD _B (V/V)	0.29	0.30	0.47

4.3.10 Conclusions

From the analysis of the results shown in previous sections, some general considerations are here provided. The experimental activity performed on the setup shown in Figure 29, indicates that, after the appropriate compensation function is measured and implemented, the generation system produces frequency tones with associated errors lower than 0.56 % over the frequency range going from 10 kHz to 150 kHz. However, this level of performance can be significantly influenced by variations in external factors, specifically temperature and burden conditions. In particular, it was found that temperature strongly impacts on the performance of the generation system. For instance, in case of temperature variation of the SUT from 25 °C to 30 °C, the error associated with the HF tone can increase of one order of magnitude, going from a maximum of 0.56 % to ~8 %.

Regarding the burden effect on the system, it was evidenced that varying burden lead to significant variations of the module of $\overline{G}_{SUT}(f)$ of some order of magnitude.

The analysis on the effects of temperature and burden revealed that the test procedure for using the proposed generation setup should include two important steps:

- the measurement of the generation system frequency gains with the circuit set up in the final test configuration to accurately account for the real burden;
- the tracking of temperature during long-duration tests in uncontrolled environments to evaluate if it is necessary to repeat the identification step to measure the proper $\overline{G}_{SUT}(f)$ function.

4.4 Series connected Generators for DC Voltage at FFII

4.4.1 Introduction

This section presents the development of a generation system capable of superimposing high-frequency AC components onto a high-voltage DC signal. The concept relies on connecting a regulated HVDC source in series with a high-frequency voltage transformer, driven by an arbitrary waveform generator and a broadband amplifier. This configuration enables the production of distorted test waveforms, where a stable DC level is combined with controlled supraharmonic tones in the range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. The setup was conceived to evaluate the interaction between DC and AC sources, verify insulation strategies, and provide a flexible tool for testing instrument transformers under combined DC and supraharmonic conditions.

4.4.2 Tests of two series generators arranged at FFII

The series-generator, Figure 34, setup consisted of two main subsystems connected in series: (1) a high-voltage DC source, and (2) a high-frequency AC source with a step-up transformer. The conceptual schematic is illustrated in the following scheme for clarity:

Figure 34. Conceptual schematic of the two series generator.

1. High-Voltage DC Generator: A regulated HV DC supply capable of up to 50 kV output was used to generate the DC component. A HV filter/inductor was placed in series with the DC output to allow steady DC current flow while blocking AC (thus preventing the HF harmonics from feeding back into the DC supply). The DC source was ramped to the desired voltage during tests.
2. High-Frequency AC Source: To generate the supraharmonic components, a programmable arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) produced sinusoidal signals in the target frequency range (9 kHz up to 150 kHz for these tests). The AWG output was amplified by a broadband power amplifier (rated approximately 150–200 W over the frequency range of interest). The amplifier could output up to ~100–150 VAC into a load and was configured with no DC offset (pure AC output mode).
3. High-Frequency Voltage Transformer (HFVT): A step-up transformer was used to couple the amplifier's low-voltage AC output into the high-voltage circuit. The HFVT had a ferrite core and was designed to have a high turns ratio (for example, an initial prototype used ~10 primary turns to 25 secondary turns) to increase the voltage, with the secondary winding insulated for several tens of kV. The HFVT's secondary was connected in series with the HVDC circuit. Several HFVT configurations were tested over the course of Task A2.1.3 (modifying the turns ratio and core sizes) to improve the performance (as discussed later in results). To ensure proper insulation in the high-voltage section, the final design of the HFVT consisted of a series arrangement of two transformers:

- a. The first transformer, with a 5:5 ratio, featured high insulation in both wirings to properly insulate the AWG from the high voltage.
- b. The second transformer, with a 5:50 ratio, intended to step up the voltage from the power amplifier to the HVDC circuit. Its LV wiring had 5 turns of HV insulated cable, while its HV wiring had 50 turns of copper wire.

The reason behind this transformer configuration was primarily to ensure sufficient insulation between the high-voltage (HV) and low-voltage (LV) windings. Since the system needed to withstand up to 50 kV DC, it was essential that one winding be constructed using HV cable. However, placing the HV cable on the high-voltage side would have significantly degraded the transformer's frequency response, due to the considerable distance between the winding and the core in every turn. Therefore, the HV cable was implemented on the low voltage winding instead, preserving a better frequency response while still providing the required insulation. To further enhance dielectric isolation, an additional HV transformer was connected in series with the primary transformer, resulting in a cascaded arrangement that increased overall safety and voltage-withstand capability. Figure 35 shows an image of this arrangement.

Figure 35. High Frequency Voltage Transformer.

4. Load and Measurement: The output of the combined system (the junction of the HV DC source, HFVT secondary, and coupling capacitor) was applied to a load representative of an instrument transformer's impedance. This was largely capacitive, dominated by the input capacitance of the measuring equipment itself – specifically, a high-voltage divider used to measure the output waveform had approximately 1 nF capacitance. Thus ~1 nF served as the test load in these verifications. The HV divider (1000:1 ratio) was connected to an oscilloscope to record both the DC level and the AC waveform simultaneously. The series combination of the HV supply, HFVT, and load completed the circuit, with the ground reference at the low side of the HV divider and the return of the HV supply.

4.5 Transient voltage generator at FFII

4.5.1 Introduction

This section presents the design and characterization of a Transient Voltage Generator developed to reproduce damped sinusoidal waveforms in the frequency range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz with peak amplitudes up to 3 kV. The generator is intended to emulate realistic high-frequency overvoltages occurring in medium-

voltage networks, thereby enabling the testing of instrument transformers under conditions that go beyond the 50/60 Hz fundamental. The system is based on a resonant RLC discharge circuit, where a capacitor is charged to a defined voltage and then discharged through an inductive network via a fast semiconductor switch. By selecting appropriate capacitor and inductor values, the oscillation frequency can be tuned to the desired range. Coupled with high-frequency step-up transformers, this approach provides a flexible source of controlled, reproducible transient voltages for calibration and research purposes.

4.5.2 Test setup design

The transient generator was developed as a resonant RLC discharge circuit triggered by a high-speed switch. The core idea is to charge a capacitor to a set high voltage and then abruptly connect it to a resonant inductive network, producing a decaying sinusoidal voltage across the connected load.

The transient voltage generator follows a similar design philosophy to the DC voltage generator in terms of how it introduces high-frequency signals into the test circuit. Instead of utilizing an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) and broadband power amplifier to synthesize and inject the high-frequency component, the transient generator replaces these elements with the semiconductor-triggered RLC discharge circuit. The output of this RLC Generator, capable of producing controlled, damped sinusoidal transients, is then directly connected to the high-voltage, high-frequency transformer. Figure 36 shows the conceptual schematic of the transient voltage generator.

The main generator is composed of the following components:

- Capacitor Bank: Selected to tune the oscillation frequency in combination with the circuit inductance. Various capacitance values (from tens of nF up to a few μF) were selected to target specific frequencies, e.g. using $\sim 0.25 \mu\text{F}$ for $\sim 95 \text{ kHz}$, $15 \mu\text{F}$ for $\sim 9 \text{ kHz}$.
- Inductances: A combination of dedicated inductors and the leakage inductance of the step-up transformer formed the resonant inductive element. Initial tests used $\sim 11 \mu\text{H}$ inductance yielding $\sim 90 \text{ kHz}$ oscillations with $\sim 0.255 \mu\text{F}$ capacitance. For lower frequencies, larger inductances or transformer windings were used, e.g. $\sim 35 \mu\text{H}$ for $\sim 20 \text{ kHz}$ range.
- Switching Device: A high-voltage MOSFET transistor was used to switch and connect the charged capacitor to the inductive circuit, discharging the capacitor into the resonant loop. The MOSFET provided controlled triggering of the transient and was tasked to withstand the peak current, tens to hundreds of amperes, during the discharge. The gate of the MOSFET was activated via a fiber optic trigger. The trigger pulses were generated using a function generator, allowing the triggering of the MOSFET to be synchronized with the zero-crossing or another selectable phase point of the 50 Hz voltage if necessary.
- HV Supply to charge the RLC circuit capacitors: A programmable DC source (Fluke 410B) was used for consistent charging up to $\sim 1.0\text{--}1.5 \text{ kV}$.
- High Frequency Voltage Transformer: The output of the resonant circuit was coupled to the measurement or test object through a transformer. This step was critical to achieve the desired 3 kV amplitude without exposing the MOSFET/capacitor to the full HV. Several transformer configurations were tested to cover the wide frequency span:
 - A 5:50 HFVT (high turns ratio $\sim 1:10$) was used for the lowest frequencies ($\sim 9\text{--}20 \text{ kHz}$) where a large voltage amplification was needed.
 - A tunable ratio HFVT was used for mid and high frequencies up to 150 kHz. This HFVT allowed for flexible winding configuration: the primary winding could be selected with either one or two turns depending on the experimental requirements, while the secondary—being a toroidal-type transformer—enabled manual adjustment of the number of turns. This made it possible to increase or decrease the transformation ratio as needed by simply adding or

removing turns from the secondary winding, which was especially useful for adapting the output to the required frequency range or voltage level.

- A high-voltage divider and high-speed oscilloscope were used to monitor the output waveform. The oscilloscope power supply was isolated from ground to prevent grounding issues.

Figure 36. Conceptual schematic of the Test Setup.

4.5.3 Test procedure

The test procedure consisted of the following steps until obtaining the full capability of generation for each frequency. All these tests were performed with an HVDC level of 25 kV.

1. Frequency Tuning: Small-signal tests were done to verify that the selected LC values produced the intended oscillation frequency. For example, with $L \approx 11 \mu\text{H}$ and $C \approx 0.255 \mu\text{F}$, the calculated frequency was 95 kHz, and the measured value was 88.5 kHz. Differences between the measured and calculated value are due to stray inductances and capacitance and the main capacitor tolerances. Similar checks were done for other capacitor values ($0.1 \mu\text{F}$ for ~ 150 kHz, etc.).
2. Incremental Voltage Tests: The capacitor charge voltage was gradually raised and transients triggered to observe the waveform and look for distortion or saturation. The current through the MOSFET switch was also being monitored, so that it would not go above the rated current value.
3. Full-Scale Shots: Finally, full-energy shots were conducted. The capacitor was charged to around 1.0–1.1 kV (and up to ~ 1.5 kV in some cases) and the MOSFET triggered to generate the transient. The output voltage and current were recorded across the frequency bands.

Figure 37 shows views of the test setup for each HFVT.

(a) (b)
Figure 37 View of the test setup. a) 5:50 ratio HFVT. b) Tunable ratio HFVT

4.6 Results

The voltage transient generator developed in this task successfully produced damped sinusoidal voltages across the target frequency spectrum. It achieved the 3 kV peak voltage goal at representative frequencies in the low, mid, and high ends of the range. Depending on the frequency range, the following conclusions were drawn:

- Low Band Frequency (9 - 18 kHz): Using the 5:50 HFVT and large capacitances, e.g. from 4 μF to 15 μF .
- Mid Band Frequency (20 - 60 kHz): Using the tunable ratio HFVT with a ratio from 1:8 to 1:11 and moderate capacitances, e.g. from 3 μF to 7.5 μF .
- High Band Frequency (60 - 150 kHz): Using the tunable ratio HFVT with a ratio of 1:4 and smaller capacitances, e.g. from 0.1 - 0.5 μF .

Table 4-5 shows the configuration parameters of the generator and the transient voltage results for each frequency and Figure 38 shows an example of a generated sinusoidal damped transient voltage.

Table 4-5. Generator parameters and test results.

Center frequency (kHz)	HFVT output ratio	LC circuit		Voltage transient V_{peak} (kV)	Current through the Mosfet I_{peak} (A)
		Inductance (μH)	Capacitance (μF)		
8.8	5:50	20	15	2.96	608
11.5	5:50	35	4.5	3.04	72.6
16.3	5:50	20	4	2.95	214
21.9	1:11	8	7.5	3.10	671
22.2	1:11	8	7.5	3.10	630
26.7	1:8	10	4	2.89	529
30.4	1:8	10	3	3.09	478
39.1	1:8	6	3	2.94	567
62.1	1:4	11	0.5	2.91	173

128.8	1:4	11	0.1	3.13	69
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Figure 38. Example of a sinusoidal damped transient voltage.

4.7 Conclusion

The developed transient voltage generator successfully produced damped sinusoidal transients across the entire target frequency band, achieving peak voltages of about 3 kV. Different transformer ratios and LC combinations were used to cover the low (9–18 kHz), mid (20–60 kHz), and high (60–150 kHz) frequency ranges, with stable operation and consistent waveform quality. The results confirm that the generator can reliably reproduce realistic supraharmonic transients, making it a suitable tool for evaluating medium-voltage instrument transformers under transient overvoltage conditions.

5 Generation Architectures for CT Testing

5.1 Two parallel separated current generation

This section presents three different solutions for generation and measurement systems by RISE, VSL and VTT for calibration of current sensors from 50 Hz to 1 kHz up to 2 kA and from 2 kHz to 150 kHz up to 100 A.

5.1.1 RISE system

At RISE an AC current generation system has been developed using two current sources suitable for calibration of window type measurement systems. One source generates 50 to 1 kHz up to 2 kA and the other source generates supraharmonics from 2 to 20 kHz up to 100 A and 20 A for frequencies up to 150 kHz. The device under test (DUT) is then connected to both sources.

5.1.2 Set-up

A Chroma 61605 is computer controlled in frequency and amplitude via a DA converter, e.g. NI USB 6216, which current is feeding a Nokia step-up transformer. The computer interface can either lock-in to the local power frequency or be run at 50 or 60 Hz with a general mixture of harmonics up to 2 kHz synchronized or free-running via an Agilent 33500B. A HITEC Zero-Flux core is used for measurement of the signals from the line frequency and harmonics thereof. The signal is sampled by one of the PXIe-6396 channels measuring the line frequency and harmonics current.

Figure 39: Schematic of the RISE set-up

The supraharmonics are generated from a computer-controlled Keysight 33500B driving a modified Clarke-Hess 8200 amplifier. In this manner a line frequency/phase and frequency independent current with single frequency or spectrum of supraharmonics is generated from 2 to 150 kHz. From a 100A DSWM current shunt type CS2D (RISE model) the voltage is sampled by one of the PXIe-6396 channels measuring the supraharmonic current. The computer program gives the fundamental and/or one or several harmonics feeding the Chroma 61605 generator and a mixture of supraharmonics to the Clarke Hess. The fundamental can be synchronized with the grid line frequency. The set-up is shown in Figure 39.

The components in Figure 39 and their functions are the following:

- Core controller - LabVIEW program “Follower”: This program generates signals for the testing and slowly ramps up and down the currents to avoid overvoltage from inductances or transients. The program also collects the signals from the three CTs via a PXIe-6396 digitizer.
- Digitizer PXIe-6396: The signals from the reference CTs, i.e. a HITEC 500/2000 or 6000A (peak current) measuring the line frequency and harmonics and a current shunt RISE CS2D measures the supraharmonics up to 100 A, are sampled by this digitizer. The digitizer has 8 channels simultaneously sampled, 18 bits resolution and a sampling rate up to 15 MS/s. Supraharmonics are sampled at least with a sampling rate = 2^n , larger than $5 \cdot 150$ kS/s (7 periods), which is $2^{20} = 1.05$ MS/s. This choice is for adaptation to the FFT analysis to avoid spectral leakage. The sampling length is dictated by the line frequency, i.e. a duration of at least 7 periods of 50Hz = 140 ms, rounded to 200 ms, about 200 kS.
- Arbitrary Waveform Generator (Agilent 33500B): Samples the power line frequency for generation of true voltage and harmonics via a computer controller (LabVIEW “follower”). The 33500B generates the waveshapes for supraharmonics and controls the output of the generator Clarke-Hess 8200.
- Arbitrary Waveform Generator (NI-USB 6216): Provides a wave shape output with programmable amplitude and frequency (50 Hz to 1 kHz). This signal can be synchronized to the line frequency and can contain harmonics with amplitude and relative phase.
- A Chroma type 61605 4 kVA generator is used to generate currents controlled by the NI-USB 6216 arbitrary wave form generator via an external input from 15 – 1000 Hz with 32A/20A (150V/300V) ranges. Using a step-up transformer 100:1 the maximum current is 3.2 kA.
- A modified transconductance amplifier Clarke-Hess 8200 is used for generation of supraharmonics up to 150 kHz. The amplifier can generate 100 A up to 20 kHz and 20 A up to 150 kHz, limited by the compliance voltage of 7V. The waveshape of the amplifier is controlled by the computer program via an Agilent 33500B.

5.1.3 Test of the generation system

The two generation systems are tested exciting the fundamental 50 Hz combined with an odd harmonic, e.g. 150 Hz, 250 Hz, ... using the Chroma 61605. This at the same time combined with supraharmonic frequencies excited with the Clarke-Hess 8200 close to 2 kHz, 5 kHz, 10 kHz and 20 kHz up to 100 A, and 50 kHz, 100 kHz and 150 kHz up to 20 A, while avoiding multiples of the fundamental frequency. The limiting factor for the currents above 20 kHz was the compliance voltage from the inductance in the loop where the Clarke-Hess 8200 can drive up to 7 V.

5.1.4 Results

The Current sensor Pearson 301X was used to test the system. This sensor can measure up to 400 A and is designed for impulse current measurements. A mixed signal of 50 and 150 Hz, with amplitudes up to 365 A @ 50 Hz and 35 A @ 150 Hz was generated with the Chroma 61605 + transformer and several supraharmonic signals around 20 A from 2 to 150 kHz were injected with the Clarke-Hess 8200. In Figure 2 the ratio error and phase error are plotted. The Pearson 301X is apparently not very good at lower frequencies which was expected from the impulse design. For the supraharmonics it behaves well and is within 0.08% for the ratio and within 3% phase error.

Figure 40 : Results for a Pearson 301X impulse current sensor.

5.1.5 Measurement uncertainties

The ref CT (HITEC Zero-Flux cores) have errors less than 50 ppm and 60 mrad at 50 Hz, and 200 ppm and 1 rad at 1 kHz. Using corrections the phase displacement can be reduced for the Zero-flux cores. The high frequency reference the current shunt RISE CS2D, has an uncertainty of less than 2 ppm for the amplitude from 50 Hz to 150 kHz, less than 2 μ rad at 50 Hz and up to 200 μ rad around 25 kHz for the phase using a linear correction. Calibration of amplitude error and phase shifts of both sensors and using corrections can be used to improve the performance.

The PXIe-6396 has a specified measurement uncertainty of <200 ppm for the amplitude. After calibration we expect this to be better than 100 ppm. The phase uncertainty depends on the sampling frequency and delays between the channels. The digitizer has a simultaneous sampling of all channels, so this reduces delay contributions to the phase uncertainty. The specified timing accuracy is 50 ppm of sample rate, which means the higher sampling rate the lower is this contribution. Further description of the measurement system and a detailed analysis of the measurement results will be published in a paper.

5.1.6 VSL system

At VSL an AC current generation system has been developed with the aim of generating 2 kA at the fundamental frequency and at least 20 A from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz. This generation system is meant to characterize window-type current transformers, where it can be used to feed the separate parallel power frequency and high frequency branches.

Current transformers can be characterized using bridge or comparator techniques, shunt-based methods, or comparison using sampling methods. In this report, the latter technique is envisaged, in which a high current is simultaneously fed through the primary windings of the CT under test and a reference CT, such that the

complex ratio of the secondary currents provides a direct indication for the complex ratio error of the CT under test (i.e., magnitude error as well as phase displacement). The secondary currents can be measured using step-down transformers, current buffers, and high-precision sampling voltmeters at high accuracy, or using a power analyser as a simplified method.

Figure 41 shows a schematic overview of the measurement setup for characterising the DUT and reference CT. A high-current source produces the required primary excitation current (I_p) at a single frequency ranging from 50 Hz to 150 kHz via two transformers connected in series. The power analyser's current channels (sampling ammeters) use internal coaxial shunts to monitor secondary currents. The setup's current generating circuit includes a compensation capacitor and inductor to prevent DC magnetisation of the CT cores and to provide series compensation for the circuit impedance.

Figure 41: Schematic representation of the measurement setup where a high-current source feeds both the DUT CT and the reference CT [2]. The secondary outputs are recorded using a power analyser for ratio comparison.

5.1.7 High-frequency generation system

The basic idea of the distorted high-current generation system is to generate the 50 Hz fundamental component with current magnitudes up to 2 kA and the high-frequency components separately, i.e., the fundamental component and the distortion are generated through two separate systems and carried through two separate conductors. The two conductors can be sensed simultaneously by the CTs when feeding them both through the primary winding of the CTs. The generation and measurement of the fundamental component has been well described in literature. Therefore, the focus of this report is on the generation of the high-frequency distortions.

To generate the required high-frequency distortions of 20 A in the frequency range of 50 Hz to 150 kHz, a high-bandwidth power amplifier system was constructed, as illustrated in Figure 42. This system is designed to maintain stable, safe, and accurate current injection into the primary circuit under varying frequency-dependent load conditions. Because of the DUT and reference CT system are simultaneously measured, a small deviation/drift of a couple of percent deviation from the ideal current is not an issue.

Figure 42 High-bandwidth power amplifier system for generation of currents up to 150 kHz.

The components shown in Figure 42 and their functions are as follows:

- Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG): Provides a sinusoidal voltage output with programmable amplitude and frequency (50 Hz to 150 kHz).
- Variable Potentiometer (POT): Allows gradual adjustment of the input voltage to the power amplifier. As the impedance of the primary circuit changes with frequency, the potentiometer is used to fine-tune the output and achieve the target 20 A current, as verified by the clamp meter. This allows for a gradual and safe ramp-up of the primary current.
- Amplifier (AMP): Converts the AWG voltage into a current signal. This broadband power amplifier (Hero-Power DCU 2250-10 FM 1295 by Rohrer Mess- & Systemtechnik) provides sufficient gain and power to overcome the inductive and capacitive reactance of the primary circuit at high frequencies.
- Inductor (L): Connected in parallel with the CTs to divert any DC components originating from the amplifier. This is to prevent core magnetisation in the CTs, which could lead to measurement errors.
- Compensation Capacitor (C): Placed in series with the CTs, this capacitor helps to block DC and further ensures that only AC current is present in the measurement circuit. It also helps with series compensation of the long cable connected that loops through the CTs.
- Current Clamp (Clamp): Provides a convenient means for real-time monitoring and adjustment of the primary current during ramp-up and operation. Accurate measurement of the primary current is done using the sampling ammeter, not the current clamp.

5.1.8 Testing of the generation system

To ensure standardized and consistent characterization, the generation system delivers a primary current up to 20 A to the CTs under test. The primary current is tested at a series of discrete frequencies: 50 Hz, 100 Hz, 200 Hz, 500 Hz, 1 kHz, 2 kHz, 5 kHz, 10 kHz, 20 kHz, 50 kHz, 75 kHz, 100 kHz, 125 kHz, and 150 kHz (a total of 14 points). These frequency points were selected to provide approximately three measurement samples per decade (with some extra points at higher frequencies, as this is most the most interesting). Magnitudes higher than 20 A were generated for frequencies up to 100 kHz. For higher frequencies, the power amplifier could no longer provide sufficient power. The highest magnitude obtained at 150 kHz was still 14 A, however. These currents were measured using a Yokogawa WT5000 broadband power analyser (with 1 MHz bandwidth).

The primary current generation system was further tested by measuring the primary and secondary currents of two similar NRC electronically compensated current transformers [53], with an accuracy of about 1 ppm at

50 Hz and a nominal turns ratio of 100:1. Figure 43 shows the measured ratio between the primary and secondary currents for the two CTs investigated in this study. The magnitude of the current applied was 10 A over the whole frequency range. The primary and secondary currents were measured using 30 A and 5 A input modules of the WT5000 with proper range selection, respectively.

Figure 43: Primary-to-secondary current ratios for the two CTs A and B. Deviations become more pronounced above 10 kHz.

The CTs use internal compensation electronics to ensure low errors (less than 20 ppm and 20 μ rad) up to 5 kHz. However, the internal amplifiers' bandwidth, in particular, restricts the effectiveness of correction beyond a few kilohertz; subtle differences in electronics between the two CTs could have an impact on high-frequency performance. This explains the differences between CT A and CT B observed in Figure 43. A further description of the measurement system and a detailed analysis of the measurement results, including an uncertainty budget, can be found in [5] and will be left for a separate report.

5.1.9 VTT system: Low-current multitone harmonics system

VTT system for generation and measurement of 50 Hz fundamental and harmonics is shown in Figure 44. A signal with up to 10 frequency components is created, and it is uploaded to the two-channel arbitrary waveform generator (AWG, Keysight 33500B). One channel of the AWG feeds the transconductance amplifier (Guildline 7620), and the other channel provides a synchronized trigger signal to the two-channel digitizer (Applicos WFD20). A wideband shunt is used as the reference for calibration of current sensors or shunts. The system is controlled by a PC. A typical recorded reference multitone signal and its FTT are shown in Figure 45.

As the sampling is coherent with the multitone reference signal, no windowing is needed, and each generated harmonic will fall in one FTT bin without spectral leakage.

Figure 45 shows an example of a recorded frequency response of a wideband current sensor (Pearson 110A) between 50 Hz and 150 Hz.

Figure 44: VTT multitone generation and measurement setup.

Figure 45: An example of a measured multitone waveform. Even though the signal level is low, the signal-to-noise ratio is c. 75 dB.

A wideband shunt is used as the reference for calibration of current sensors or shunts. The system is controlled by a PC. As the sampling is coherent with the multitone excitation signal, no windowing is needed for each generated harmonic to fall in one FFT bin without spectral leakage. Figure 45 shows an example of the measured multitone signal and its FFT.

5.1.10 VTT system: High-current low frequency system

This multitone current generation system can be used together with VTT high-current system for power frequency calibration. The high-current generator has a bandwidth up to 1 kHz, and it can generate up to 8 kA at 50 Hz. This system can be used together with the multitone system for calibration of supraharmonics of window type measurement systems. One source generates 50 Hz or 60 Hz up to 8 kA and the other source

generates supraharmonics from DC to 100 kHz up to 20 A and 2 A for frequencies up to 1 MHz. The device under test (DUT) is then connected to both sources.

5.2 Two parallel-grounded generators

5.2.1 Proposed generation architecture by UniCampania and INRIM

The proposed general generation architecture is shown in Figure 46. It is based on the use of two different current sources: one is dedicated to the generation of Low Frequency (LF) DC or AC 50/60 Hz current with high-amplitude ($i_{LF}(t)$) while the other source is used to generate low-amplitude currents with frequencies up to several hundreds of hertz ($i_{HF}(t)$). Two blocking elements are connected in series with the current generators when it is necessary to protect each generator from the current generated by the other one. Downstream of the filtering elements, the two currents are provided to the measurement branch which consists of the device under test (DUT) connected in series with the reference transducer (REF).

The scheme in Figure 46 is flexible and can be easily adopted in several cases and some of them are here recalled. Regarding the generation of the high amplitude currents $i_{LF}(t)$, two cases can be distinguished: DC currents and AC 50/60 Hz currents. For the DC case, high current levels can be obtained using a commercial generator, a transconductance amplifier or a generation system composed by a three-phase generator coupled with an autotransformer and a rectifier.

Figure 46: General scheme for the characterization of MV/HV current sensors under a current signal composed of high current at DC/power frequency with low amplitude and high frequency superimposed tones

For the AC 50/60 Hz high current generation, the common adopted solutions are power transformers, commercial amplifier, power generator coupled with step up current transformers (CTs).

For the generation of $i_{HF}(t)$ it is possible to use step up current transformers for MV application up to ~100 A suitably designed to have a flat frequency response within the desired band or a commercial transconductance amplifier.

Depending on the adopted solution, it can be necessary to appropriately design the blocking element. The input quantities in the design process are the current levels and their frequency content, the input impedances of the two current generators and the impedance value of the series connection of the device under test and the reference one.

5.2.2 Experimental setup and procedure

This Section introduces the experimental setup and the test procedure applied to assess the validity of the proposed architecture. The primary objective of the experimental activity presented here is to quantify the mutual impact between the two sources and the resulting current flowing into the measurement branch. In other words, the tests aim to evaluate how the presence of the LF generator affects the HF current in the measurement branch, and vice versa.

Starting from the general scheme presented, two cases are implemented:

- in the first case (case A), both $i_{LF}(t)$ and $i_{HF}(t)$ are generated using two transconductance amplifiers, each driven by an Arbitrary Waveforms Generator (AWG).
- in the second case (case B), the $i_{LF}(t)$ current is generated using a power amplifier coupled with a step-up CT whereas the $i_{HF}(t)$ is obtained by using a transconductance amplifier coupled with an AWG.

5.2.3 Generation and Measurement Setup

Considering Case A, the transconductance amplifiers used are one Clarke Hess 8100 and one Clarke Hess 8200. The two transconductances are driven by two Keysight 33500 B AWGs (± 10 V, 120 MHz, THD lower than $300 \mu V/V$). Despite the dual-channel capability of the AWG, two separate AWGs are used to mitigate potential errors stemming from crosstalk phenomena among the channels.

For Case B, the HF tones are generated using a Clarke Hess 8200 driven by a Keysight 33500 B. As for the LF fundamental component, two different step-up current transformers with different features have been used:

- CT1: for MV application, 5/75 A/A, series inductance L_s of $19 \mu H$.
- CT2: window type, 5/250 A/A, series inductance L_s of $0.5 \mu H$.

Both in Case A and Case B, the generated current flowing into the measurement branch is measured by the means of a reference shunt Fluke A40B (flat frequency response within tens of ppm up to 100 kHz) and a Fluke 8588 A multimeter used in digitizer mode with a sampling frequency of 2 MHz.

5.2.4 Test Procedure

As already mentioned, the main goal of the performed experimental activity is to quantify how each source affects the current in the measurement branch generated from the other source when they are both active. To this end, the test procedure involves three steps:

1. the sole generation of $i_{LF}(t)$,
2. the sole generation of $i_{HF}(t)$ and
3. the simultaneous generation of the two currents $i_{LF}(t)$ and $i_{HF}(t)$.

The first two steps are indicated in the follow using the subscript “S” whereas for the third step the subscript “FHF” is used indicating that the resulting current is composed by a fundamental tone plus a high frequency component.

Experimental results are presented as the errors $\varepsilon(f)$ associated with the current tone at frequency f , measured during the FHF test, compared to those measured during the single tone test S. Mathematically, the errors $\varepsilon(f)$ are defined according to Equation 1:

$$\varepsilon(f) = \frac{I_{FHF}(f) - I_S(f)}{I_n(f)} \quad (1)$$

where I_{FSH} and I_S are the RMS values of the current at frequency f measured under FHF and S test, respectively; I_n is the nominal RMS value of the current at frequency f . Since the only difference between the single-generation test S and the FHF test is the presence of both the generators, the index $\varepsilon(f)$ quantifies the

impact on the current tone at frequency f flowing into the measurement branch due to the presence of a second generator producing a current at different frequency and amplitude.

As regards the test points of the experimental activity here presented, the LF fundamental component is fixed at 50 Hz, whereas the HF tone frequency ranges from 10 kHz to 150 kHz with amplitude equal to 10 % of the LF tone.

5.2.5 Experimental results

In the following, the results of the two investigated configurations are discussed.

5.2.6 Connection of two transconductance amplifiers

Initially, steps 1 and 2 for exclusively generating one of the two currents are performed by setting the other generator in three different modes: 1) in standby and not connected to the circuit (galvanic insulation), 2) in standby but connected to the circuit (standby), 3) generating 0 A and connected to the circuit (operate 0 A). Considering the case of the solely generation of $i_{HF}(t)$, results related to these three configurations of the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator are provided in Figure 47. By the comparison of the curve obtained in standby mode and the one measured with galvanic insulation, it can be observed that deviations go from 170 μ A at 10 kHz to 1.5 mA at 150 kHz. Considering the case of the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator connected to the circuit and producing 0 A and the case of galvanic insulation of $i_{LF}(t)$ generator, higher deviations are observed with the increase of the frequency. Specifically, at 10 kHz deviation is lower than 200 μ A but it increases to 180 mA at 150 kHz.

Figure 47 $I_{HF}(f)$ values measured under three configurations of $i_{LF}(t)$ generator: connected to the circuit and generating 0 A (blue line circle maker), connected to the circuit but set in standby mode (red line square marker) and disconnected from the circuit (yellow line asterisk marker).

The main result of this experiment consists in the verification that the transconductance amplifier exhibits different impedances and behaviours, depending on its configuration. The results shown in the following refer to the case in which the single test S is conducted by galvanically isolating the other generator.

Figure 48 Errors $\epsilon(f)$ associated with HF tones measured when the iLF(t) generator is connected to the circuit and generating 40 A at 50 Hz, compared to the case when the iLF(t) generator is galvanically isolated.

Focusing on the comparison between FHF and S test, Figure 48 provides the values of the errors $\epsilon(f)$ associated to the HF tones whereas for the 50 Hz current, the maximum error $\epsilon(50 \text{ Hz})$ is 50 $\mu\text{A/A}$.

Looking at figure, it can be observed that the presence of iLF(t) generator has a low impact on the iHF(t) flowing into the measurement branch up to 50 kHz being the error $\epsilon(f)$ lower than 0.3 %. The 1 % threshold is reached at ~80 kHz whereas at 150 kHz the error increases to 4.50 %. As a general consideration, it can be observed that the error curve has a positive polarity for all the frequencies that, according to Equation 1, turns into higher values of HF currents in FHF test with respect to the HF current measured under single test S case.

To better investigate this phenomenon, the same test procedure is performed by selecting two different gains of the transconductance amplifier used to generate the 50 Hz iLF(t) current at 40 A: 10 S and 100 S. The comparison of the obtained results is provided in Table 1 where it can be observed that for 100 S gain case, error five times higher is measured at 150 kHz. The results of these experimental tests underscore that under the FHF test there is a coupling between the two generators that leads the LF generator to capture, amplify and generate HF components too.

However, between the two cases 10 S and 100 S, an increase in error by a factor of 10 is not observed even if the gain increases ten times because the change in the transconductance gain also results in a modification of its output impedance.

In summary, the generation setup composed by two transconductance amplifiers poses no significant issues for the generation of the iLF(t) at 50 Hz with superimposed HF tones up to 80 kHz, with errors lower than 1 %. However, when frequencies increase from 80 kHz to 150 kHz, the coupling between the generators leads to a rise in the error $\epsilon(f)$ of up to 4.5 %.

Table 5-1 Impact of the gain of the transconductance used to generate 50 Hz current on the HF tones

Frequency (kHz)	ε (%)	
	10 S	100 S
10	0.000	-0.042
20	0.042	0.022
50	0.278	0.493
100	1.347	3.053
125	2.468	7.130
150	4.496	21.141

5.2.7 Connection of a step-up current transformer and a transconductance amplifier

As said in previous section, this configuration is setup with two different CTs. For both, experimental results are presented in Figure 49 for the HF tones; instead, errors lower than 500 $\mu\text{A/A}$ are measured at 50 Hz. As it can be observed, the different specifications of the two CTs result in errors $\varepsilon(f)$ that differ significantly, by an order of magnitude. For CT1 $\varepsilon(f)$ is always lower than -1 % whereas for CT2 goes from -9.7 % at 10 kHz to -5.7 % at 150 kHz.

However, in both cases the errors are always negative, which means that $I_S(f) > I_{HF}(f)$. Therefore, the connection of the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator to the circuit causes part of the $i_{HF}(t)$ current to flow through the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator instead of the measurement branch.

This phenomenon is inversely proportional to the current frequency because, as the frequency increases, the output impedance of the step-up transformer, which can be approximated as $Z=j\omega L_s$, also increases.

Based on this consideration, it is clear why the errors in HF current tones are much lower when CT1 is used as a step-up transformer for generating 50 Hz current with respect to CT2. In fact, L_s of CT1 has a value about 38 time higher than the one of CT2.

Additionally, CT1 has a significantly lower turns ratio than CT2, with the two being in a ratio of $\sim 1:15$. The turns ratio t is a crucial parameter because the output resistance and inductance of the power amplifier used to drive the CTs, are reflected to the CT secondary side with a factor equal to $1/t^2$. Therefore, since the same power amplifier is used in both cases, the impedance of the amplifier is reflected to the secondary side of CT1 weighted by $(5/75)^2$, while for CT2 it is weighted by $(5/250)^2$.

Figure 49. Errors $\epsilon(f)$ associated with HF tones measured when the iLF(t) generator composed by power amplifier and CT1 (blue line circle marker) and CT2 (red line asterisk marker) are connected to the circuit and generating the fundamental tone, compared to the case when they are galvanically isolated.

To improve the performance of the generation system based on the use of the CT2, it is possible to introduce an inductive blocking element (BlockHF) into the circuit to reduce the $\epsilon(f)$ error associated to the high-frequency current tones. Regarding the blocking element BlockLF, in the case analysed in this paper, its necessity is not emphasized because the transconductance amplifier used to generate the HF current has a capacitive input impedance able to provide high impedance at 50 Hz.

5.3 Transient generators

The 22NRM06 ADMIT project addresses the characterization of instrument transformers under high-frequency conditions up to 150 kHz in medium-voltage grids. One of the main challenges lies in the generation of large-amplitude currents at power frequency (on the order of kiloamperes) combined with superimposed high-frequency components. Within this framework, the primary objective of Task A3.1.4 was to develop a transient current generator capable of producing a power-frequency current up to 2 kA with superimposed damped high-frequency currents extending up to 150 kHz. To achieve this, a system based on two coordinated sources operating in parallel has been designed.

The first source is dedicated to generating the fundamental 50 Hz current, delivering amplitudes up to approximately 2 kA peak in order to reproduce realistic nominal operating conditions of power systems. The second source generates high-frequency transient currents, typically in the form of damped sinusoidal waveforms within the 9 kHz–150 kHz frequency range, with peak amplitudes up to 500 A. These components are intended to emulate fast oscillatory disturbances or high-frequency phenomena superimposed on the fundamental current.

A key design requirement is that both sources operate simultaneously while feeding a common load, without mutual interference. This is achieved through an appropriate coupling strategy, typically based on impedance separation and filtering elements, allowing each source to dominate within its respective frequency band while sharing the same test circuit.

The resulting transient current generator is therefore capable of producing reproducible composite waveforms, such as a 50 Hz current of 1 kA with a superimposed damped oscillation at 10 kHz with an amplitude of several hundred amperes, without introducing significant distortion or compromising system integrity. The availability of such controlled and repeatable test conditions is essential for the subsequent experimental evaluation of instrument transformer accuracy under realistic wideband operating scenarios.

5.3.1 Tests of two series generators

The initial concept was to implement a circuit in which two current generators were connected in series, with toroidal transformers each supplying current to the same current loop. The secondary windings of these transformers would be arranged such that the first transformer would inject 50 Hz current, while the second would inject high-frequency current. It was already known that the superposition of the fundamental 50 Hz current would lead to core saturation in the high-frequency transformer. To prevent this effect, the approach included the addition of an LC resonant circuit. This resonant branch was designed to be tuned precisely at 50 Hz, thereby shunting the fundamental current around the high-frequency transformer and minimizing its exposure to 50 Hz flux.

However, it was observed that placing the injection transformer in the 50 Hz loop significantly increases the loop's inductance at that frequency, and the 50 Hz transformer is unable to inject current. To give an idea, 10 V on the high-voltage side generate 3.3 A on the low-voltage side. Extrapolating, 400 V on the high-voltage side would produce 130 A on the low-voltage side, which is far below the 2 kA target. Therefore, this initial idea was discarded, and the circuit was redesigned to be a parallel generator. Figure 50 shows the test setup of the two series generators.

Figure 50: Test setup of the two series generator.

5.3.2 Test setup of the two parallel generators

The transient current generator was implemented as two current sources wired in parallel into the same test loop, with appropriate filtering elements:

The 50 Hz source consisted of a high-power AC supply capable of several kiloamperes. In practice, a variable transformer feeding multiple step-down current transformers, e.g. three TORIVAC 10 kVA units in parallel, to

generate the $2 \text{ kA}_{\text{rms}}$ at 50 Hz in the test circuit. These transformers were injecting the current to the 50 Hz loop through several meters of braided copper conductor. This loop also carried a percentage of the HF current, which depends on the inductance ratio between the combined loop inductance and the 50 Hz loop inductance.

The high-frequency source was realized as a resonant RLC discharge circuit triggered by a high-speed switch. It comprised a capacitor bank charged to a specified voltage and then rapidly switched to induce a damped sinusoidal current through the HF injection transformer into the test loop. By adjusting the capacitance and inductance, different oscillation frequencies were achieved. This loop carried the high-frequency transient current and a small portion of the 50 Hz current, which also depended on the impedance ratio at 50 Hz between the combined loop impedance and the HF loop impedance. It is composed of the following components:

Capacitor Bank: Selected to tune the oscillation frequency in combination with the circuit inductance. Various capacitance values, from $0.3 \mu\text{F}$ up to a $75 \mu\text{F}$, were tried to target specific frequencies, e.g. using $0.3 \mu\text{F}$ for $\sim 150 \text{ kHz}$, $75 \mu\text{F}$ for $\sim 9 \text{ kHz}$.

Inductances: Only the inductances inherent to the current loop formed the resonant inductive element. These inductances were calculated to be $\sim 4 \mu\text{H}$.

High Frequency Injection Transformer. The output of the resonant circuit was coupled to the HF current loop through a high frequency ferrite core transformer. The ratio of the transformer can be selected to be 1:1 or 2:1.

Switching Device: A high-voltage MOSFET transistor was used to switch and connect the charged capacitor to the inductive circuit, discharging the capacitor into the resonant loop. The MOSFET provided controlled triggering of the transient and was tasked to withstand the peak current, tens to hundreds of amperes, during the discharge. The gate of the MOSFET was activated via a fiber optic trigger. The trigger pulses were generated using a function generator, allowing the triggering of the MOSFET to be synchronized with the zero-crossing or another selectable phase point of the 50 Hz voltage if necessary.

A coupling network was devised to enable both sources to feed the load without affecting the other transient source. Although a small portion of the 50 Hz current was flowing through the HF loop, some units of amperes were sufficient to saturate the HF injection transformer. Because of this, initially, an explicit compensation branch composed of a series resonant LC filter tuned to 50 Hz was added in parallel with the HF injection transformer to greatly reduce 50 Hz current flow through the HF source. However, this idea was later discarded, as it needed a fine tuning of the LC components. Instead, a 50 Hz capacitive current was applied to a third winding of the HF injection transformer to generate a counteracting 50 Hz flux against the inductive current from the test circuit.

The combined output was injected into a test circuit that mimics the conditions of a current transformer under calibration: a copper sheet of around 1 meter. Figure 51 shows the conceptual schematic of the two parallel generators.

Figure 51. Conceptual schematic of the two parallel generators.

5.3.3 Test procedure: Theoretical LC Circuit Calculation

The first step was calculating the theoretical values of capacitance needed, given a chosen inductance, to achieve the target transient frequencies. The inductance was calculated as $L \approx 4 \mu\text{H}$, representative of the high-frequency injection transformer’s leakage inductance and the overall circuit wiring. The targeted resonant frequencies were 9 kHz, 15 kHz, 30 kHz, 50 kHz and 150 kHz.

The theoretical sizing provided a starting point for capacitors selection and charging voltages, so that the semiconductor switching device could be selected. Table 5-2 shows the results of these calculations.

Table 5-2: Theoretical calculations of the required capacitance values and charging voltage

I_p (A)	500	500	500	500	500
f (kHz)	9.0	15.0	30.0	50.0	150.0
T/2 (μs)	55.6	33.3	16.7	10.0	3.3
L (μH)	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0
C (μF)	78.2	28.1	7.0	2.533	0.281
U_c (V)	113.1	188.5	377.0	628.3	1885.0

5.3.4 Test circuit characterization.

As specified in previous paragraphs, the 50 Hz current is injected through its own low-inductance path (e.g. a short, thick braid), and the HF transient is injected via the HFCT onto the same conductive plate, but not in series with the entire 50 Hz circuit. This created two parallel paths on the plate: one for 50 Hz, one for HF, that meet at common connection points. In this configuration, some fractions of the HF transient current can still circulate through the 50 Hz source and vice versa depending on impedance. This ratio was characterized by using a flat copper plate of 25 cm and 100 cm as the point of coupling between loops. Figure 52 shows the view of the test circuit.

Figure 52: View of the two parallel generators. (1) 50 Hz Transformer and current loop; (2) High Frequency Injection Transformer; (3) LC resonant circuit to tune the current transients; (4) Combined output of the current loops; (5) Reference current probe; (6) Capacitor to compensate the 50 Hz flux flowing into the High Frequency Injection Transformer.

For this purpose, high-frequency current was measured in both the central HF loop and in the 50 Hz loop using current probes, and similarly the distribution of 50 Hz current between the intended path and any induced into the HF loop was measured. Table 5-3 and Table 5-4 show the current distribution characterization through the different current loops for both the 50 Hz and the HF current injections for the 100 cm bus bar.

Table 5-3. 50 Hz current measurements through the various current loops.

I_{BT} (A) EUT loop	I_{BT} (A) HF loop	50 Hz Ratio HF/EUT (%)
31.2	1.28E-01	0.41%
64	2.48E-01	0.39%
130	4.96E-01	0.38%
328	1.14E+00	0.35%
2015.4	8.3	0.41%

Table 5-4. HF current measurements through the various current loops.

f (kHz)	C (nF)	I_{BT} (A) EUT	I_{BT} (A) 50Hz	I_{BT} (A) HF	HF Ratio EUT/HF (%)
90	225	11.6	2.6	18.4	81.92%

		22.6	4.8	31.2	82.48%
		45.6	9.8	59.2	82.37%

The tests showed that over 99.6% of the 50 Hz current remained in the main loop, with only 0.4% coupling into the HF branch. This means that at a current level of 2000 A, 8 A would flow through the HF loop. This issue is addressed in the following paragraphs to avoid core saturation of the HF Injection Transformer. Regarding the HF current injection, it was noted that roughly 80% of the transient current stayed in the “HF loop” portion (the plate and local return), while ~20% flow through the 50 Hz source loop. The HF current transients do not cause any harm to the iron core transformer, but it means that the HF current loop will have to inject an extra 20% of current transient to achieve the objective current.

5.3.5 Combined 50 Hz and Transient Operation

In the final tests, the transient generator and the 50 Hz high-current source were operated together in the configuration validated earlier. Specifically, a 50 Hz current of 2000 A was established through the main loop, and then transient pulses at various frequencies, 9 kHz, 15 kHz, 25 kHz, 55 kHz, 120 kHz and 160 kHz were injected at different angles of the 50 Hz current: 0°, 60°, 75° and 90°.

The 50 Hz compensation loop was first introduced in this test. Three 112 µF capacitor connected in series were included in the 50 Hz compensation loop, which was energized at the same voltage as the 50 Hz injection transformer.

When a transient was injected at the 50 Hz current zero-crossing, the transient behaved almost identically to the case with no 50 Hz present. The high-frequency oscillation had its full amplitude and frequency content, and the output ratio of the injection transformer was OK. However, when the transient was injected at 90°, the output ratio of the HF injection transformer was clipped, suggesting that the transformer was approaching the magnetic saturation knee. This issue would be solved tuning better the current through the compensation loop. Table 5-5 shows the results of the tests. Figure 53 shows an example of the combined 50 Hz and the transient current recorded by the oscilloscope.

Table 5-5. HF current measurements through the various current loops.

Capacitor voltage charge (V)	Capacitance (μF)	Frequency (kHz)	Angle ($^\circ$)	I_{BT} (A) HF	I_{BT} (A) EUT
191	75	9.25	0	651	553.35
			60	647	549.95
			75	619	526.15
			90	543	461.55
254	30	15	0	617	524.45
			60	613	521.05
			75	605	514.25
			90	549	466.65
452	10	25	0	645	548.25
			60	645	548.25
			75	623	529.55
			90	569	483.65
960	2	55	0	637.0	541.45
			60	634	538.9
			75	615	522.75
			90	559	475.15
1564	0.5	120	0	621	527.85
			60	621	527.85
			75	617	524.45
			90	586	498.1
1575	0.325	161	0	503	427.55
			60	503	427.55
			75	502	426.7
			90	495	420.75

Figure 53. Example of a 50 Hz current signal and a superimposed transient current.

6 Voltage measuring systems

6.1 LNE measuring system

This section describes the development and characterization of a reference high voltage system developed at LNE, intended for instrument transformer calibration up to 150 kHz, in accordance with IEC 61869, for measurements involving a 35 kV fundamental component with superimposed harmonics typically ranging from a few volts up to several hundreds of volts.

The objective of this work is to develop a reference measurement chain capable of accurately calibrating and assessing the conformity of instrument transformers (ITs) according to the wideband accuracy classes defined in IEC 61869, particularly WB2 and WB3, including the measurement of low-amplitude harmonics in the supraharmic range. Most existing approaches do not specifically address these requirements and remain limited in their ability to measure harmonics with very low amplitudes. In practice, supraharmic components are several orders of magnitude lower than the fundamental, requiring measurement systems with very high dynamic ranges. Meeting standard limits for weak harmonics, down to 0.1 % or even 0.01 % of the fundamental, demands reference systems capable of resolving these components without distortion or coupling from the fundamental signal. Current methods either rely on simplified frequency-response measurements at low amplitudes or on combined fundamental–harmonic approaches, typically limited to lower frequencies and relatively high harmonic levels (e.g., ≥ 1 %). A reference method extending up to 150 kHz, particularly for voltage transformers, is still lacking, which remains a key limitation for reliable conformity assessment in the supraharmic range. To address this gap, this work proposes a new reference chain developed within the ADMIT project. It enables conformity assessment of ITs up to Class WB3, as defined in IEC 61869. Achieving the required uncertainty levels—at least five times lower than the standard limits—requires a redesigned measurement architecture, including a voltage divider with flat amplitude and phase response, as well as dedicated attenuators, filters and acquisition systems.

The developed system is composed of a high voltage divider, precision attenuators and high pass filters, all specifically designed and characterized for this application. It incorporates two parallel measurement paths. The first path, based on the high voltage divider combined with an attenuator, is optimized for measurements of the fundamental component with superimposed harmonics. The second path, consisting of the high voltage divider followed by a high pass filter, is dedicated to the measurement of very low-level harmonic components by improving the signal to noise ratio. Both paths are connected to a digitizer, forming a complete and modular measurement system. The expanded measurement uncertainty has been carefully evaluated and demonstrates that the system is suitable for instrument transformer calibration up to 150 kHz. Furthermore, the architecture of the system allows for future extension up to 500 kHz, addressing emerging needs related to high frequency power quality disturbances and enhancing measurement capabilities in this domain.

6.1.1 Calibration of Voltage Transformers up to 150 kHz

The calibration methodology described in this section establishes the reference chain for assessing voltage transformers in the extended frequency range up to 150 kHz. It provides the practical implementation of the proposed approach. This section first presents the general and theoretical principles of calibration, then details the adopted chain architecture, followed by the design and characterization of its key components and finally the uncertainties of measurement.

6.1.2 Calibration Principle

The amplitude and phase assessment of ITs is performed using a reference IT in combination with a digitizer, as illustrated in Figure 54. The ITs are used to scale down the high voltage to levels compatible with the digitizer input. The reference IT consists of impedances $Z1$ and $Z2$ with known characteristics, defined by $N1(n)$ and $\varphi1(n)$, where n is the harmonic order, $N1(n)$ corresponds to the amplitude transfer function (scale factor), and $\varphi1(n)$ represents the phase response. The IT under test is modelled by impedances $Z3$ and $Z4$,

with unknown characteristics $N2(n)$ and $\varphi2(n)$, corresponding respectively to its scale factor and phase response.

Figure 54 Calibration of an instrument transformer by comparison to a reference high-voltage chain and a digitizer.

The outputs of both ITs are connected to a digitizer, which acquires $V1(n)$ and $V2(n)$. The frequency dependent scale factor of the IT under calibration is determined using Equation (1), while the phase response is obtained using Equation (2).

$$N2(n) = N1(n) \cdot \frac{V1(n)}{V2(n)} = N1(n) \cdot N3(n) \quad (1)$$

$$\varphi2(n) = \varphi1(n) + \Delta\varphi(n) \quad (2)$$

The calibration of the IT relies on the accurate knowledge of the scale factor and phase response of the reference IT as well as on the precise measurement of the voltage ratio and phase difference between the output signals at the digitizer. Consequently, the traceability and overall uncertainty of the calibration are primarily determined by the performance of the reference IT and the digitizer.

6.1.3 The generator

The generation architecture used here consists of the parallel connection between the Power Frequency (at 50/60 Hz) generator and the High-Frequency generator. It proposes a classical characterization method based on the comparison of the outputs of a reference VT and of a VT under test, by means of a comparator. Both the comparator as well as the reference VT should have sufficient accuracy in the frequency range from the power frequency up to 150 kHz.

The Power Frequency Generator is obtained by means of an Arbitrary Waveform Generator cascaded by a low-voltage amplifier, cascaded, in turns, by a step-up transformer to reach the required voltage levels. Instead, the high-frequency generator is obtained by means of a second Arbitrary Waveform Generator cascaded by another low-voltage amplifier, having an output frequency range from DC up to 150 kHz. The generation measurement setup is shown in Figure 55.

Figure 55. Setup implementation of the generator

The applied voltage signals are provided by a two-channels arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) Keysight 33612A (± 10 V output range, 660 MHz maximum sampling rate, and 64 million of samples per channel of onboard memory). The output of the first channel of the AWG (AWG ch. 1) is connected to a voltage amplifier (± 120 V, ± 50 A, 6 kVA) feeding the VT under test through a 100 V / 35 kV with a power capacity of 5 kVA. The output of the second AWG (AWG ch. 2) is connected to a power amplifier N4L LPA400 (± 400 V, 50 mA, DC – 1 MHz, selectable gain). The device under test (DUT) represents the total load of the whole system (mainly reference IT and IT under calibration). Two other dividers have been used to measure 50 Hz and high frequency voltages respectively, just at the output of the corresponding generators. Divider D1 is a commercial RC divider (300 M Ω /10 pF, ratio 1000:1, accuracy 0.1 % at 50 Hz and 1 % at 150 kHz). Divider D2 is a commercial RC divider (100 M Ω /3 pF, ratio 1000:1, accuracy 0.1 % at 50 Hz and 1 % at 150 kHz).

A full remote control of the setup has been implemented in LabVIEW environment. The realized software allows to choose generation parameters, to enable and disable the generation, and to monitor overvoltage and overcurrent situations.

6.1.4 Development of the reference IT

The reference IT acts as a calibrated divider front end that converts high-voltage signals into measurable low-voltage quantities with preserved amplitude and phase information. It should be capable of operating under both DC and AC conditions depending on the type of the IT. For DC applications, test voltages can reach up to 50 kV and measurements are typically performed at 100 % of the rated voltage. For AC applications, the reference condition is usually a 50 Hz (or 60 Hz) sinusoidal waveform with a test voltage of around 35 kV rms (50 kV peak), also applied at nominal voltage. Harmonic components are intentionally superimposed on the fundamental waveform. These harmonics can have amplitudes ranging from 0.01 % to 1 % of the fundamental voltage. The key challenge lies in accurately detecting and quantifying such small harmonic components, both in amplitude and phase, when they are superimposed on a large fundamental voltage. This becomes even more demanding when the frequency of the harmonic content extends up to 150 kHz. The chain must therefore ensure excellent linearity, high dynamic range and minimal phase error across a wide bandwidth.

To address this, two main measurement approaches can be considered. The first technique involves using a single high-voltage divider (HVD) connected to a digitizer with a very high dynamic range. This allows the chain to simultaneously capture both the high-amplitude fundamental component and the much smaller harmonic components. The main advantage of this approach is that it preserves the full waveform and avoids the need for any signal conditioning. However, the drawback lies in the difficulty of finding digitizers or acquisition chains that offer sufficiently high resolution, linearity and noise performance to resolve very-low-level signals (e.g., 0.01 % of the fundamental).

The second approach consists of applying filtering techniques to suppress the fundamental frequency and retain only the harmonic components. This can significantly reduce the dynamic range requirement of the acquisition chain, as the large fundamental component is no longer present in the captured signal. However, this method introduces its own challenges. The accuracy of the measurement can be affected by the non-linearity and imperfections of the filter, particularly in terms of amplitude flatness and phase response.

Each technique has its own advantages and limitations and the choice between them depends on the specific performance targets and available instrumentation. In our case, the target is to be able to assess Class 0.1-WB3 ITs with a target uncertainty five times lower than the accuracy limits defined in IEC 61869-1, namely, 0.02 % for the fundamental frequency, 0.2 % up to 20 kHz and 1 % up to 150 kHz. To overcome the limitations of each individual technique, we have adopted a dual-path architecture that implements both approaches, enabling redundancy, flexibility and improved reliability in harmonic measurements. This hybrid strategy allows for cross-verification. The implemented chain is shown in Figure 56.

Figure 56 Overview schematic of the reference IT for instrument transformer calibration up to 150 kHz.

The reference IT begins with the HVD composed of resistive and capacitive elements (RC structure). The scale factor of the divider has been chosen to be 500. This scaling ensures that the harmonic signal remains high enough for the filtration operation. On the other hand, the fundamental component, after division, reaches a level of ± 100 V peak at the output of the HVD. To bring this signal within the input range of most digitizers, an attenuation stage is developed to reduce the signal to ± 1 V peak, compatible with both the input range and linearity specifications of most high-performance digitizers.

The selection between Path 1 and Path 2 is based on the signal amplitude at the digitizer input. Path 1 (HVD + attenuator) is used whenever the expected input signal is higher than approximately 1 mV (this limitation is defined according to the characterization results of the selected digitizer, see below), which guarantees an adequate signal-to-noise ratio. Otherwise, Path 2 (HVD + high-pass filter) is employed to enhance sensitivity. As an illustration, for a fundamental of 50 kV, a harmonic at 0.1 % of the fundamental corresponds to 50 V at the primary and about 1 mV at the digitizer input after division (scale factor 50,000), making Path 1 appropriate. However, for lower fundamental voltages, the same harmonic ratio results in signals below 1 mV, and Path 2 must therefore be used. This criterion ensures robust operation across different primary voltage levels.

6.1.5 Design of the HVD

The voltage divider is the primary sensing element that scales down the voltage. The development of a new voltage divider is necessary to overcome the limitations of currently available commercial dividers and existing in-house solutions. Most of these dividers are specifically designed for DC, AC@50–60 Hz or impulse voltage measurements and are not optimized for broadband applications involving harmonic content up to 150 kHz. They often feature large scale factors (e.g., 10,000), which limit the output signal amplitude and reduce the visibility of low-level harmonic components, especially when their amplitude represents very small fraction of the fundamental waveform. In addition, these dividers typically suffer from higher noise-to-signal ratios and limited or non-linear frequency responses, making them unsuitable for precise amplitude and phase characterization of weak harmonic signals superimposed on the fundamental.

We have decided to choose an RC structure which combines resistive and capacitive branches in parallel and which, with proper compensation, can reach a bandwidth of several MHz. The high-voltage arm consists of a resistor of $R1 = 100$ M Ω and a capacitor of $C1 = 100$ pF. Moreover, to maintain waveform fidelity, the time constant of the low-voltage part (comprising R2, C2, R3, and C3, as well as the downstream attenuator components R4, R5, C4, and C5) has been precisely adjusted to match the time constant of the high-voltage

arm (R1, C1). This compensation ensures that the divider maintains a flat frequency response and minimal phase shift across the operating bandwidth.

Figure 57. The developed RC high-voltage divider for voltages up to 50 kV peak: (a) high-voltage arm using NP0 capacitors and metallic resistors on a PCB with a zigzag structure; two PCBs mounted in parallel and in opposite directions to reduce electric field influence. (b) Low-voltage arm with a compact coaxial structure, using the same SMD components as the high-voltage arm; (c) electrical circuit of the low-voltage arm.

The HVD that was developed is shown in Figure 57. To build the resistor R1, we have selected resistors of $1\text{ M}\Omega \pm 0.1\%$ from Vishay, type MELF (metal electrode leadless face), 400 mW, 350 V and 15 ppm/°C, due to their excellent voltage linearity. We have measured their voltage linearity from 10 V to 350 V, and they exhibited very good performance, with a voltage deviation better than 0.005 %. When the rated voltage was applied continuously for 10 min, the resistors showed minimal self-heating effects with a deviation better than 0.001 %, confirming excellent thermal stability under power dissipation. We have developed a 50 kV (+20 % of safety margin) section by assembling 200 resistors in series using a zigzag structure on a printed circuit board (PCB). Despite the excellent characteristics of each individual component, applying high voltage has generated intense electric fields around the resistors which have affected the voltage linearity by 0.1 %. To mitigate the influence of these electric fields, we have decided to use two PCBs placed in parallel and opposite directions, so the current flowing through one board circulates in the opposite direction of the second one. This configuration significantly improves the overall voltage linearity. The value of R1 in this case is about 100 M Ω (two 200 M Ω in parallel) and the DC current at the rated voltage is equal to 0.5 mA at 50 kV, which is high enough to eliminate the influence of the leakage current.

To build the capacitor C1, only one type of capacitor meets our requirements: negative/positive-zero (NP0) ceramic capacitors, known for their very low temperature coefficient (TC), typically less than 30 ppm/°C. Polypropylene capacitors also offer good performance but their higher TC (e.g., <300 ppm/°C) exceeds the target uncertainty of 0.02 % at the fundamental frequency. The value of C1 has been selected to be 100 pF to minimize the influence of parasitic capacitance to ground and to limit power dissipation from the voltage source. Murata capacitors rated at 10 nF and 650 V peak-to-peak have been chosen. Each capacitor has been soldered in parallel with each MELF resistor.

In the low-voltage arm of the HVD, the same component technologies as those used in the high-voltage arm have been employed. This approach helps cancel out mutual influences such as temperature, voltage and frequency behaviours. Moreover, the low-voltage arm has been designed with a compact layout to better meet these conditions and minimize parasitic effects. The components R2 and C2 have been soldered in a coaxial configuration to eliminate the influence of stray capacitance to ground. R3 is a damping resistor, and its value is equal to the characteristic impedance of the coaxial cable (50 Ω).

The HVD has been calibrated under various conditions to characterize its scale factor and dynamic behaviour. The main results are presented in Table 6-1, and the output of the divider has been loaded using a measuring instrument with an input impedance equivalent to that of the attenuator.

Table 6-1 Calibration results of the HVD.

Condition	Voltage Range	Scale Factor	Relative Deviation	Remarks
DC	1 kV to 50 kV	500.848	0.004 %	Voltage response
AC/50 Hz	1 kV to 35 kV rms	500.729	0.011 %	Voltage response
DC to 150 kHz	200 V	500.37	0.07 %	Frequency response
Phase shift	200 V			Time constant = -38 ns

At AC@50 Hz, the divider was calibrated from 1 kV to 50 kV yielding a scale factor of 500.848 with a relative deviation of 0.004 %. A second calibration at AC@50 Hz, from 1 kV to 35 kV rms, produced a scale factor of 500.729 with a deviation of 0.011 %. Additionally, a frequency sweep from DC to 150 kHz was performed at 200 V, resulting in a scale factor of 500.37 with a maximum deviation of 0.10 %. Regarding phase behavior, a time constant of -38 ns was measured, characterizing the phase shift performance of the divider across frequency, and can be calculated using Equation (3):

$$\text{Phase (rad)} = 2\pi ft, \quad (3)$$

where f is the frequency of the signal and t is the time constant.

The calibration results demonstrate that the HVD offers excellent performance in terms of accuracy and stability across a wide range of voltages and frequencies. The divider meets the stringent accuracy requirement in terms of the scale factor from DC to 150 kHz. Additionally, the measured time constant of -38 ns ensures reliable correction of the phase behaviour for each frequency.

6.1.6 Design of the Attenuator

The attenuator plays a crucial role in the measurement chain by further reducing the already scaled-down voltage from the HVD to a level compatible with the input range of the measurement instrument such as a digitizer. Beyond voltage reduction, the attenuator also aids in impedance matching between the divider and the measuring device, minimizing signal reflections and preserving measurement accuracy. By providing a stable and linear attenuation over a wide frequency range, it helps maintain signal integrity. The input impedance of the attenuator is designed to emulate the input impedance of the digitizer; therefore, when the attenuator is connected, HVD frequency behaviour does not change if compared to the behaviour measured with HVD only. As, for the case at hand, the input impedance of the digitizer is typically about 1 M Ω /30 pF, while the input impedance of the attenuator is fixed to R4 \cong 1 M Ω and C4 \cong 30 pF.

The developed attenuator has a scale factor of 100. It is built using components similar to the HVD (NPO capacitors and metallic resistors) and features a coaxial and compact structure in order to minimize parasitic effects and maintain excellent high-frequency behaviour. The output of the attenuator is matched to the input impedance of the digitizer, typically also equal to 1 M Ω in parallel with 30 pF. Additionally, the time constant of the high-voltage part is matched with that of the low-voltage part to ensure good frequency behaviour.

The combination of the HVD and the attenuator results in a total scale factor of 50,000. Consequently, when measuring a high-voltage signal of 50 kV peak, the chain provides an output of 1 V, which can be accurately captured using the 1 V input range of the digitizer. Two attenuators have been developed: attenuator A is associated with the HVD, while attenuator B is potentially associated with the instrument transformer (IT) under calibration. Additional attenuators can be easily developed to match the scale factors of various ITs (e.g., attenuation of 5, 10, 50 and 200) or various impedances (e.g., 2 M Ω and 10 M Ω). The electrical circuit and the developed attenuators are shown in Figure 58.

(b)

(c)

Figure 58. Developed attenuators. (a) Electrical circuit; (b) measurement results for amplitude response; (c) measurement results for phase response.

From the results, it is shown that the frequency responses of both attenuators are relatively flat over the range from DC to 150 kHz. Attenuator A maintains a scale factor around 102.5, with minimal variation (~0.1 %). Attenuator B shows slightly more variation, with a gradual decrease in the scale factor from approximately 102.6 to 102.3, which re-mains negligible. In terms of phase, the phase at the fundamental frequency is almost zero for both attenuators. A small overshoot is observed around 7 kHz; beyond that, the phase response is nearly linear, allowing for correction if necessary. Note that the scale factor and phase values are obtained under certain conditions; the load, specifically the input impedance of the digitizer, has a significant influence. For example, a 1 pF variation in the capacitance and 1 % variation in the resistance of 1 MΩ affects the scale factor by about 0.01 % and the phase by approximately 0.0015 crad. Therefore, the input impedance of the digitizer must be measured precisely to apply corrections if necessary.

6.1.7 Design of the Filter

The filter enhances the sensing capability for weak harmonics. The objective of the filter is to analyse high frequency harmonic components with very small amplitudes (e.g., 0.01 % of the fundamental). It is required to strongly attenuate the fundamental frequency (50 Hz) and its low-order harmonics, particularly up to a few hundreds of Hz. The goal is to suppress dominant low-frequency components and only retain harmonics in the range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. To achieve sufficient rejection of the fundamental and its harmonics, a filter of at least the 4th order is necessary. The use of filters in harmonic measurement is common and has been the subject of numerous scientific studies; we have decided to develop a high-pass filter (HPF) to analyse these supraharmonics.

The equivalent impedance of the filter needs to be high to not strongly disturb the metrological characteristics of the HVD. However, this high impedance comes with trade-offs: it tends to increase the cutoff frequency of the filter. In addition, the capacitor C6 of the filter needs to be much higher than the input capacitance of the digitizer (typically around 30 pF), because together they form a capacitive voltage divider. If the filter capacitor is too small, it will significantly reduce the signal reaching the digitizer, resulting in undesired attenuation of the output voltage. As a result, an ideal filter response is not achievable, and a balance must be found between attenuation performance and phase linearity; a small attenuation and phase shift will still be present in the range of 9 kHz–150 kHz.

Another limitation in the filter design arises from the input resistor of the digitizer, typically 1 MΩ, which is internally connected in parallel with its input capacitance. This resistor cannot be removed or modified, yet it forms part of the overall RC network seen by the filter. As a result, it introduces a fixed time constant that limits the ability to precisely control the cutoff frequency of the filter using the external resistor R7 alone. Even if R7 is carefully selected, the presence of the digitizer’s internal 1 MΩ resistor means that the effective resistance seen by the filter is not purely defined by R7, but by the parallel combination of R7 and the digitizer’s input resistance. This constraint reduces the flexibility in filter tuning and must be considered when designing the frequency response. In particular, it makes it more difficult to achieve sharp cutoffs or target specific bandwidths without compromising other aspects such as signal attenuation or phase linearity. A possible solution is to develop impedance matchers or active filters, but such developments will bring other difficulties such as electronic noise.

For these reasons, the filter is intended to be used only when the harmonic voltages are very low (typically < 0.1 % of the fundamental), where precise filtering is critical. In cases where harmonics are more significant, the primary measurement chain (HVD + attenuator) is used without the filter to preserve accuracy. Because the implementation of the filter slightly modifies the electrical behaviour of the measurement chain, particularly in terms of impedance, frequency response and phase behaviour, it is essential to characterize the complete chain with the filter to ensure measurement reliability and traceability.

We have chosen to set up a 4th-order low-pass filter using a cascade of RC (resistor–capacitor) stages. A 4th-order passive RC filter was selected to ensure stability, simplicity and reproducibility in the 9–150 kHz frequency range. Passive filters present the advantage of being inherently linear and free from additional noise or distortion that can be introduced by active components. A higher-order design was considered unnecessary as the 4th-order response already provided sufficient attenuation outside the band of interest while maintaining good phase characteristics. Each stage consisted of a 220-pF capacitor and a 500-kΩ resistor to ground, forming individual first-order low-pass filters. By cascading these stages, we obtained a sharper frequency roll-off characteristic of a 4th-order filter, which attenuates low-frequency components more aggressively. The capacitors and resistors were chosen from the same technologies as the HVD and the attenuator. The results of this filter are presented in Figure 59.

Figure 59. The developed filter: (a) electrical circuit; (b) gain and frequency results of the developed filter only; (c) gain and frequency results of the developed filter associated with the HVD.

From the results of the filter alone, it can be observed that the attenuation between 9 kHz and 150 kHz is approximately 5 dB. This attenuation is primarily due to the influence of the input impedance of the digitizer, as previously discussed. The 50 Hz fundamental component is attenuated by about 85 dB, while the 10th harmonic of the 50 Hz signal (i.e., 500 Hz) is attenuated by approximately 40 dB. When the filter is combined with the HVD, the attenuation between 9 kHz and 150 kHz increases significantly, ranging from 60 dB to 57 dB, and the 50 Hz fundamental is attenuated by approximately 126 dB. These results demonstrate that the filter is sufficiently effective in suppressing both the fundamental and low-frequency harmonics. However, as previously noted, the impedance seen by the filter (e.g., impedance of the digitizer) has a strong influence on the gain and phase responses of the filter. According to the characterization results, a variation of just 1 pF in this impedance can lead to an error of approximately 0.9 % in gain and 0.04 crad in phase at 150 kHz.

In practice, the divider and associated filter are calibrated together as a complete chain to ensure traceability of the scale factor and frequency response in the 9–150 kHz range. Since the calibration is performed with an impedance slightly different from that of the digitizer input, a correction is applied during data processing to account for the exact input impedance of the digitizer. This guarantees that the influence of the filter and the impedance mismatch are both compensated for, ensuring accurate amplitude and phase measurements over the frequency range of interest.

6.1.8 Selection and Characterization of the Digitizer

The digitizer completes the sensing chain by converting the conditioned analogue signals into digital data for further analysis. To ensure accurate measurements, the digitizer used in the chain must meet several important requirements. Its input impedance, typically 1 M Ω /30 pF, needs to be known accurately in order to correct the measuring chains if needed in terms of both scale factor and phase. When used in combination with the filter, the digitizer characteristics become even more critical. In this configuration, the digitizer and filter together form a capacitive voltage divider, which can significantly affect the signal amplitude if not properly accounted for. Therefore, the input capacitance of the digitizer must be precisely known and considered during chain calibration. The corrections of the input impedances of the digitizers are usually obtained by experimentations.

The input voltage range must be compatible with the output of the measurement chain, ideally allowing a 1 V peak full-scale input when measuring up to 50 kV peak, assuming a total scale factor of 50,000. The digitizer should provide high resolution, preferably 16 bits or more, to accurately capture small signal components such as harmonics down to 0.1 % of the fundamental. A wide analogue bandwidth is also essential; the digitizer should offer a bandwidth of at least several MHz to accurately capture signal content up to 150 kHz without amplitude distortion or phase error. A high sampling rate (e.g., 10 MS/s or higher) is required to prevent aliasing and enable precise time- and frequency-domain analysis.

Several digitizers were considered for high-voltage measurements, including the PicoScope 4262, Fluke 8588A, Keysight 3458A, NI PXIe-6396 and Applicos WFD22. While the Fluke and Keysight models offer excellent accuracy and resolution for low-frequency metrology, their single inputs necessitate the need to use two digitizers with a high-accuracy synchronization chain. The NI PXIe-6396 and Applicos WFD22 provide higher performance and resolution but require more complex integration and software development. The PicoScope 4262 was ultimately chosen for its ideal balance of low noise (~8.5 μ V RMS), 16-bit resolution, 5 MHz bandwidth and 10 MS/s sampling rate, along with fast USB communication, easy programming and two internally synchronized channels. The datasheet of the PicoScope 4262 does not specify the time delay between the two channels. This delay has been determined during the calibration of the instrument. An alternative method to mitigate a possible delay is to interchange the oscilloscope channels so that the effect cancels out. However, we chose to include this delay directly in the measurement uncertainty section. These features make it well suited for capturing small harmonic signals up to 150 kHz and for rapid integration.

The PicoScope 4262 was characterized in the ± 1 V range by measuring small signals of 10 mV and 1 mV amplitude, corresponding to 1 % and 0.1 % of the range, respectively. This was performed to assess the scope's ability to detect low-level signals within a high dynamic range in the frequency from 10 kHz to 150 kHz. The oscilloscope was configured identically to its operational setup for the acquisition of a fundamental @50 Hz and the superimposed harmonics: with a 5 MHz analogue bandwidth, 10 MS/s sampling rate and horizontal resolution set to 20 ms/div. Measurements were carried out using two methods: direct time-domain acquisition with RMS readings and frequency-domain analysis using FFT. While the RMS method provides a general

measure of signal energy, it incorporates all harmonic components, along with noise, offset and spurious signals, which reduces its accuracy, especially at low amplitudes around 0.1 % of the range. In contrast, the FFT method is more representative, as it allows for direct extraction of specific harmonic amplitudes, making it more suitable for evaluating small-signal detection. The results were expressed either in terms of absolute amplitude or as the ratio of amplitudes and their phase shifts between two input channels. This ratio is particularly relevant, as it reflects the actual quantity being measured in the chain according to the governing Equations (1) and (2). Using the amplitude ratio also helps reduce sensitivity to absolute gain variations or noise and thus provides a more accurate evaluation of the chain harmonic measurement performance. The results are presented in Figure 60.

Figure 60. Digitizer error across a range of frequencies (10 kHz to 150 kHz) for different measurement methods (rms and FFT) and signal amplitudes (1 mV and 10 mV) in ± 1 V range.

It is evident that RMS-based measurements, particularly for individual channels (A and B), exhibit higher errors, around 0.2 % at 10 mV. At the 1 mV level, the rms results are unusable due to the influence of noise, offset and non-harmonic components included in the rms calculation. The amplitude ratio (A/B) shows significantly lower and more stable errors, typically below 0.05 %, demonstrating improved accuracy in detecting small harmonic components. Even at very low signal levels (1 mV or 0.1 % of the range), the FFT method maintains acceptable performance, with errors remaining under 0.3 % across the frequency range. In terms of phase shift between both inputs, an error of approximately 0.1 crad is observed up to 150 kHz, measured by applying the same signal to both inputs. At the fundamental frequency (AC or DC), the FFT technique has also been used to measure the amplitude ratio (A/B), with observed errors around 0.04 % with an associated uncertainty of 0.01 %.

These results confirm that the PicoScope 4262, when used with FFT-based ratio measurements, provides a more accurate and representative evaluation of harmonic components in high-dynamic-range conditions, particularly when signal amplitudes are low. For harmonic voltages lower than 0.1 % of the range and down to 0.01 %, the use of the dedicated filter becomes beneficial. In this case, the filter enhances the harmonic component while suppressing the fundamental, so that the voltage applied to the digitizer re-mains above 1 mV, making it measurable with acceptable error levels, typically around 0.3 %, as demonstrated.

6.1.9 Estimation of Measurement Uncertainties

Two measurement paths are available. The first path, consisting of the HVD followed by the attenuator (scale factor of 50,000), is used to measure the fundamental frequency and any harmonic components with amplitudes greater than 0.1 % of the fundamental. The maximum test voltage is 50 kV according to the characteristics of the HVD. In this case, 0.1 % of the fundamental corresponds to 50 V at the divider input, i.e., 1 mV at the measurement output. However, if the test voltage is lower than 50 kV, the relative criterion of 0.1 % is no longer meaningful. Therefore, there is a minimum limit of 1 mV at the output, regardless of the actual test voltage.

The second path, which bypasses the attenuator and uses the HPF, is configured to only measure harmonics with amplitudes as low as 0.01 % of the fundamental (or output voltage < 1 mV if using the first path). Since this path avoids additional attenuation, it offers a better signal-to-noise ratio for detecting weak harmonics that might otherwise be buried in the noise floor or undetectable due to limited resolution.

This separation of signal acquisition paths ensures the following:

- Path 1: (HVD + attenuator) for the measurement of fundamental and harmonic amplitudes as low as 0.1 % of the fundamental (or output voltage as low as 1 mV);
- Path 2: (HVD + HPF) for the measurement of weak harmonics as low as 0.01 % of the fundamental (or output voltage lower than 1 mV using the first path).

The calibration uncertainty depends solely on the calibration uncertainty of the reference measuring chain (Path 1 or Path 2) and on the voltage ratio measured at the digitizer side. The influence of temperature has been neglected, since all components used in the development have very small temperature coefficients, and all measurements are per-formed in a high-precision, temperature-controlled room at $(23 \pm 1) ^\circ\text{C}$.

6.1.10 Uncertainty Estimation for the Fundamental Component

The main uncertainty contributions for the measurement of the fundamental are as follows:

- Calibration of Path 1: To achieve low uncertainty at the fundamental, the entirety of Path 1 is calibrated using our internal reference procedure that accounts for stray impedance effects. Calibration is performed with an impedance equivalent to that of the digitizer. The resulting standard uncertainty is 0.0015 % for amplitude (AC and DC) and 0.0015 crad for phase.
- Digitizer calibration: The voltage ratio is calibrated in both amplitude and phase by injecting two known voltage signals directly into the digitizer inputs in the same configuration as it is used during high-voltage measurements. The signals are analysed using FFT to determine the complex ratio between channels. The estimated standard uncertainties are 0.01 % for amplitude (AC and DC) and 0.01 crad for phase (at 50 Hz).
- Influence of the attenuator load: The uncertainty caused by load effects is included in the overall uncertainty budget since Path 1 is calibrated without the digitizer. The input impedance of the digitizer needs to be accurately determined to correct this influence if needed. We consider an associated uncertainty of 1 pF for the capacitive part and 1 % for the resistive part, resulting in an estimated uncertainty of 0.01 % for amplitude (AC and DC) and approximately 0.0015 crad for phase, considered negligible.

6.1.11 Uncertainty Estimation of Harmonics using path 1.

To ensure accurate harmonic analysis from 9 kHz to 150 kHz, we set a threshold of 1 mV (output voltage > 1 mV if using Path 1). Harmonic components above this threshold are acquired using Path 1. To maintain the required measurement uncertainty, each component of Path 1 (HVD, attenuator) must be calibrated separately. Calibrating the entire path as a whole can degrade accuracy, especially for phase, due to the small voltage on the output of Path 1 (scale factor of 50,000). Calibrating each part independently under controlled conditions minimizes uncertainty and ensures traceability. The main contributions are as follows:

- HVD Calibration: Calibrated up to 150 kHz. A standard uncertainty of 0.1 % is adopted for amplitude. For phase, a correction factor of 38 ns is applied, with a standard uncertainty of 1 ns (equivalent to 0.1 crad at 150 kHz). The HVD is calibrated with a load equivalent to the attenuator (30 pF//1 M Ω).
- HVD Load Sensitivity: A variation of 1 pF in capacitance and 1 % in the 1 M Ω resistive load introduces a standard uncertainty of approximately 0.005 % for the amplitude and a negligible phase uncertainty over 9 kHz to 150 kHz.
- Attenuator Calibration: Calibrated up to 150 kHz in both amplitude and phase. From Figure 58, a standard uncertainty of 0.1 % is adopted for amplitude. For phase, a correction is applied, with a standard uncertainty of 0.1 crad.
- Attenuator Load Sensitivity: A 1 pF change in capacitance and 1 % variation in resistive load introduces an uncertainty of approximately 0.005 crad in phase and 0.03 % in gain over the 9 kHz to 150 kHz range.

- Digitizer Calibration: As shown in Figure 60, for harmonic voltages at 0.1 % of the fundamental, a standard uncertainty of 0.3 % can be adopted. For 1 % of the fundamental, 0.1 % uncertainty is applicable. The associated phase uncertainty is 0.1 crad.

6.1.12 Uncertainty Estimation of Harmonics using path 2

For accurate detection of very-low-level harmonics down to 0.01 % of the fundamental (or output voltage < 0.1 mV if using the path1), we use Path 2 (HVD + Filter). The output voltage of Path 2 is then higher than 1 mV due to its low attenuation (about 60 dB).

The uncertainty contributions come primarily from Path 2 and the digitizer.

- Path 2 Calibration: To achieve accurate results, Path 2 can be calibrated at 20 V, from 9 kHz to 150 kHz, using our reference procedure that accounts for stray impedance effects. Calibration is performed with a load equivalent to that of the digitizer. The resulting standard uncertainties are 0.2 % for amplitude and 0.2 crad for phase.
- Digitizer Calibration: As described earlier, the voltage ratio is calibrated using two known signals and FFT analysis. Given the scale factor of Path 2 (up to 3000), a harmonic at 0.01 % of a 5 V fundamental results in an up to 1.6 mV signal at the digitizer input. This can be easily acquired using the 10 mV range of the digitizer. The estimated standard uncertainty is 0.2 % for amplitude and 0.1 crad for phase.
- Filter Load Sensitivity: A 1 pF variation in capacitance and 1 % in the 1 M Ω resistive load introduce a phase uncertainty of approximately 0.04 crad and a gain uncertainty of about 0.9 % in the 9 kHz to 150 kHz frequency range.

6.1.13 Expanded uncertainties

The calibration uncertainty of the measurement chain was evaluated across the frequency range of 9 kHz to 150 kHz using the GUM. The results are summarized in Table 6-2 and Table 6-3, respectively, for amplitude and phase. The expanded uncertainties (with a coverage factor $k \approx 2$) were determined for different amplitude levels of harmonic components relative to the fundamental. Equation (4) has been used for the calculation of the expanded uncertainty.

$$U = 2 \sqrt{\sum u_i^2}, \quad (4)$$

where u_i is the standard uncertainty of each contribution source.

The results presented in Table 6-2 show that the measurement chain achieves expanded uncertainties close to the target values that we have fixed and required for the conformity assessment of IT instrument transformers according to IEC 61869 Class WB3. For the fundamental frequency, the uncertainty is slightly above the ideal target (0.028 % vs. 0.02 %) but remains acceptable for most practical applications. For harmonics with voltage output higher than 0.1 %; the uncertainties (0.29 % and 0.45 %, respectively) are also just above the target thresholds (0.2 % and 0.4 %) yet still demonstrate adequate performance for PQ evaluation in the 9 kHz to 150 kHz range. For very-low-level harmonics, 0.01 % of the fundamental, the expanded uncertainty reaches 2 %, which is two times higher than the fixed target uncertainty (1 % up to 150 kHz). The major contribution here is the load sensitivity of the filter.

Table 6-2. Calibration uncertainty of instrument transformers for amplitude

Contribution/Source	Fundamental (Path 1)	9 kHz to 150 kHz U out > 1 mV (Path 1)	9 kHz to 150 kHz U out < 1 mV (Path 2)
Calibration of path/HVD	0.0015 %	0.1 %	0.2 %
Digitizer calibration	0.01 %	0.1 % (U out > 10 mV) 0.3 % (U out > 1 mV)	0.2 %
Attenuator calibration	(included in path)	0.1 %	-
Load sensitivity	0.01 % (attenuator)	0.005 % (HVD) 0.03 % (attenuator)	0.9 % (filter)
Expanded uncertainty (k = 2)	0.028 %	0.29 % (U out > 10 mV.) 0.45 % (U out > 1 mV.)	1.9 %

Table 6-3. Calibration uncertainty of instrument transformers for phase

Contribution/Source	Fundamental (Path 1)	9 kHz to 150 kHz U out > 1 mV (Path 1)	9 kHz to 150 kHz U out < 1 mV (Path 2)
Calibration of path/HVD	0.0015 %	0.1 %	0.2 %
Calibration of path/HVD	0.0015 card	0.1 card	0.2 crad
Digitizer calibration	0.01 card	0.1 crad	0.1 crad
Attenuator calibration	–(included in path)	0.1 crad	-
Load sensitivity	0.005 crad (attenuator)	0.005 % (HVD) 0.005 crad (attenuator)	0.04 crad (filter)
Expanded uncertainty (k = 2)	0.020 crad	0.3 crad	0.5 crad

6.1.14 Conclusion

A reference measurement chain for the assessment of medium-voltage instrument transformers ITs in the extended frequency range up to 150 kHz has been developed and validated. The chain is based on a dual-path architecture combining a wideband high-voltage divider, precision attenuators and a dedicated high-pass filter, enabling both accurate fundamental measurements and the detection of very-low-level harmonic components.

The results demonstrate that the chain achieves expanded uncertainties of 0.028 % at the fundamental frequency, below 0.5 % for harmonic components down to 1 mV (0.1 % of the fundamental) and around 1.9 % for very-low-level harmonics at lower than 1 mV (e.g. 0.01 % of the fundamental). Although these latter results remain compatible with the IEC 61869 Class WB3 requirements, the margin becomes narrow at such low levels. This limitation is mainly due to the sensitivity of the high-pass filter to load conditions and further improvements in the filter design are expected to reduce the uncertainty below the current 1.9 % and extend the chain to the WB4 range up to 500 kHz.

Finally, the chain described in this work can be reproduced by transformer manufacturers and adapted either for direct use in grid measurements under realistic conditions or for the characterization of their products in test laboratories. This makes it not only a reference for NMIs but also a practical tool for industry. This establishes the chain not only as a reference measurement setup but also as a high-voltage platform that can be reproduced and adapted for industrial applications.

6.2 RISE measuring system

The objective of WP2 of the project was to design and characterise a voltage measurement system for measurements of line frequency and harmonics up to 5 kHz superimposed by supraharmonics in the frequency

range 9 – 150 kHz. The measurement system shall meet the requirements for a substation monitoring with system voltage of 36 kV. A voltage divider thus have be designed for 21 kV phase-to-earth voltage.

RISE reference measurement system builds on the design of a 500/320 kV (DC/ACrms) universal divider which was developed in the EMPIR 19NRM07 HVcom2 project [5]. The divider was scaled down to a smaller broadband divider RCR125 - 125/80 kV (DC/ACrms), increasing the bandwidth from 500 kHz to 1 MHz to meet the frequency requirements of ADMIT. The RCR125 was designed, built and characterized late 2024, and the ratio and phase error is plotted in Figure 61.

Figure 61. The RCR125 divider and ratio/phase errors.

The performance of RCR125 was deemed insufficient and a decision was made to go beyond and reduce the ratio and phase errors further.

A new generation wideband divider, the RCR36, was designed and built to measure up to 50 kV DC, 36 kV ACrms, withstand 100/70 kV (DC/ACrms) and withstand 175 kV lightning impulse voltages. This divider has a crossover frequency of 3.8 MHz (C-Rd) and a crossover frequency L/Rd of 15 MHz.

Three RCR36 dividers are being built to be able to measure on three-phase systems. The digitizer for the final set-up is an 18-bit, 8ch simultaneously sampling board from National Instruments, the PXIe-6396. With this and three Rogowski current sensors a measurement system is ready to monitor power grids in substations with 36 kV system voltage. Here should be noted that the voltage divider will measure three phase voltages of 21 kV, and these must withstand overvoltages up to 70 kV [19] which is met by this design.

An active bandpass filter with 10x or 100x amplification has been designed to increase the sensitivity for supraharmonics (9 – 150 kHz) with parallel sampling of the output from the divider. Each phase will then be simultaneously sampled by 2 channels.

6.2.1 The RCR36 system

A schematic of the system is shown in Figure 62 with divider, attenuator, bandpass amplifier and digitizer inputs per phase. A photo of the 3-phase voltage measurement system is presented in Figure 63 and builds on the experience of an earlier design. For future use in substations the divider designed in this project must withstand 1.95 times the nominal phase voltage and if needed the HV modules can be stacked.

Figure 62. Schematic and physical layout of the measurement system.

Figure 63. Three phase voltage divider set-ups with PXIe-6396 digitizer.

The voltage divider has two outputs, one for DC and AC fundamental components, and the other for harmonics measurement. The harmonics measurement branch incorporates a precision voltage divider, filtering, and amplification before data acquisition. Filtering is necessary to attenuate the fundamental component, while the amplifier enhances the signal for precise measurement using the data acquisition system.

6.2.2 The divider

The voltage divider, with a nominal scale factor (SF) of 162, combined with an attenuator with SF 100, reduces the HV to measurable levels, lower than 2.0 V, 1.4 V, and 5.6 V for DC, AC, and impulse signals, respectively. The divider consists of HV/LV branches (1080 MΩ/6.7 MΩ) and a capacitive branch for AC measurements from 5 Hz to 1 MHz (300 pF/ 48 nF). The damping resistors (180 Ω/1.1 Ω) gives a crossover frequency from capacitive to resistive divider from damping resistors of 2.9 MHz and an upper bandwidth of c.a. 10 MHz from typical uncompensated inductance. The resulting modelled divider output is shown in Figure 64.

Figure 64. Divider design (left) and modelled divider ratio and phase error (right).

The physical construction of the divider is compact (165 mm diameter, 250 mm high, weighs 6.7 kg) and optimized for HF response and low signal distortion. The system ensures accurate HV measurements across a broad frequency range (DC–150 kHz), making it suitable for harmonic analysis and HV testing while addressing key challenges such as low noise, electromagnetic interference (EMI) immunity, and stable frequency response.

6.2.3 The attenuator

The attenuator is also an RCR divider with SF 100, has a crossover frequency from capacitive to resistive divider from damping resistors and an upper bandwidth of 1.3 MHz, and an upper bandwidth of c.a. 74 MHz from typical uncompensated inductance. The measured ratio and phase error from characterization of an attenuator using RISE DSWM Ultra reference measurement system is shown in Figure 65.

Figure 65. Measured attenuator ratio and phase error.

6.2.4 System performance

The resulting modelled system output is shown in Figure 66.

Figure 66. Measured attenuator ratio and phase error.

6.2.5 Enhancement of the supraharmonics signals

Typically, the voltage levels of the supraharmonics are typically around 100 times lower than the line voltage levels. To measure those voltages in the 9 – 150 kHz range a bandpass amplifier has been designed, suppressing the line voltages and amplifying the supraharmonics. The first design amplifies the signals by a factor of 10. Design criteria for the bandpass amplifier are shown in Figure 67

Figure 67. Design of a bandpass amplifier.

6.2.6 Measurement uncertainties

Traceability of the measurement systems of RISE is ensured by the calibration of the divider together with the attenuator in a first step using the reference measurement system DSWM Ultra with a 1 MHz bandwidth. This procedure gives a ratio uncertainty up to 0.05% and a phase uncertainty of 0.02 mrad. The specified expanded measurement uncertainty from PXIe-6396 is better than 330 μ V/V for the 2 V range, which is the maximum output from the divider/attenuator. The digitizer measurement uncertainty therefore adds 0.033% for the ratio and a negligible contribution for phase error between channels from its simultaneous sampling.

The combined expanded uncertainty for the ratio is $\pm 0.06\%$ up to 150 kHz (DSWM). The combined uncertainty for phase displacement of the calibration set up is 0.02 mrad. Ratio errors and phase shifts in the bandpass amplifier will add to the uncertainty of the 9 – 150 kHz range is applied.

6.3 VTT measuring system

6.3.1 Low voltage multitone harmonics system

VTT system for generation and measurement of 50 Hz fundamental and harmonics is show in Figure 68. A signal with up to 10 frequency components is created, and it is uploaded to the two-channel arbitrary waveform generator (AWG, Keysight 33500B). One channel of the AWG feeds the voltage amplifier (Fluke 5205A), and the other channel provides a synchronized trigger signal to the two-channel digitizer (Applicos WFD20).

A wideband voltage divider is used as the reference for calibration of voltage sensors. The VTT low voltage reference voltage divider has been characterized up to 100 kHz using two methods, 1) by comparison with AC voltage reference (Fluke 5790), and 2) by calculation from step response. The voltage step was generated using a closing mercury-wetted relay switch. Comparison of the results obtained using the two method is shown in Figure 69.

Figure 68. VTT multitone generation and measurement setup.

f	Relative uncertainty
100 Hz	0.04 %
1 kHz	0.01 %
10 kHz	0.007 %
100 kHz	0.18 %

Figure 69. VTT low voltage reference divider amplitude response.

The system is controlled by a PC. A typical recorded reference multitone signal and its FTT are shown in Figure 70.

As the sampling is coherent with the multitone reference signal, no windowing is needed, and each generated harmonic will fall in one FTT bin without spectral leakage. Both gain error and phase displacement can be obtained by dividing the complex input Fourier spectrum of the device under calibration by the output spectrum.

Figure 70. An example of a measured multitone waveform. Even though the signal level is low, the signal-to-noise ratio is c. 75 dB.

6.3.2 High voltage multitone harmonics system

The VTT wideband high voltage divider was calibrated using the low voltage divider as reference. The amplitude response and phase displacement of the high voltage reference divider up to 100 kHz are shown in Figure 71. The amplitude response has been corrected according to low voltage divider response.

Figure 71. VTT high voltage reference divider amplitude and phase response.

A high-frequency reference measuring system has been validated to extend accurate medium-voltage instrument transformer and voltage sensor calibration for range from 10 Hz to 100 kHz. The system employs both low and high voltage wideband high-voltage RC dividers in combination with a high-resolution digital recorder.

Characterization tests have been performed to confirm the system's performance and identify key uncertainty influences. The high voltage reference system scale factor overall uncertainty up to 100 kV is less than 0.1 % from 50 Hz to 100 kHz, and the phase displacement uncertainty is less than 20 mrad in the same frequency range.

6.4 INRIM measuring system

This section presents the reference dividers and the acquisition system adopted at INRIM for the characterization of MV transducers up to 150 kHz. They are integrated into a novel generation and measurement setup designed primarily for industrial applications and described in {Citation}.

6.4.1 Description and Characterization

Measuring voltage system used at INRIM is based on the use of off-shelf resistive-capacitive voltage dividers (RCVDs) and an acquisition system. Two different RCVDs are available. First, indicated as RCVD_A is air insulated, designed for DC and AC (50/60 Hz) applications. It has a rated primary voltage of 3 kV, a rated scale factor (SF) equal to 1000 V/V and accuracy class of 0.2 %. The second RCVD (RCVD_B) is gas-insulated, and it designed for PQ applications, it has ± 45 kV rated primary voltage, a SF of 10000 V/V, a declared bandwidth from DC to 1 MHz and 0.2 accuracy class at 50/60 Hz.

The two RCVDs have been characterized with a sinusoidal frequency sweep (SFS) in the range [10; 150] kHz at reduced amplitudes using a Fluke 5730A calibrator and results are provided in Figure 72. As can be observed, RCVD_A SF variation is within 0.2 % whereas for RCVD_B it is within 0.5 %.

Figure 72. Frequency dependence of the two voltage dividers used in INRIM measuring system.

The measured reference and the test signals are acquired by a comparator that includes a NI compact Data Acquisition system (cDAQ) with the NI 9223 board. The module provides four simultaneously sampled differential input channels with a 16-bit resolution, enabling accurate measurement of fast-changing signals. Each channel supports a maximum sampling rate of 1 MHz, ensuring precise time alignment across all inputs. The input range is ± 10 V, with selectable AC or DC coupling. The module features an input impedance of 1 M Ω in parallel with approximately 100 pF and includes built-in anti-aliasing filters that automatically adjust according to the selected sampling rate. The analogue bandwidth is approximately 800 kHz, making the device suitable for high-frequency measurements.

The acquisition module NI 9223 was characterized in comparator mode, i.e., by providing the same signal to two channels. When used in this configuration, the frequency response in the [10; 150] kHz range is flat within ± 70 μ V/V.

6.4.2 Conclusion

This section has presented the reference dividers and the acquisition system adopted at INRIM for the characterization of MV transducers up to 150 kHz. They are integrated into a novel generation and measurement setup designed primarily for industrial applications and described in [54]. Both the transducers and the acquisition system are implemented using off-the-shelf instrumentation, which has been metrologically characterized at INRIM.

The maximum uncertainty obtained with the proposed setup in the frequency range from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz is lower than 1.5 % and 1.5 crad (95 % level of confidence) for the ratio and phase errors, respectively.

6.5 FFII measuring system

The reference measuring system to measure harmonics is composed of a high-voltage voltage divider developed in the HVcom² project and a high-resolution PicoScope 5400 digital recorder. Its characteristics, the characterization tests carried out, and the detailed estimation of the associated measurement uncertainties are described in the following paragraphs, focusing on the harmonic range of 9 kHz to 150 kHz.

6.5.1 Description of the Reference Measuring System

FFII measuring system is shown in Figure 73. The HVcom² voltage divider is a wideband high-voltage RC divider with a nominal ratio of approximately 1000:1. It was selected as the main divider for the reference measuring system because its transfer behaviour is designed to be relatively flat and stable in both amplitude and phase up to 150 kHz, while scaling the primary voltage down to levels compatible with the acquisition instrument.

The divider output is acquired using a PicoScope 5400 series digital recorder, which acts as the digitizer of the reference chain. The instrument provides high-resolution waveform capture up to 15 bits and a sampling capability sufficient to support harmonic analysis up to 150 kHz. Using two simultaneously sampled channels, it enables synchronous acquisition of the relevant low-voltage signals so that RMS values and spectral components can be computed through dedicated post-processing.

Figure 73. FFII Reference Measuring System.

6.5.2 Characterization Tests

A series of metrological tests were carried out on the complete measuring system to quantify each source of potential error. The main tests, the methodology followed and the most relevant results are described below:

6.5.3 Frequency response

The measuring system is subjected to a frequency response characterization to obtain the ratio and the phase shift error dependent with frequency from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. The voltage is generated by a wideband power amplifier and a step-up transformer, capable of generating sinusoidal RMS voltages up to 500 V.

For the output ratio, the divider's output was measured using the PicoScope 5400 series digital recorder and compared against a reference digital multimeter. For the phase shift error, the divider's output was measured

using one channel of the Yokogawa WT5000 power analyser and compared against the other channel of the same instrument. Figure 74 and Figure 75 show the results of this characterization.

Figure 74. FFII reference measuring system output ratio frequency response.

Figure 75. FFII reference measuring system phase shift frequency response.

6.5.4 Short-Term Stability. Self-heating under DC stress

As an RC divider, it was observed that the resistances used for DC measurement would heat when subjected to DC application to verify that DC electrical stress and the associated self-heating do not modify the AC divider ratio. This test assessed the short-term stability of measuring system after prolonged DC energisation.

Two identical dividers were used. One divider was energised at 35 kV DC for 60 minutes and treated as the unit under test. The second divider was kept unenergized at ambient temperature and used as a reference. After 60 minutes, the DC source was removed, and a comparison measurement was performed between the heated divider and the reference divider by applying 500V RMS harmonics from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. Results are shown in Figure 76.

Figure 76. Output ratio changes due to self-heating.

6.5.5 Influence of High-Voltage conductor length

This test assessed the influence of the length of the high-voltage connection from the reference measuring system to the instrument under calibration. For this purpose, two identical dividers were energized in parallel. One divider was always connected in the same position, while the conductor length between dividers was increased from 0.3 m up to 3 m, separating the second divider from the reference divider. The outputs of both dividers were acquired simultaneously and compared to account for this effect. Results are shown in Figure 77.

The long lead introduced a small systematic under-reading with respect to the short-lead connection. Up to 100 kHz, the observed difference remained approximately 0.15 %. At 150 kHz, the deviation increased and reached about 0.4 %, with the divider connected through the 3 m lead reading lower. These results show that the high-voltage lead length can contribute a non-negligible error at the upper end of the frequency range and should be kept as short and as consistent as possible between reference and device under test during measurements up to 150 kHz.

Figure 77. Output ratio changes due to conductor between dividers length.

6.5.6 Influence of proximity of grounded structures

This test assessed whether nearby grounded structures influence the reference divider ratio through stray capacitance and electric field coupling. The divider was first measured in an open arrangement, with no large conductive objects close to it. A second configuration was then prepared by placing a grounded metallic plate at approximately 0.35 m from the divider. The same input voltages were applied in both configurations, and the divider output was compared against a reference multimeter. Results are shown in Figure 78.

Figure 78. Output ratio changes due grounded structures at 0.35 meters from the reference divider.

No measurable influence was observed. The divider output ratio remained the same, within the measurement uncertainty, when the grounded plate was introduced in the setup.

6.5.7 Estimation of Measurement Uncertainties

The main Type B uncertainty contributions for the measurement of the fundamental are as follows:

- uB1, Certified reference ratio. Uncertainty associated with the frequency response measurement to determine the ratio at different frequencies.
- uB2, Reference Linearity with Voltage. Possible variations of the reference divider scale factor with applied voltage level. Experimental tests showed that this effect is negligible for voltages from 300 V_{RMS} to 500 V_{RMS} .
- uB3, Short term stability. Possible variations of the reference divider scale factor due to thermal effects during prolonged DC stress. Experimental tests showed that this effect is negligible.
- uB4, Long term stability. Possible variations of the reference divider scale factor due to long-term drift between calibrations. No drift was observed in different experimental tests performed at different years during the during the project.
- uB5, Measuring instrument resolution and processing software. Includes uncertainties from the measuring instrument resolution and processing software and algorithms.
- uB6, High voltage lead length. Possible variations of the Represents the effect of HV cable length on measured voltage, due to additional inductance and capacitance. It is mainly relevant at the highest frequencies (≥ 100 kHz).

- uB7, Impedance mismatch. Possible variations of the reference digitizer input impedance, with respect to the DUT's own digitizer.

Table 6-4 and Table 6-5 summarize the uncertainty values, respectively, for amplitude and phase for 9 kHz and 150 kHz. The expanded uncertainties with a coverage factor $k = 2$ are also determined following equation (4).

Table 6-4. Calibration uncertainty of instrument transformers for amplitude

Contribution/Source	9 kHz Uncertainty contribution (%)	150 kHz Uncertainty contribution (%)
Certified Reference Ratio	0.05 %	0.23 %
Short Term Stability	0.005 %	0.005 %
Long Term Stability	0.005 %	0.005 %
Instrument resolution and software	0.006 %	0.006 %
High Voltage Lead Length	0.008 %	0.04 %
Impedance mismatch	0.006 %	0.006 %
Expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$)	0.1 %	0.5 %

Table 6-5. Calibration uncertainty of instrument transformers for phase

Contribution/Source	9 kHz Uncertainty contribution (crad)	150 kHz Uncertainty contribution (crad)
Certified Reference Ratio	0.15 crad	0.30 crad
Short Term Stability	0.02 crad	0.07 crad
Long Term Stability	0.02 crad	0.02 crad
Instrument resolution and software	0.06 crad	0.06 crad
High Voltage Lead Length	0.09 crad	0.60 crad
Proximity effect	0.02 crad	0.02 crad
Impedance mismatch	0.15 crad	0.15 crad
Expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$)	0.26 crad	0.8 crad

6.5.8 Conclusion

A high-frequency reference measuring system has been validated to extend accurate medium-voltage instrument transformer calibration into the supraharmmonic range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. The system employs a wideband high-voltage RC divider in combination with a high-resolution digital recorder.

Characterization tests have been performed to confirm the system's performance and identify key uncertainty influences. The complete reference system achieves expanded uncertainties ($k=2$) on the order of 0.1% (amplitude) and 0.26 crad (phase) at 9 kHz, increasing to approximately 0.5% and 0.8 crad at 150 kHz.

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6.6 UniCampania High Frequency Reference Device

This section describes the design, the realization and the characterization of the High Frequency Reference Device (HFRD), used as the voltage reference in the setup for the characterization of VTs realized at UniCampania and described in the deliverable D3. More details about this topic can be found in the paper [55].

6.6.1 HFRD design

A novel reference device (HFRD) was specifically developed for the characterization of VTs in the frequency range [9, 150] kHz when also a MV tone at the 50 Hz is included into the test waveform. Currently, some NMIs offer calibration services of voltage measuring devices in the frequency range [9, 150] kHz, but they are limited to voltage levels up to 100 V and make use of only sinewaves. To overcome this limitation, the proposed HFRD has a high-pass filtering behaviour, with a cutoff frequency of 5 kHz in order to attenuate in a significant way the amplitude of the 50 Hz component at MV level. Additionally, HFRD has to exhibit a quite flat response in the [9, 150] kHz range with a proper Scale Factor (SF) to ensure the reduction of tone amplitudes to levels compatible with the input stage of the acquisition system, typically within the range of ± 10 V. In the design of such a device, it is also necessary to consider the contribution of the impedance (typically a resistance in parallel with a capacitance) introduced by the input circuit of the acquisition system.

As a result, considering the resistances and the capacitances required to implement HFRD, those introduced by the acquisition system and the capacitance introduced in parallel to the step-up transformer, a device with a bandpass behaviour is obtained.

The simplified circuit diagram of HFRD is provided in Figure 79, where also the generation section is reported. In particular:

- C_s is the capacitance parallel connected to the SUT;
- C_f is the HFRD capacitance,
- R_1 and R_2 are the two resistances implementing the resistive part of the HFRD filter and, at the same time, the resistive voltage divider with a fixed SF;
- C_d and R_d represent the input capacitance and resistance of the acquisition system.

Figure 79. Simplified circuit diagram of the proposed generation and measurement setup.

In the case under analysis, R_d exceeds 100 G Ω , and thus it can be neglected, C_d is about 400 pF (including also the capacitance of the connection box and of the cable that connects it to the board) and R_1 is selected almost equal to 76 times R_2 to achieve a SF equal to about 77 V/V. By defining R_{tot} as the series of R_1 and R_2 and C_{tot} as the series of C_s and C_f , the transfer function of HFRD can be written as:

$$W(s) = \frac{sR_2C_sC_f(1/C_f + C_s)}{(1 + sR_{tot}C_{tot} + sR_2C_d + s^2R_1R_2C_{tot}C_d)} \quad (5)$$

This transfer function is characterized by one zero in $s = 0$ and, by approximating $R_{tot} \approx R_1$, two poles, having the associated time constants equal to $\tau_{p,1} = R_{tot}C_{tot}$ and $\tau_{p,2} = R_2C_d$.

Considering that the value of C_d is fixed and it depends on the acquisition system and that the value of C_s is set to meet the generation system requirements, C_f , R_1 and R_2 represent the only quantities that can be suitably selected to meet the design requirements. In this specific case, they are chosen as reported in Table 6-6, where also the cutoff frequency and the bandpass gain are provided.

Table 6-6. Reference filter parameters

Parameter	Value
C_F	275 pF
Maximum capacitor voltage	4 kV (AC voltage)
R_1	114.3 k Ω
R_2	1.5 k Ω
Bandpass gain	$\approx 1/80$
f_{cutoff}	≈ 5 kHz

6.6.2 Linear and non-linear parasitic effects of HFRD components

The resistors and the capacitors of HFRD can present linear and non-linear parasitic effects. For instance, the capacitive coupling (in the air) of the resistor terminals or the linear losses inside the capacitors can be considered linear effects; instead, the dependences of the resistance and of the capacitance on the amplitude of the applied voltages can be considered non-linear effects. Therefore, before the realization of HFRD, every single component was subjected to various kind of tests in order to quantify these effects.

The linear effects were quantified by analysing every single component through the Agilent (now Keysight) E4980A precision LCR meter, from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz. It was found that the best model for the resistors is a parallel connection of a resistance and of a capacitance; the parasitic capacitances are in the order ~ 100 fF for resistances in the order ~ 1 k Ω and ~ 10 k Ω . Instead, the best model for the capacitors is a series connection of a resistance and of a capacitance; the parasitic resistances are in the order ~ 0.1 Ω for capacitances in the order ~ 100 pF. Obviously, the presence of such linear parasitic effects alters the frequency behaviour of the components, making *Figure 79* and equation (5) be only approximated versions of, respectively, the circuit diagram and the transfer function of HFRD. However, the circuit diagram shown in *Figure 79* was numerically simulated, as it is and by including the measured linear parasitic effects. The maximum deviation between the magnitudes of the two simulated frequency responses was found lower than 0.25 %. For this reason, in order to not confuse the reader, *Figure 79* and equation (5) do not include the linear parasitic effects. It is worth to underline that this decision does not affect the accuracy of the results shown in the rest of the paper, that remain rigorous. In fact, although *Figure 79* and equation (5) neglect these effects, they are present in the physical realization of HFRD; thus, they are included in the frequency behaviour measured and treated as systematic effects, with the related measurement uncertainty, in the tests shown in previous section. As regards the possible temperature dependence of resistors and capacitors, the used laboratory has a temperature control system. Therefore, no temperature-dependent variations are expected.

For what concerns the non-linear parasitic effects of both resistors as well capacitors, they are linked to the slight non-linear behaviour of the dielectric materials used for the internal insulation of the capacitors and as covers for the resistors. For the case at hand, the electrical properties of the dielectric material mainly depend on the RMS amplitude of the electric field inside the material, that is on the RMS amplitude of the voltage applied to the component (i.e. the resistor or the capacitor).

Since the modelling of non-linear phenomena inside the electric components, like resistors and capacitors, is not the focus of the paper, these phenomena are not considered in *Figure 79* and equation (5). Instead, the impact of these effects on the HFRD performance and the associated uncertainty are accurately evaluated from an experimental point of view and the obtained results are discussed in previous section.

6.6.3 HFRD characterization

The metrological characterization of the proposed device (HFRD) should be performed in the real operating conditions, that is with waveforms composed by a 50 Hz tone at MV level and one or more frequency components, with lower amplitude, in the range of [9, 150] kHz. However, this implies the necessity to have a reference device, to determine the metrological performance of HFRD. As highlighted in HFRD design,

currently, to the best of the authors' knowledge, such a reference device is not available on the market nor at NMI level. This is why HFRD was developed.

Therefore, since in the frequency range [9, 150] kHz reference measurement instrumentation and procedures are available up to 100 V, the frequency behaviour of the proposed device has been measured at low voltage level. Some physical considerations can be made to justify this approach. HFRD is a passive device, made exclusively with resistors and capacitors, that have, at least nominally, a linear behaviour. Moreover, no resins or other insulation materials, with a possible non-linear behaviour, were used in the realization of HFRD. In addition, due to its high-pass frequency behaviour, the 50 Hz component at MV level is strongly attenuated; it mostly drops across the input capacitor of HFRD and just a residual part drops across the output resistive divider. It follows that: HFRD resistors always work at voltage levels in the order of tens of volt and their dissipated power at the maximum voltage is just a little fraction (lower than 0.1 %) of their power ratings.

Regarding the linear parasitic effects, since they do not depend on the applied voltage, their presence is accurately accounted when the HFRD frequency behaviour is measured at low voltage.

Following these considerations, the HFRD frequency behaviour has been measured at 7 V in the range [9, 150] kHz. Then, in order to consider possible dependency from the amplitude level, the ratio and phase errors at 50 Hz were measured at various amplitudes. Similar procedures, up to about 10 kHz, are commonly used by NMIs [54], [56]. The non-linear parasitic effects are instead accounted by executing specific tests on every single HFRD component and included in the uncertainty budget.

The measurement results are obtained by performing a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) over 10 cycles of the fundamental component as suggested by the International Standards [12], [11]. For each measurement, 31 iterations have been performed to evaluate the repeatability and stability according to GUM [57].

The SF and the phase error of HFRD are obtained as in equations (6) and (7):

$$SF_R(f) = \frac{V_p(f)}{V_s(f)} \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta\varphi_R(f) = \varphi_s(f) - \varphi_p(f) \quad (7)$$

where:

- $V_p(f)$ and $V_s(f)$ are the RMS values of the primary and secondary voltages at frequency f .
- $\varphi_p(f)$ and $\varphi_s(f)$ are the phase angles of the primary and secondary voltages at frequency f .

6.6.4 Low-voltage frequency characterization

In this test, HFRD was supplied directly by AWG1 and two DAQ channels are used to acquire the outputs of AWG1 and of HFRD. Figure 80 shows the measured SF (phase error) of HFRD in the range [50 Hz, 150 kHz], obtained by means of a frequency sweep with sinusoidal waveforms, having amplitude of 7 V, and according to equations (6) and (7). The initial high-pass behaviour, with a cut-off frequency of about 5 kHz, is clearly visible. Focusing on the high-frequency range, a low-pass trend, due to the parallel input capacitance of the comparator, that follows the nominal high-pass behaviour and becomes effective from about 50 kHz, can be observed. Indeed, the insets in Figure 80 show that, for frequency range from 50 kHz up to 150 kHz, the SF slightly raises, and the phase error drops below zero.

The uncertainties associated with SF_R ($\Delta\varphi_R$) have two contributions: the ratio (phase) error between the two DAQ channels (evaluated through a type B approach) and the repeatability and stability (evaluated through a type A approach). Nevertheless, the contribution from DAQ channels is negligible compared to the other contributions, especially at high frequencies.

Figure 80. Frequency behaviour of SF (a) and phase error (b) of HFRD

6.6.5 Voltage dependence at power frequency

As described in previous section, due to the possible voltage dependence of HFRD capacitor, possible deviations of HFRD behaviour, when it is used with an input voltage in the MV range rather than in the LV range, can occur. Therefore, in order to account for these possible deviations, HFRD has been tested at 50 Hz with increasing amplitudes from 10 % to 120 % of the rated voltage of the generation system. In this test, done at 50 Hz, LFRD was used as reference device.

Figure 81 shows the SF and the phase error deviations, at fundamental frequency and at different voltage amplitudes, with respect to the values obtained in the low voltage frequency characterization. It can be observed that the SF (phase error) deviation is lower than 0.05 % (within 0.8 mrad). These deviations of SF and phase error are included in the uncertainty associated to HFRD.

Figure 81. SF and phase error deviation, with respect to the value measured at 7 V, at fundamental frequency versus the percentage of rated setup voltage.

6.6.6 Impact of non-linear parasitic effects of HFRD resistors and capacitors

In this Section, results related to the quantification of non-linear parasitic effects of one single resistor and one single capacitor of HFRD are shown; similar results are obtained for all the other components.

As for the capacitor (C_{UT}), having a maximum applicable voltage of 700 V, the comparison method was used, like the one shown in [58], [59]. A reference capacitor (C_{REF}), calibrated at INRIM, having a maximum applicable

voltage of 34 kV is used. The same voltage is applied to C_{UT} and C_{REF} ; their currents are measured through two 8.5 digit Digital MultiMeters Fluke 8508, calibrated at INRIM. Since the applied voltages are the same, the ratio of the measured currents depends on the ratio of the capacitances. From the knowledge of the voltage dependence of C_{REF} (measured at INRIM), the voltage dependence of C_{UT} is measured.

Various waveforms are used:

- 1) a 50 Hz sinewave with amplitude from 100 V to 700 V;
- 2) a waveform with a fixed amplitude of 600 V composed by a 50 Hz fundamental tone and a 150 Hz and 30 % harmonic tone with variable phase;
- 3) a waveform with amplitude from 100 V to 700 V composed by a 50 Hz fundamental tone, a 10 kHz and 2 % tone, a 50 kHz and 1.2 % tone and a 150 kHz and 1 % tone.

It is worth to underline that the used waveforms represent realistic power system waveforms, and a wide variety of waveform amplitudes and shapes are involved. The maximum measured variation of C_{UT} in all the tests is lower than 0.031 %.

As regards the resistor (R_{UT}), subjected to a maximum voltage of 20 V (when 3.6 kV is applied to HFRD), the resistance was measured by using two 8.5-digit Fluke 8508 digital multimeters, one as voltmeter and one as ammeter. Various waveforms are used:

- 1) a 50 Hz sinewave;
- 2) a 10 kHz sinewave;
- 3) a 150 kHz sinewave;
- 4) a waveform composed by a 50 Hz tone, a 10 kHz and 2 % tone, a 50 kHz and 1.2 % tone, a 150 kHz and 1 % tone.

The RMS amplitudes are in the range [1, 20] V.

The maximum measured variation of R_{UT} in all the tests is lower than 0.032 %. These effects are treated as an uncertainty source and included in the uncertainty of \dot{G}_{HFRD} .

6.6.7 Uncertainty associated to HFRD

Four uncertainty sources have been identified for HFRD SF and phase error: 1) the contribution of DAQ channels (coming from INRIM calibration), 2) variation of the frequency behaviour with the input voltage amplitude, 3) the contribution of the non-linear parasitic effects of HFRD resistors and capacitors and 4) a contribution associated to repeatability and stability (evaluated through a type A approach). The DAQ contribution is negligible compared to the other three. As regards the input voltage contribution, it is evaluated by accounting the maximum SF and phase error deviations (see Figure 75). Similarly, the contribution of the non-linear parasitic effects is evaluated by accounting the deviations presented in previous section. The combined standard uncertainty on HFRD SF (phase error) goes from 600 $\mu\text{V/V}$ (630 μrad) at 9 kHz to 7.0 mV/V (6 mrad) at 150 kHz.

6.6.8 Frequency behaviour of a VT: measurement model and associated uncertainty budget

This section discusses the measurement model and the associated uncertainty related to the evaluation of the frequency behaviour of a VT. Referring to the measurement architecture of Figure 82, it is possible to express the complex gains of a DUT at fundamental frequency ($\dot{G}_{DUT,LF}$) and at high frequency ($\dot{G}_{DUT,HF}$), respectively, as in equations (8) and (9):

$$\dot{G}_{DUT,LF} = \frac{\bar{V}_{ch3} \dot{G}_{LFRD}}{\bar{V}_{ch1} \dot{G}_{LVD}} \dot{K}_{acq,31} \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{G}_{DUT,HF} = \frac{\bar{V}_{ch3} \dot{G}_{HFRD}}{\bar{V}_{ch2} \dot{G}_{LVD}} \dot{K}_{acq,32} \quad (9)$$

where:

- \bar{V}_{chX} is the phasor of the voltage acquired by the channel X of the DAQ;
- \dot{G}_{LFRD} is the complex gain of LFRD;
- \dot{G}_{HFRD} is the complex gain of HFRD obtained combining (3) and (4), $\dot{G}_{HFRD} = \frac{1}{SFR} e^{j\Delta\phi_R}$.
- \dot{G}_{LVD} is the complex gain of the LVD (it is present only in the case of inductive VTs or for any DUT with voltage output greater than the maximum input voltage of DAQ);
- $\dot{K}_{acq,jk}$ is the complex ratio between the gain of DAQ channel j and the DAQ channel k .

Figure 82. Basic block scheme of the proposed generation and measurement setup arranged at University of Campania

All the complex gains of equations (8) and (9) represent systematic deviations that are evaluated and compensated. The values of \dot{G}_{LFRD} , \dot{G}_{LVD} and $\dot{K}_{acq,jk}$ and the associated uncertainties are obtained by the INRIM calibration. The calibration of HFRD (\dot{G}_{HFRD}) has been previously discussed.

Table 6-7 reports, for each row, the uncertainty values, associated to a specific source, at various frequencies. Note that the contribution associated to \dot{G}_{LFRD} is present only in the first column because measurement model of equation (8) applies only at 50 Hz. Repeatability and stability (evaluated through a type A approach) on the complex ratios $\bar{V}_{chj}/\bar{V}_{chk}$ are also reported.

Table 6-7. Uncertainty budget of $u_\epsilon(\mu\text{V}/\text{V})$ and $u_{\Delta\phi}(\mu\text{rad})$

Source	Frequency (kHz)									
	0.05		9		50		100		150	
	u_ϵ ($\mu\text{V}/\text{V}$)	$u_{\Delta\phi}$ (μrad)								
\hat{G}_{LFRD}	50	50	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
\hat{G}_{HFRD}	-	-	600	630	1500	2100	5000	4000	7000	6000
\hat{G}_{LVD}	50	50	200	150	350	150	1300	350	1000	350
$\hat{K}_{acq,jk}$	40	40	40	40	120	120	400	400	400	400
Repeatability and Stability	10	10	30	50	60	150	100	300	200	300
u_c	82	82	630	650	1600	2100	5200	4000	7100	6000
U_c (95 %)	160	160	1300	1300	3200	4200	10000	8000	14000	12000

The last two rows of Table 6-7 report, respectively, the combined standard (u_c) and the expanded (U_c , level of confidence 95 %) uncertainties associated to \hat{G}_{DUT} . It can be noted that, especially at the higher frequencies, \hat{G}_{HFRD} is the main source of uncertainty. This is due to the effect of parasitic parameters, which becomes relevant at higher frequency and worsens the measurement repeatability, increasing, in turn, the uncertainty.

6.6.9 Frequency characterization of commercial Voltage Transformers

As an application of the realized measurement setup, the frequency characterization of two commercial VTs, a LPVT and an inductive VT was performed. The VTs' main features are summarized in Table 6-8.

The ratio and the phase errors of the VTs under test are measured as in equations (10) and in (11), respectively:

$$\epsilon(f) = \frac{k_r \cdot V_s(f)}{V_p(f)} - 1 \tag{10}$$

$$\Delta\phi(f) = \phi_s(f) - \phi_p(f) \tag{11}$$

where $k_r = \frac{V_{p,r}}{V_{s,r}}$ is the rated transformation ratio ($V_{p,r}$ and $V_{s,r}$ are the rated primary and secondary voltages).

The generated test waveforms are of FH1 type and composed by the fundamental tone at 50 Hz and 3 kV, one frequency tone having frequency in the range [9, 150] kHz and amplitude equal to 2 % of fundamental tone.

Table 6-8. Rated characteristics of the analyzed VTs

	Rated primary voltage (kV)	Rated secondary voltage (V)	Rated Burden (VA)	Accuracy class
LPVT	3	3	5	0.5
Inductive VT	3	100	20	0.5

6.6.10 Characterization of LPVT

The ratio and phase errors of the LPVT at 50 Hz are, respectively, 0.1 % and 600 μrad . Figure 83 shows the ratio and phase errors in the range [9, 150] kHz. It can be observed that the ratio error is within 10 % up to

130 kHz and equal to 11 % at 150 kHz. The phase error is within 0.1 rad up to 150 kHz. With reference to the accuracy classes extensions defined in [19], regarding the ratio error it can be observed that the LPVT totally meets the requirements of WB1 and WB2, whereas it only partially satisfies the requirements of WB3 and completely misses the ones of WB4. As regards the phase error, the LPVT meets the requirements of all the accuracy class extension, as the phase error is within $5.0^\circ = 0.087$ rad up to 150 kHz.

Figure 83. Ratio and phase errors versus frequency for the LPVT

6.6.11 Characterization of inductive VT

The ratio and phase errors of the inductive VT at 50 Hz are, respectively, 0.05 % and 500 μ rad. Figure 84 shows the ratio and phase errors in the range [9, 150] kHz. It can be observed that the ratio error is within ± 20 % up to 50 kHz. A first resonance occurs at about 12 kHz, whereas a second resonance, having a lower entity, at about 60 kHz. The last observable resonance occurs over 150 kHz. The phase error is within ± 0.4 rad up to 150 kHz. With reference to the accuracy class extensions defined in IEC 61869 International Standard Family, regarding the ratio error it can be observed that the inductive VT totally meets the requirements of WB1, whereas it completely misses the ones of WB2, WB3, and WB4. As regards the phase error, the inductive VT totally meets the requirements of WB1 and WB2, whereas it only partially satisfies the requirements of WB3 and WB4. The IEC 61869-1 ed.2 specifies that some extensions may not apply to some specific ITs. These results show that the extended accuracy class limit should not be applied to inductive VTs.

Figure 84. Ratio and phase errors versus frequency for the inductive VT

6.6.12 Conclusion

This Section has a voltage reference device realized and characterized at UniCampania. It is inserted in a novel generation and measurement setup for the frequency characterizations of MV VTs from 9 kHz up to

150 kHz. The proposed architecture represents an extension of the measurement setups commonly employed by NMIs to characterize VTs. The generation is obtained by a series connection between two generators, a high-frequency amplifier and a step-up transformer, used to generate the power frequency component at MV level. The measurement of the fundamental component and of the high frequency components are obtained through two different reference devices. A commercial divider is used as reference device for the measurement of the fundamental component. Instead, a new reference device, operating in the range [9, 150] kHz, is designed, realized and characterized. The maximum uncertainty obtained with the proposed setup in the frequency range from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz lower than 1.4 % and 1.2 crad (level of confidence 95 %) for the ratio and phase errors, respectively. In conclusion, the proposed generation and measurement setup allows for the characterization of inductive and low power VTs at power frequency and from 9 kHz to 150 kHz with waveforms having amplitudes at MV level.

7 Current measuring systems

7.1 VSL system

The VSL reference current measurement system is designed for the traceable characterisation of window-type current transformers (CTs) in the frequency range from 50 Hz up to 150 kHz, covering both steady-state single-frequency excitation and power-frequency currents with superimposed higher-frequency components. The system supports CT characterisation over a wide current range, with primary currents up to 2 kA at power frequency and reduced-amplitude current components of up to 20 A at the highest frequencies, consistent with the objectives of Task 3.2 of the ADMIT project.

The measurement principle is a ratio-based comparison method, in which the CT under test (DUT) is measured against a reference CT sensing the same primary current [60]. From the complex ratio of the simultaneously measured secondary currents, the magnitude ratio error and phase displacement of the DUT are obtained. This approach avoids the need for direct measurement of wideband high-current primary current and is well suited for the extended frequency range up to 150 kHz, as discussed in detail in [61].

For applications where reduced complexity is preferred and higher uncertainties are acceptable, a direct primary–secondary measurement method is also employed, in which both primary and secondary currents are measured simultaneously using a calibrated sampling power analyser. This second approach serves mainly routine measurements.

7.1.1 Current Generation

The current generation itself is not part of the reference measurement chain but provides the controlled excitation required for CT characterisation. At VSL, power-frequency currents up to 2 kA and high-frequency currents up to 150 kHz are generated using dedicated current sources and broadband amplifiers, as described in detail in previous section.

From the perspective of the measurement system, the current-generation part is characterised by two separate primary conductors fed through both the DUT and the reference CT: one for the power-frequency fundamental component and the other for the superimposed distortion components. The primary loops are designed to have low inductance to support high-frequency currents. During operation, controlled current ramp-up and stabilisation are applied before the data acquisition to ensure reproducible measurement conditions. Proper grounding is implemented at the low terminals of the CT secondary outputs to minimise common-mode effects and unwanted coupling.

7.1.2 Measurement System

The measurement system is entirely located on the secondary side of the CTs and is independent of the current generation hardware (see Figure 85).

Figure 85 Schematic representation of the measurement setup where a high-current source feeds both the DUT CT and the reference CT [3]. The secondary outputs are recorded using a power analyser for ratio comparison.

For ratio-based CT characterisation, the secondary currents of the DUT and the reference CT are measured simultaneously using a wideband sampling power analyser operated as a precision sampling ammeter. A Yokogawa WT5000 power analyser is used, equipped with interchangeable current input modules with selectable current ranges for secondary currents typically in the 0.2 A to 5 A range. The analyser measures the voltage drop across its internal shunts with synchronous sampling, allowing determination of both magnitude ratio and phase displacement of the secondary currents over the full frequency range up to 150 kHz. Since the ratio of two currents is measured, the gain error of the modules is cancelled by interchanging the two modules and repeating the measurement.

The reference CT in this system was an NRC electronically compensated CT with an accuracy of about 1 ppm at 50 Hz and a nominal turns ratio of 100:1. The CTs use internal compensation electronics to ensure low errors (less than 20 ppm and 20 μ rad) up to 5 kHz [53]. However, the internal feedback amplifier bandwidth restricts the effectiveness of compensation beyond a few kilohertz, which has an impact on high-frequency performance. This impact results in differences measured when two similar reference CTs with minor differences in feedback electronics are compared using this method, at which one of the two CTs is considered the reference and the other the DUT (see Fig. 2).

Figure 86 Magnitude ratio error and phase difference between secondary currents of CT A and CT B, measured using the ratio method with CT A as a reference. Up to 10 kHz, the magnitude ratio and phase displacement differences between the CTs is less than 10 ppm and 10 µrad, respectively. Increasing deviations are observed at higher frequencies

For the simplified primary–secondary measurement method, the same sampling power analyser is used to directly measure both the CT primary and secondary currents. Although this method results in higher uncertainties and is limited to primary currents of 30 A only, it provides a practical measurement chain for routine use for lower-current applications.

Figure 87 Primary-to-secondary current magnitude ratios and phase displacements of two similar reference CTs, A and B, measured using the direct measurement method at 10 A primary current. Differences become more pronounced above 10 kHz.

7.1.3 Traceability and Typical Uncertainties

Traceability of the VSL CT measurement setup is established through two complementary routes that share common calibrated references. Across both routes, frequency-dependent effects such as bandwidth limitations, phase shifts, and sampling-related errors are addressed through calibration data and correction models.

At high primary current levels, traceability is realised by direct comparison of the 100:1 reference CT against calibrated current shunts. The primary conductor is looped 20 times through the CT core to effectively increase the primary-to-secondary ratio, enabling operation at favourable secondary current and voltage levels. The secondary output of the reference CT is connected in series with a broadband calibrated 1 A shunt (1 Ω

nominal), while a broadband calibrated 5 A shunt (0.2 Ω nominal) provides the reference voltage in parallel. With 20 primary turns, a primary current of 5 A per turn produces 1 A at the CT secondary; the voltages across the 1 A and 5 A shunts are then nominally equal, providing ratio and phase comparison with low uncertainty. These voltages are measured with the synchronised voltage inputs of a broadband power analyser, and frequency-dependent amplitude and phase corrections of the shunts are shown to be negligible based on traceable calibration against resistance and AC current standards. Typical relative uncertainties achieved at 150 kHz with this route are of the order of parts in 10^4 and few tenths of mrad [3].

For applications where reduced complexity is preferred, traceability is achieved by measuring both primary and secondary current directly using the sampling ammeters of the power analyser, and obtaining the CT complex ratio error from the measured current ratio. In this route, calibration of the power analyser current channels is performed using the same 1 A and 5 A calibrated shunts, together with a calibrated AC voltage reference standard, to establish amplitude and phase accuracy of the sampling system across the relevant frequency range. The relative uncertainties at 150 kHz are typically the order of parts in 10^3 and few mrad, reflecting the simpler measurement chain and the additional dependence on analyser channel calibration and combined system effects.

7.2 METAS system

The METAS reference current measurement system is designed for the metrological characterization of window-type current transformers (CTs), with a particular focus on wideband performance up to 150 kHz. The measurement principle is based on a comparative approach between the primary current injected into the CT, measured using a high-precision shunt (reference), and the secondary current output by the CT, measured indirectly as a voltage signal.

The magnitude ratio error of the CT is determined by comparing the measured transformation ratio with the nominal ratio. The phase displacement is obtained from the phase difference between the primary and secondary signals.

To enable testing at high equivalent currents while maintaining wideband performance, the system uses multi-turn configurations on the primary side of the CT. This allows an increase of the effective primary current (typically, up to 2 kA) without requiring the current generation chain to deliver the full current directly.

7.2.1 Current Generation

The current generation chain consists of a function generator, defining the test signal waveform and frequency, and a transconductance amplifier, converting voltage into current. The amplifier is capable of delivering: up to 100 A with frequencies up to 100 kHz on high current ranges and up to 150 kHz on low current ranges. At higher frequencies, bandwidth limitations require a reduction of the output current magnitude. This limitation is mitigated by using multiple turns on the primary side of the CT. In this way, the system is capable of generating a primary current of 20 A at a frequency of 150 kHz using a 2 A input with 10 turns.

The amplifier output is equipped with connectors suitable for different current levels (125 A and 32 A), providing flexibility depending on the test configuration.

7.2.2 Measurement System

The measurement system is based on the simultaneous acquisition of primary and secondary signals using a high-precision power analyser such as the Yokogawa WT5000.

Figure 88 Schematic representation of the METAS measurement setup

The primary current is measured using high-precision shunts, which convert current into a proportional voltage. Special care is taken regarding Kelvin connections, minimization of parasitic inductance and thermal stability.

The CT secondary current is measured via a shunt providing a voltage proportional to the secondary current. Proper grounding is provided at the lower terminals of the CT's secondary outputs to minimize common-mode effects and unwanted coupling. Both primary and secondary voltages are acquired on the voltage inputs of the analyzer. The system enables amplitude measurement and phase difference determination. The different component of the measurement systems are calibrated at each combination of current magnitude and frequency of interest. Magnitude and phase corrections are applied to each measurement channel to compensate for systematic errors.

Figure 89 Magnitude ratio error and phase difference between secondary currents of CT and shunt. Increasing deviations are observed at higher frequencies.

7.2.3 Traceability and Typical Uncertainties

The metrological traceability of the system is ensured through the following element:

- The voltage inputs of the power analyzer are calibrated using a reference calibrator. Corrections are applied to account for gain errors and inter-channel phase deviations.
- The current shunts are calibrated by a specialized laboratory of METAS, ensuring traceability to the International System of Units (SI). Although the calibration is performed in DC, the shunts exhibit low frequency dependence, allowing their use in AC conditions with controlled uncertainty over the frequency range of interest.
- Additional uncertainty contributions arise from cable inductance and capacitance, electromagnetic coupling, multi-turn configurations (increased inductance and possible resonances).

The overall measurement system exhibits a typical relative uncertainty in amplitude on the order of a few hundreds ppm. This uncertainty is mainly dominated by the accuracy of the Yokogawa WT5000, with minor contributions from the calibrated shunts.

The typical phase uncertainty is on the order of a few tenths of milliradians, primarily limited by the inter-channel phase accuracy of the measurement instrument. Additional contributions from cabling and parasitic effects may become significant at higher frequencies.

7.3 FFII system

The FFII reference current measurement setup targets traceable characterization of current transformers over an extended bandwidth, from 50 Hz up to 150 kHz. The setup is intended to cover both single-frequency steady-state excitation and power frequency operation with superimposed higher-frequency components. The applicable current range spans up to 2 kA at power frequency, while the injected high-frequency components are generated at reduced amplitude, up to 50 A from 9 kHz to 150 kHz.

The primary CT characterization at FFII is based on a ratio comparison: the DUT and the reference CT are subjected to the same primary current, and their secondary currents are acquired synchronously. The DUT ratio error and phase displacement are then obtained from the complex ratio between the two measured secondary currents. The reference CT used at FFII are a Tettex model 4764CL for 50 Hz and a Fluke i800s for 9 kHz to 150 kHz, and the acquisition, ratio evaluation and phase displacement measurements are performed with a Yokogawa WT 5000.

7.3.1 Current Generation

In the FFII setup, there are two primary conductors passing through both the DUT and the reference CT. One of the conductors is included in a loop that carries the power frequency current, while the second conductor is included in a second loop that carries the superimposed component.

A dedicated high current source composed of numbers of feeds the 50 Hz loop. The harmonic components are generated by a calibrator fluke 5500, which feeds a power amplifier Ae Techron 9110, which feeds the high frequency current loop. Figure 90 shows a drawing and a picture of the calibration test setup.

Figure 90 Drawing of the calibration test setup.

7.3.2 Measurement System

The fluke i800s is a ferrite core current clamp connected to a calibrated resistance with a nominal output ratio of 10 mV/A. It was selected as the main reference equipment for the reference measuring system due to its linear and stable behavior throughout the frequency wide-band up to 150 kHz.

Figure 91 and Figure 92 show the scale factor and phase error of the probe throughout the frequency.

Figure 91 Reference measuring system magnitude ratio error.

Figure 92 Reference measuring system phase error.

Data acquisition is performed with the Yokogawa WT5000’s Data Streaming feature to save waveform in an external computer. The waveform is then analyzed using a sinusoidal wave fitting algorithm to isolate the high-frequency component and enhance waveform resolution. Ratio magnitude and phase displacement are calculated using a signal correlation method.

Figure 93 shows a comparison of the sinusoidal fitting with a wideband pass filter, suppressing the fundamental 50 Hz component. It is observed that the fitted signal maintains the waveform parameters while eliminating background noise.

Figure 93 Comparison of wave analysing methods

7.3.3 Traceability and Typical Uncertainties

The metrological traceability of the system is ensured through the calibration of the current clamp is against a coaxial shunt TRANSMILLE AC/DC 100A. This shunt is calibrated from 50 Hz to 100 kHz and its AC/DC ratio is characterized to be in the ppm range through all frequencies.

The combined uncertainty for the current transformation ratio is $\pm 0.39\%$ at 9 kHz and $\pm 2.7\%$ at 150 kHz. The combined uncertainty for the overall phase displacement of the calibration set up is 0.9 crad in all frequencies.

7.4 RISE system

At RISE an AC current generation system has been developed using two current sources suitable for calibration of window type measurement systems. One source generates 50 to 1 kHz up to 2 kA and the other source generates supraharmonics from 2 to 20 kHz up to 100 A and 20 A for frequencies up to 150 kHz. The device under test (DUT) is then connected to both sources.

7.4.1 Current Generation

A Chroma 61605 is computer controlled in frequency and amplitude via a DA converter, e.g. NI USB 6216, which current is feeding a Nokia step-up transformer. The computer interface can either lock-in to the local power frequency or be run at 50 or 60 Hz with a general mixture of harmonics up to 2 kHz synchronized or free-running via an Agilent 33500B.

One generator is injecting the fundamental 50 Hz combined with an odd harmonic, e.g. 150 Hz, 250 Hz, ... using the Chroma 61605. This at the same time combined with supraharmonic frequencies is generated with the Clarke-Hess 8200 close to 2 kHz, 5 kHz, 10 kHz and 20 kHz up to 100 A, and 50 kHz, 100 kHz and 150 kHz up to 20 A, while avoiding multiples of the fundamental frequency. The limiting factor for the currents above 20 kHz was the compliance voltage from the inductance in the loop where the Clarke-Hess 8200 can drive up to 7 V.

7.4.2 Measurement System

A HITEC Zero-Flux core is used for measurement of the signals from the line frequency and harmonics thereof. The signal is sampled by one of the PXIe-6396 channels measuring the line frequency and harmonics current.

Figure 94 Schematic of the RISE set-up.

The supraharmonics are generated from a computer-controlled Keysight 33500B driving a modified Clarke-Hess 8200 amplifier. In this manner a line frequency/phase and frequency independent current with single frequency or spectrum of supraharmonics is generated from 2 to 150 kHz. From a 100A DSWM current shunt type CS2D (RISE model) the voltage is sampled by one of the PXIe-6396 channels measuring the supraharmonic current. The computer program gives the fundamental and/or one or several harmonics feeding the Chroma 61605 generator and a mixture of supraharmonics to the Clarke Hess. The fundamental can be synchronized with the grid line frequency. The set-up is shown in Figure 94.

The components in figure and their functions are the following:

- Core controller - LabVIEW program "Follower": This program generates signals for the testing and slowly ramps up and down the currents to avoid overvoltage from inductances or transients. The program also collects the signals from the three CTs via a PXIe-6396 digitizer.
- Digitizer PXIe-6396: The signals from the reference CTs, i.e. a HITEC 500/2000 or 6000A (peak current) measuring the line frequency and harmonics and a current shunt RISE CS2D measures the supraharmonics up to 100 A, are sampled by this digitizer. The digitizer has 8 channels simultaneously sampled, 18 bits resolution and a sampling rate up to 15 MS/s. Supraharmonics are sampled at least with a sampling rate = 2^n , larger than $5 \cdot 150$ kS/s (7 periods), which is $2^{20} = 1.05$ MS/s. This choice is for adaptation to the FFT analysis to avoid spectral leakage. The sampling length is dictated by the line frequency, i.e. a duration of at least 7 periods of 50Hz = 140 ms, rounded to 200 ms, about 200 kS.
- Arbitrary Waveform Generator (Agilent 33500B): Samples the power line frequency for generation of true voltage and harmonics via a computer controller (LabVIEW "follower"). The 33500B generates the waveshapes for supraharmonics and controls the output of the generator Clarke-Hess 8200.
- Arbitrary Waveform Generator (NI-USB 6216): Provides a wave shape output with programmable amplitude and frequency (50 Hz to 1 kHz). This signal can be synchronized to the line frequency and can contain harmonics with amplitude and relative phase.
- A Chroma type 61605 4 kVA generator is used to generate currents controlled by the NI-USB 6216 arbitrary wave form generator via an external input from 15 – 1000 Hz with 32A/20A (150V/300V) ranges. Using a step-up transformer 100:1 the maximum current is 3.2 kA.
- A modified transconductance amplifier Clarke-Hess 8200 is used for generation of supraharmonics up to 150 kHz. The amplifier can generate 100 A up to 20 kHz and 20 A up to 150 kHz, limited by the compliance voltage of 7V. The waveshape of the amplifier is controlled by the computer program via an Agilent 33500B.

7.4.3 Results

The Current sensor Pearson 301X was used to test the system. This sensor can measure up to 400 A and is designed for impulse current measurements. A mixed signal of 50 and 150 Hz, with amplitudes up to 365 A @ 50 Hz and 35 A @ 150 Hz was generated with the Chroma 61605 + transformer and several supraharmonic signals around 20 A from 2 to 150 kHz were injected with the Clarke-Hess 8200. In Figure 95 the ratio error and phase error are plotted. The Pearson 301X is apparently not very good at lower frequencies which was expected from the impulse design. For the supraharmonics it behaves well and is within 0.08% for the ratio and within 3% phase error. calibrations

Figure 95 Results for a Pearson 301X impulse current sensor.

A Rogowski coil PEM CWT15 was selected for use in substation monitoring. Results are 0.03% ratio error and 22 mrad phase displacement at 50 Hz. The frequency dependence is to be characterized.

7.4.4 Traceability and Typical Uncertainties

Traceability of the measurement systems of RISE is ensured by the calibration of a HITEC Zero-Flux 2000 A up to 1 kA and 1 kHz, or a HITEC Zero-Flux 6000 A up to 2 kA and 1 kHz, using a step-up procedure referenced to the primary 100A DSWM current shunt type CS2D. From the HITEC Zero-Flux the traceability for the DUT of the line frequency and harmonics up to 1 kHz is realised. Traceability for the supraharmonics 9 – 150 kHz is realised by the 100A DSWM current shunt type CS2D itself.

The 8 ch simultaneous sampling digitizer PXIe 6396 is traceable up to 150 kHz from Fluke calibrator 5700A. The time lag between the channels is mapped for contribution to phase uncertainties from the current sensors. The expanded measurement uncertainty from PXIe-6396 is better than 180, 330, 800 and 1500 $\mu\text{V/V}$ for 1, 2, 5 and 10 V range. Using a For HITEC 2000 an expanded measurement uncertainty of 1500 $\mu\text{V/V}$ with max 1.4 kA fundamental freq. Instead, using a HITEC Zero-flux 6000A core, 2 kA rms can be sampled with the 5V range and hence 800 $\mu\text{V/V}$, which is the selection for the system. The phase uncertainty for the 6000A core is 1.0 mrad

The chosen DUT, the PEM CWT15 has a sensitivity 2 mV/A. for supraharmonics typical voltage levels observed are 40 A at 45 kHz, which translates to 80 mV output and the 1V range of the PXIe-6396 with an exp unc. of 180 $\mu\text{V/V}$. The noise level of the PEM is 7 mV max pk-pk, which gives an uncertainty contribution of 3%. Using the designed bandpass amplifier with 10x amplification the output increase to 800 mV. For this the 2V range is used with 0.033 % uncertainty and a 0.3% noise contribution. Increasing the amplification to 50x the output is 4 V with an uncertainty of 0.08 % and noise contribution of 0.06%. The conclusion is that for matching of noise from the PEM with the digitizer uncertainty the amplification in the bandpass filter will be optimal for 50x. Since we are analysing the signals using FFT the noise is suppressed by 20 dB or more, thus reducing the amplification to 10x the noise is reduced to contribute 0.03% or less, which would be an optimal trade-off.

100A DSWM current shunt type CS2D the expanded measurement unc. at 150 kHz is 0.0150% for the ratio and 2.5 mrad for the phase angle.

The combined expanded uncertainty for the calibration of ratio at 150 kHz is $< \pm 0.16\%$ and phase displacement is 2.5 mrad. The combined expanded uncertainty for the calibration of ratio < 1 kHz is $< \pm 0.02\%$ and phase displacement is 1 mrad.

7.5 VTT system

VTT system for generation and measurement of 50 Hz fundamental and harmonics is show in Figure 96. A signal with up to 10 frequency components is created, and it is uploaded to the two-channel arbitrary waveform generator (AWG, Keysight 33500B). One channel of the AWG feeds the transconductance amplifier (Guildline 7620), and the other channel provides a synchronized trigger signal to the two-channel digitizer (Applicos

WFD20). A wideband shunt is used as the reference for calibration of current sensors or shunts. The system is controlled by a PC.

As the sampling is coherent with the multitone reference signal, no windowing is needed, and each generated harmonic will fall in one FFT bin without spectral leakage.

Figure 97 shows an example of a recorded frequency response of a wideband current sensor (Pearson 110A) between 50 Hz and 150 Hz.

Figure 96 VTT multitone generation and measurement setup.

Figure 97 An example of a measured multitone waveform. Even though the signal level is low, the signal-to-noise ratio is c. 75 dB.

7.5.1 High-current low frequency system

This multitone current-generation system can be used together with the VTT high-current system for power-frequency calibration. The high-current generator has a bandwidth up to 1 kHz, and it can generate up to 8 kA

at 50 Hz. This system can be used together with the multitone system for calibration of supraharmonics of window type measurement systems. One source generates 50 Hz or 60 Hz up to 8 kA and the other source generates supraharmonics from DC to 100 kHz up to 20 A and 2 A for frequencies up to 1 MHz. The device under test (DUT) is then connected to both sources.

7.5.2 Traceability and Typical Uncertainties

The metrological traceability of the system is ensured through the set of wideband reference shunts. The shunts are calibrated from 50 Hz to 100 kHz and their AC/DC ratio is characterized to be in the ppm range through all frequencies.

The combined uncertainty for the ratio is less than 0.1% up to 150 kHz. The combined uncertainty for the overall phase displacement of the calibration set up is less than 2 crad in the same frequency range.

7.6 Traceability and Measurement Uncertainty

7.6.1 General Traceability Concepts

The reference current measurement systems described in Section 4 have been developed to provide traceable characterisation of current transformers over an extended range of current and frequency up to 150 kHz. Although the technical implementations differ between the participating laboratories, the traceability follows a common metrological approach. In all cases, the measurement result is linked to the SI through calibrated electrical quantities such as resistance, voltage, current, and time or frequency, combined with frequency-dependent characterisation of the reference sensors and acquisition channels.

At VSL, for example, traceability is realised either by direct comparison of a 100:1 reference CT with calibrated 1 A and 5 A broadband shunts, or by direct primary–secondary measurement using a calibrated wideband power analyser. At METAS, traceability is established through calibrated current shunts and calibrated voltage channels of the analyser. At FFII, the wideband clamp used as reference is calibrated against a coaxial AC/DC shunt. At RISE, the traceability chain combines zero-flux current transformers, a broadband current shunt, and a calibrated digitiser. At VTT, traceability is based on a set of wideband reference shunts whose AC/DC ratio has been characterised over the relevant frequency range.

7.6.2 Reference Sensors

A key outcome of Task 3.2 is the identification, development, and use of suitable reference current sensors for wideband traceable measurements. The implemented systems use several classes of reference elements, each with its own advantages and limitations. These include electronically compensated reference CTs, zero-flux current transformers, broadband current shunts, Hall-effect current transducers, wideband current clamps, and Rogowski-type current sensors. The choice of reference element depends on the current range, required bandwidth, target uncertainty, and practical complexity of the measurement chain.

For the highest current levels, reference CTs remain attractive because they allow scaling of kiloampere primary currents to manageable secondary currents without dissipating large amounts of power in shunts. This principle is used, for example, in the VSL system, where the DUT is compared against an NRC electronically compensated reference CT, and in the RISE setup, where HITEC zero-flux current transformers are used for the fundamental and lower harmonics. These reference transformers provide very low errors at low frequency, but their high-frequency behaviour depends on the bandwidth of internal feedback and compensation electronics. The report therefore makes clear that their use above a few kilohertz requires dedicated characterisation and careful uncertainty assignment.

Broadband current shunts are used either as the primary reference element or as a calibration artefact within the traceability chain. Their main advantage is a well-defined current-to-voltage transfer with comparatively simple modelling of frequency dependence. This is the basis of the METAS and VTT systems and also forms part of the VSL and RISE traceability routes. Wideband shunts are particularly suitable for frequencies above several kilohertz, but at very high current levels they are less practical because of dissipation and construction constraints.

7.6.3 Comparator Systems

The required comparator functionality is realised in different ways. VSL, METAS, and FFII use a Yokogawa WT5000 wideband power analyser as a synchronous sampling comparator, measuring either two secondary currents directly or current-related voltages derived from shunts. RISE uses a multi-channel PXIe-6396 digitiser with simultaneous sampling, allowing coherent analysis of multiple channels over a broad frequency range. VTT uses an Applicos WFD20 digitiser in combination with coherent multitone generation. In all cases, one essential development has been the extension of the comparator functionality beyond the classical 50/60 Hz range toward at least 150 kHz, including attention to channel gain, inter-channel phase deviation, synchronisation, and spectral processing.

The upgrades reported in this deliverable are therefore not limited to a single comparator hardware design. Rather, they comprise the development of complete wideband comparator systems, including calibrated input channels, synchronised acquisition, suitable signal ranges, and processing methods capable of determining ratio and phase over the full frequency range of interest. This is one of the key technical results of the work described in Section 4.

7.6.4 Frequency Dependent Effects

At frequencies up to 150 kHz, the uncertainty is influenced not only by the calibration of the reference sensor itself, but also by the combined effect of cables, grounding arrangements, parasitic inductances and capacitances, burden conditions, and the bandwidth of the acquisition channels. In several of the reported systems, these effects become the dominant contributors to the uncertainty above approximately 10 kHz.

For this reason, all participating laboratories explicitly characterise frequency-dependent effects in their traceability chains. Examples include calibration of shunts over frequency, calibration of analyser voltage or current channels using reference calibrators, mapping of inter-channel time delay in digitiser systems, and evaluation of the influence of cable routing, connector choice, and grounding. In the VSL wideband CT system, practical setup choices such as range selection, cabling, and grounding were found to have a measurable impact on the final uncertainty. At METAS, corrections are applied to account for gain and phase errors in the measurement channels. At RISE, the digitiser timing and the channel-to-channel phase behaviour are explicitly included.

7.6.5 Uncertainty Evaluation Methodology

The uncertainty evaluations associated with the reference current measurement systems follow the general principles of the Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM), in which all relevant input quantities are identified, quantified, and propagated to the measurand. Depending on the system, the measurand is either the complex ratio error of the DUT relative to a reference current sensor or the ratio and phase relationship between the primary and secondary quantities of the DUT. In both cases, the uncertainty associated with the result is frequency dependent and, in some cases, also current dependent.

The dominant uncertainty contributions reported in Section 4 may be grouped into several categories:

- Reference sensor uncertainty, including amplitude and phase uncertainty of the reference CT, current shunt, current clamp, or other reference device.
- Acquisition system uncertainty, including gain error, linearity, inter-channel phase deviation, timing error, and range-selection effects of the power analyser or digitiser.
- Frequency-dependent setup effects, such as cable impedance, connector repeatability, parasitic inductive or capacitive coupling, grounding arrangements, and burden effects.
- Signal-related effects, including signal-to-noise ratio, repeatability, residual drift, waveform stability, and spectral leakage or fitting residuals in the signal-processing stage.
- Scaling and auxiliary elements, such as multi-turn arrangements, current buffers, compensation electronics, and any auxiliary ratio stages required to bring the signals into a suitable range.

In the lower-frequency range, uncertainty is often dominated by the calibration of the reference sensor and by the gain and phase accuracy of the instrument channels. At higher frequencies, setup-dependent phase effects, bandwidth limitations, and parasitic couplings become increasingly important. This trend is visible

throughout the systems described in Section 4: VSL reports uncertainties of the order of parts in 10^{-4} for the shunt-supported high-accuracy route at 150 kHz, while simplified direct measurement routes are closer to parts in 10^{-3} . METAS reports amplitude uncertainties of a few hundred parts in 10^{-6} and phase uncertainties of a few tenths of a milliradian. RISE reports combined expanded uncertainties below 0.16 % and 2.5 mrad at 150 kHz, and VTT reports ratio uncertainties below 0.1 % up to 150 kHz. FFII reports higher uncertainties, reaching the percent level at the top of the frequency range, consistent with the chosen reference transducer and measurement chain.

A complete uncertainty budget should therefore always be provided together with the specific measurement configuration to which it applies. In practice, multiple budgets may be needed for a single system, for example as a function of frequency band, current range, or chosen traceability route. This is especially relevant when a system offers both a high-accuracy reference mode and a simplified routine-measurement mode.

7.6.6 Example Uncertainty Budget

The uncertainty budgets described by the partners are not fully uniform in structure, because the systems differ in architecture and intended use. The following tables provide illustrative examples of uncertainty budgets for magnitude (ratio) and phase displacement at a frequency of 150 kHz. The values are indicative and are intended to demonstrate a suitable structure for reporting and interpreting uncertainty contributions in wideband current measurements.

Table 7-1 Typical uncertainty budget for magnitude

Source of uncertainty (magnitude)	Evaluation method	Standard uncertainty
Reference sensor calibration	Type B	50 ppm
Acquisition channel gain ratio	Type B	80 ppm
Cable and connector effects	Type B	100 ppm
Grounding / parasitic coupling	Type B	80 ppm
Signal processing / fitting residuals	Type B	40 ppm
Repeatability	Type A	30 ppm

Table 7-2 Typical uncertainty budget for phase

Source of uncertainty (phase)	Evaluation method	Standard uncertainty
Reference sensor calibration	Type B	0.10 mrad
Inter-channel phase deviation	Type B	0.15 mrad
Cable and connector phase effects	Type B	0.10 mrad
Grounding / parasitic coupling	Type B	0.10 mrad
Signal processing / fitting residuals	Type B	0.05 mrad
Repeatability	Type A	0.05 mrad

For this example, the combined standard uncertainty in amplitude is of the order of 150–200 ppm, and the combined standard uncertainty in phase is of the order of 0.2–0.3 mrad. Using a coverage factor $k = 2$, the resulting expanded uncertainty would be of the order of 300–400 ppm in amplitude and 0.4–0.6 mrad in phase. These values are representative of a well-characterised high-accuracy wideband ratio system and are broadly consistent with the best performance levels reported in Section 4. By contrast, simplified systems or systems employing reference sensors with stronger frequency dependence may yield substantially larger uncertainties, especially near the upper end of the investigated frequency range.

7.6.7 Discussion and Conclusion

The reference current measurement systems developed within Task 3.2 enable traceable characterisation of current transformers up to 2 kA and frequencies up to 150 kHz. The presented approaches demonstrate that both high-accuracy comparator-based systems and simplified sampling-based methods can be extended into the supraharmmonic frequency range, provided that frequency-dependent effects are properly characterised and accounted for.

The achieved uncertainties, ranging from parts in 10^{-4} for high-accuracy reference systems to parts in 10^{-3} for simplified methods, are suitable for the intended applications and provide a solid metrological basis for further development of calibration services.

The results establish a sound foundation for future work on wideband instrument transformer calibration and contribute to ongoing standardisation efforts in this field.

8 Recommendations for IEC/CENELEC TC38

The results obtained within the ADMIT project provide a coherent and experimentally validated framework for the characterization of instrument transformers (ITs) under high-frequency conditions, extending up to 150 kHz. These outcomes directly address a limitation of the current IEC 61869 standard series, which does not fully address the behaviour of instrument transformers in the presence of supraharmonic and fast-transient phenomena.

Based on these findings, several recommendations can be formulated to support IEC and CENELEC TC38 in future standardization activities. These recommendations are not intended as prescriptive requirements but rather as a structured contribution based on validated experimental evidence and measurement experience, aimed at facilitating the evolution of existing standards or the development of new normative documents.

A first key aspect emerging from the project concerns the frequency range that should be considered in future standards. The analysis of both the literature and experimental campaigns confirms that disturbances in modern medium-voltage networks extend well beyond the harmonic range currently addressed by standards. In particular, emissions associated with power electronic devices are typically observed in the supraharmonic range, extending up to several tens of kilohertz, with components approaching 150 kHz under specific conditions.

In this context, it appears appropriate that future revisions of the IEC 61869 series take into account this extended frequency range, ensuring that the behaviour of instrument transformers is assessed under conditions representative of actual grid operation.

Closely related to this aspect is the need to define representative test conditions. The project activities have contributed to the identification of characteristic waveforms and frequency components that are relevant for testing purposes. These include not only single-frequency sinusoidal components, but also more complex conditions such as multi-frequency signals and transient waveforms, which better reproduce the disturbances generated by modern equipment installed in the grid.

From a standardization perspective, the introduction of test profiles that reflect these conditions would improve the relevance of laboratory testing and support more meaningful comparisons between different instrument transformer technologies.

Another important outcome of the project concerns the definition of accuracy requirements in wideband conditions. At present, the performance of instrument transformers is mainly specified at power frequency, with limited consideration of harmonic components and no comprehensive treatment of higher-frequency behavior.

The results obtained in the project demonstrate that it is feasible to characterize both ratio error and phase displacement across an extended frequency range with controlled uncertainty. This suggests that future standards could benefit from a more detailed, frequency-dependent description of accuracy, enabling performance evaluation consistent with the intended application, whether for power quality measurement, protection, or monitoring.

The experimental work carried out within the project also highlights the importance of harmonizing test methods and measurement setups. The developed generation and measurement systems have demonstrated adequate performance in terms of stability, repeatability, and achievable uncertainty across the frequency range considered.

These results indicate that it would be beneficial for standardization bodies to guide reference test configurations and procedures. Such guidance would facilitate reproducibility of results across laboratories and help reduce discrepancies arising from different test implementations, ultimately strengthening confidence in the assessment of instrument transformer performance.

A further aspect that emerges clearly from the project is the role of uncertainty evaluation and traceability. The characterization of ITs in the supraharmonic range requires a rigorous metrological approach, including the identification and quantification of uncertainty contributions associated with both generation and measurement systems.

In this respect, the inclusion of appropriate guidance within standards, together with the definition of suitable uncertainty targets and the requirement for traceability to national standards, would significantly improve the reliability and comparability of measurement results.

Regarding the practical implementation of these developments, integration into the IEC 61869 standard series is a key step. The results of the project appear suitable either for incorporation into existing parts of the standard by introducing additional clauses addressing extended frequency behavior, or for inclusion in new dedicated documents focusing on wideband applications. Both approaches may be considered depending on the desired structure and level of flexibility, and their evaluation could form part of future discussions within TC38.

It should also be noted that the issues addressed in the project are not limited to a single technical domain, but are closely connected to activities carried out by other IEC Technical Committees dealing with electromagnetic compatibility, grid integration, and measurement systems.

For this reason, continued coordination and alignment between IEC TC38 and other relevant committees would appear beneficial to ensure consistency in the definition of frequency ranges, test signals, and measurement methodologies, and to avoid fragmentation in the standardization framework.

Finally, the evolution of modern power systems highlights the growing importance of applications requiring wideband characterization of instrument transformers. These include, among others, power quality monitoring systems, traveling-wave-based protection schemes, and advanced diagnostic and monitoring functionalities. The results of the project suggest that future standards could more explicitly take these applications into account, linking performance requirements and test conditions to specific use cases.

In conclusion, the outcomes of the ADMIT project demonstrate that characterizing instrument transformers over the extended frequency range up to 150 kHz is technically feasible using traceable and reproducible methods.

The recommendations presented in this section are intended to support IEC/CENELEC TC38 in addressing current gaps in standardization and guiding the development of future standards aligned with the evolving requirements of modern electrical networks.

10 Bibliography

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